

Deliverable 2.1

Review Results and Final Version of the Scalability Assessment Framework and Criteria

23 December 2024

Giovanni Maccani
Paola Zanchetta
Javier Creus

Document details

Project Acronym / Name	CROPS: Curating, Replicating, Orchestrating, and Propagating Citizen Science across Europe
Project URL	http://crops-cs.eu
Project Type	Coordination and Support Action (CSA)
EU Call	HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01
Grant Agreement No.	101131696
Project Start Date	1 January 2024
Project end date	31 December 2026
Work Package	
Work Package	WP2 - Curation: Appraisal of current CS actions and their suitability for upscaling
Deliverable	
Deliverable	Deliverable 2.1: Review Results and Final Version of the Scalability Assessment Framework and Criteria
Due date of Deliverable	31/12/2024
Actual Submission date	23/12/2024
Lead Beneficiary for this deliverable	Ideas For Change (IFC)
Reviewed by	All partners
Revision	5.0
Dissemination level	Public
Number of pages	87 (excluding appendices)

Document history			
Version	Date	Comment	Modification made by
1.0	September 2024	First Draft and table of content	Paola Zanchetta, Giovanni Maccani, Javier Creus (IFC)
2.0	October 2024	Review and comments	Dilek Fraisl (IIASA) Mariana Malta, Catarina Azevedo (INOVA+)
3.0	09/12/2024	First Full Draft Shared	Paola Zanchetta, Giovanni Maccani, Javier Creus (IFC)
4.0	15/12/2024	Review, feedback and comments	James Sprinks (Earthwatch) Dilek Fraisl (IIASA) Arianna Liconti (OutBe) Julia Lotina (EUN)
5.0	19/12/2024	Integration of feedback and final version	Paola Zanchetta, Giovanni Maccani, Javier Creus (IFC)

To cite this document:

Giovanni Maccani, Paola Zanchetta, Javier Creus. Deliverable 2.1: Review Results and Final Version of the Scalability Assessment Framework and Criteria, December 2024, Deliverable report of project Horizon Europe CROPS (grant agreement No. 101131696)

Copyright

© Partners of the CROPS Consortium, 2024

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Contents

1 Introduction	8
1.1 The Task	9
1.2 Structure of this document	10Z
2 Defining the Scope: Definitions, Approach & Methodology	12
2.1 What do we mean by upscaling?	12
2.2 Across the spectrum of citizen participation, what do we recognise to be CS projects?	14
2.3 What do we mean by “CS Project”?	15
2.4 What fields and disciplines do we consider?	16
2.5 What geographical scope do we consider?	16
2.6 What do we aim to upscale?	17
2.7 What are the key factors to be considered when assessing upscaling potential? The CROPS Upscaling Framework	18
3 The Review	23
3.1 Search strategy	23
3.2 Selection/Inclusion criteria	26
3.3 Data extraction - what data we extracted and why	26
4 Preliminary Findings	32
4.1 A Soil Deal for Europe	33
4.1.1. Introduction to the Mission	33
4.1.2 CS Projects contributing to the Soil Mission	34
4.1.3 CS and Soil Mission: A Summary So Far	40
4.2 Adaptation to Climate Change	42
4.2.1 Introduction to the Mission	42
4.2.2 CS Projects Contributing to the Adaptation to Climate Change Mission	43
4.2.3 CS and Adaptation to Climate Change Mission: A Summary So Far	48
4.3 Climate Neutral Smart Cities	49
4.3.1. Introduction to the Mission	49
4.3.2 CS Projects Contributing to the Smart Cities Mission	50
4.3.3 CS and the Climate Neutral Smart Cities Mission: A Summary So Far	55
4.4 Restore our Ocean and Waters	57
4.4.1. Introduction to the Mission	57
4.4.2 CS projects contributing to the Ocean and Waters Mission	58
4.4.3 CS and Ocean and Waters Mission: A Summary So Far	71
4.5 Cancer Mission	73
4.5.1. Introduction to the Mission	73
4.5.2 CS projects contributing to the Cancer Mission	73
4.5.3 CS Projects from the wider healthcare domain	78
4.5.4 CS and the Cancer Mission: A Summary So Far	80

5 Conclusions, Limitations and Future Work	83
5.1 Next Steps	84
5.2 Limitations	85
References	88
Appendix 1 “A Soil Deal for Europe” Mission’s projects	91
Appendix 2. “Adaptation to Climate Change” Mission’s projects	115
Appendix 3. “Climate Neutral Smart Cities” Mission’s projects	133
Appendix 4. “Restore our Ocean and Waters” Mission’s projects	148
Appendix 5. “Cancer” Mission’s projects	166

List of Tables

Table 1: Search terms
Table 2: Categories of Data Extracted and Related Constructs
Table 3: Mission assignment
Table 4: Overview of Soil Mapping CS Projects
Table 5: Soil Mapping Projects’ Outputs
Table 6: Cancer Mission Projects Clusters

List of Figures

Figure 1: Dimensions of Scaling (Radicchi et al., 2023)
Figure 2: Upscaling Constructs (Maccani et al., 2020)
Figure 3: CROPS Workshop at ECSA 2024
Figure 4: CROPS Workshop at ECSA 2024 - Projects
Figure 5: Overview of projects identified across the 5 EU Missions
Figure 6: Soil Sensors Map from grow Observatory
Figure 7: Share the Bean Homepage
Figure 8: Data Map One Million Voices in Agroecology
Figure 9: Soil Modules for Children - Elementary GLOBE Soil Module
Figure 10: Adaptation to Climate Change Mission Platform
Figure 11: iNaturalist Citizen Science Projects Dashboard
Figure 12: BeeWatch.it Dashboard, Monitoring of Bees and Butterflies
Figure 13: Plant Letters landing
Figure 14: GreenSCENT “Knowledge Graph” tool page
Figure 15: Telraam CS Data Platform on Traffic Counting
Figure 16: PS Lifestyle Homepage
Figure 17: Front page of FLOW project
Figure 18: Front page of Seasearch project
Figure 19: Front page of Reef Check Med project
Figure 20: Front page of SeagrassSpotter project
Figure 21: Spectrum of contributions of CS projects addressing Litter and Waste

- Figure 22: Front page of PlasticPirate project
- Figure 23: Scheme contribution CS projects addressing Litter and Waste II
- Figure 24: Front page of Debris Tracker project
- Figure 25: Scheme contribution CS projects addressing Litter and Waste III
- Figure 26: Front page of National Plastic Watch project
- Figure 27: Scheme contribution CS projects addressing Litter and Waste
- Figure 28: Front page of MCS Wild Bottle Sightings project
- Figure 29: Front page of Freshwater Watch project
- Figure 30: Front page of Ice Watch project
- Figure 31: The BEACH Program, a Sea Safety project
- Figure 32: Front page of Our Radioactive Ocean project
- Figure 33: Front page of From Sea to Street project
- Figure 34: Foldit Main Page and Evidence of impact on cancer Mission
- Figure 35: Front page of Citizen Health Project
- Figure 36: EUCanImage Frontpage
- Figure 37: Mark2Cure
- Figure 38: LIVES Project Homepage
- Figure 39: Neureka Project
- Figure 40: Overview and Timeline of Tasks 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3

Executive Summary

Despite the growing demonstrated impact of Citizen Science and its more and more acknowledged value to address several pressing issues we face globally and locally as a society, too often it struggles to achieve sustainability and move beyond local actions and impact. CROPS focuses on upscaling Citizen Science at the transnational level. It does so in the context of the 5 EU Missions: Adaptation to Climate Change; Cancer; Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030; 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030; and A Soil Deal for Europe.

Within CROPS, WP2 focuses on reviewing existing Citizen Science projects with respect to their scalability potential. As part of this effort, this document addresses two main purposes:

1. Presenting the overall methodology and foundational framework for this effort. This framework is drawn upon existing theories of Participatory Design, Diffusion of Innovations, and Adoption and Use of Innovations, and outlines nine enabling factors for citizen science projects to upscale.
2. Reporting the preliminary findings from the review. So far, 518 projects have been identified and clustered under the Mission(s) they address. Of these, 368 have been reviewed. From this exercise, preliminary insights and findings are presented.

This report finally positions this study within the overall CROPS project and proposes some lessons learned as well as reflection points that will require particular attention during the ongoing scalability assessment.

1 Introduction

We live in a polycrisis context, where each decision generates political, technological, economical, ecological and social changes on a planetary scale. Given the urgency of our situation, immediate action is imperative. Achieving the required magnitude of change at the necessary pace demands a triple approach - comprising systemic transformation, individual and collective behavioral changes. It is only through the synergistic integration of the three of them that we can effectively address the challenges before us.

Confronting the unprecedented transnational environmental and societal challenges, the European Union has launched an ambitious path toward sustainability and resilience. The European landscape is currently confronting significant environmental and health-related challenges, which are shared globally. From the impact of plastic pollution on our oceans and freshwater systems, to the urgent need for soil regeneration to sustain nutritional demands, these issues demand immediate attention. Simultaneously, there is a critical need to develop smarter urban systems that enhance quality of life while optimising the use of planetary resources. Additionally, pressing health challenges, such as cancer, and the broader implications of climate change on natural food chains highlight the interconnectedness of these crises.

In this context, Citizen Science (CS) emerges as a valuable approach to address these complex issues by leveraging collective research efforts. This practice aligns with the objectives of the five European Missions established by the European Commission, which aim to provide concrete solutions to some of the greatest challenges of our time. With ambitious yet actionable goals, these missions are designed to deliver measurable outcomes by 2030, advancing sustainability and resilience across Europe and beyond.

Over the last two decades, the number of CS projects has grown exponentially. Citizens are increasingly empowered to contribute to innovative policy making and participate in socio-technical innovation (Hecker et al., 2018). This is partly due to the rapid adoption of open innovation and science paradigms and the advancement and pervasiveness of today's digital technologies (Haklay, 2015; Balestrini et al., 2017).

CS generally refers to the practice of involving the public in one or more stages of scientific research and knowledge production. It does so by answering research questions, providing observations, creating data via the use of specific hardware and/or software, gathering and sharing local knowledge and skills in a required situation, identifying research questions, communicating and disseminating results, etc. These processes often result in enhancing a better granularity of understanding of a specific topic, and/or raising public awareness, and/or potentially leading to policy changes and action or even the creation of new

services and technologies. Today, CS principles are used and have proven effective in various scientific fields across multiple geographical scales (de Sherbinin et al., 2021), including the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Fraisl et al., 2020; Sprinks et al., 2021). These include (and are not limited to) the 5 EU Missions¹: 1. Adaptation to Climate Change, 2. Cancer, 3. Restore our Oceans and Water, 4. Climate Neutral and Smart Cities, 5. A Soil Deal for Europe, the areas of focus of the CROPS project.

The problem addressed in CROPS is clear and well-acknowledged in both the literature and the practice: ensuring the sustainability of actions and projects to contribute more effectively to the 5 EU Missions. In other words, many CS projects tend not to go beyond pilot stages, i.e. tend to be on a small or local scale. This is typically due to specific temporary funding mechanisms, lack of effective business models, or more technical causes, among other reasons. While this local approach offers significant value both for scientific research and the individuals and communities involved, many of these initiatives have an untapped potential to maximize their impact. By addressing broader societal challenges, they can benefit much larger segments of society, particularly those who are typically marginalized. The overall objective of CROPS is, therefore, to go beyond these small scale projects, and bring the contribution of CS to the 5 EU Missions “*from small-scale to a Europe-wide level, moving it towards a modern, open science approach*” (CROPS proposal).

As part of the project’s main goal, the main objective of WP2 is to explore, identify, assess, and select CS projects that are suitable for upscaling, i.e. to amplify their impact on the 5 European Missions.

1.1 The Task

The objective of this WP is drawn upon two main pillars:

1. Identify, review, and assess CS projects with respect to their upscaling potential. Specifically, identify at least 500 CS projects, review and assess at least 100, and select at least 3 projects per each of the 5 EU Missions.
2. Identify current and potential synergies between CS actions and the EU Mission’s objectives.

These objectives are framed as part of the overall primary goal of CROPS, that is to enable and facilitate upscaling of CS to a Europe-wide level for each of the 5 EU Missions, that are:

1

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe_en

1. **Adaptation to Climate Change:** support at least 150 European regions and communities to become climate resilient by 2030;
2. **Cancer:** working with Europe's Beating Cancer Plan to improve the lives of more than 3 million people by 2030 through prevention, cure and solutions to live longer and better;
3. **Restore our Ocean and Waters** by 2030;
4. **100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities** by 2030;
5. **A Soil Deal for Europe:** 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthier soils by 2030.

This document reports the first 11 months (from January to November 2024) in this effort and specifically focuses on:

3. Presenting the overall methodology and foundational framework for this effort.
4. Outlining the specific methods and techniques used for the initial review.
5. Reporting the preliminary findings from the review.

1.2 Structure of this document

According to its objectives, and since the main scope of this deliverable is about the review of CS projects, this document is structured consistent with the recommendations for presenting review results through the staged process proposed in Okoli (2015):

1. **Define scope of the review and the review question(s)** (section 2): in this first step the scope of the review is clarified. In CROPS this means establishing both key definitions and the overall methodology and framework to be followed. In particular, this section provides the key definitions adopted in CROPS for upscaling (section 2.1), CS and CS projects (sections 2.2 and 2.3 respectively), the key fields and disciplines considered (section 2.4), the geographical scope of this review (section 2.5), and what do we aim to upscale (section 2.6). Section 2.7 focuses on the actual framework and overall methodological strategy employed.
2. **Search strategy:** based on the scope, section 3.1 presents the strategy together with the actual sources leveraged for collecting evidence about CS projects. A mixed approach of combining insights from practitioners, academic literature, existing platforms such as EU Citizen Science², SciStarter³ (among others), expert focus groups, and other publicly available resources have been adopted.

² <https://eu-citizen.science/>

³ <https://scistarter.org/>

3. **Selection/Inclusion criteria:** section 3.2 presents the criteria established for selecting the 500 projects to be considered for the review.
4. **Data extraction and analysis:** section 3.3 focuses on what data we extracted, how it has been classified, and why. This section is divided into two key parts: first, we discuss how we assign CS projects to the different EU Missions, as their contribution can sometimes be not straightforward or overlap across different missions. Second, we present the different data points extracted from the review, consistent with the overall framework designed (section 2.7).
5. **Write up the review:** the last step, i.e. together with section 2.7 the core of this document, presents the findings achieved to-date in the review. These are tackled separately for each of the 5 EU Missions in section 4.

Finally, section 5 provides concluding remarks and outlines the next steps to be undertaken in this WP and in CROPS.

This deliverable and, more generally, the work conducted in WP2 is interrelated with all other WPs within CROPS. On the one hand, this review and scalability assessment provides other WPs and their tasks with learning on the scalability potential of the CS projects identified as well as with a list of projects that are suitable for upscaling. On the other hand, other tasks within CROPS will investigate specific aspects of upscaling more in depth. For example, Task 3.5 will contribute with an analysis and insights on the scientific relevance of these in terms of their contributions to the 5 EU Missions. Tasks 4.1 and 4.2 will contribute with insights on best practices and opportunities for leveraging existing open data repositories and to produce interoperable and FAIR data respectively. Task 4.3, in a similar fashion, focuses on existing funding models and opportunities. Monthly consortium meetings, including dedicated WP2 meetings, are being undertaken to enable a smooth knowledge and perspective exchange among partners responsible for the different tasks and WPs.

2 Defining the Scope: Definitions, Approach & Methodology

The overall objective of this WP is to explore, assess, and identify CS projects suitable for upscaling, contributing to one or more of the 5 EU Missions. In the following subsections the main scope of this work is clearly defined and established through addressing the key concepts involved. It covers respectively: (1) what do we mean by upscaling? (2) Across the spectrum of citizen participation, what do we recognise to be CS projects? (3) What fields and disciplines do we consider? (4) What geographical scope do we focus on? (5) What do we aim to upscale? And (6) What are the key factors to be considered when assessing upscaling potential (i.e. the CROPS Upscaling Framework)? As part of the latter, we also outline the main methodological steps designed for this WP.

2.1 What do we mean by upscaling?

The original EU call for this project, provided the following prompt for action: “Many citizen science initiatives could achieve much higher impact if they were implemented on a transnational basis, collecting, analysing and exploiting vast amounts of cross-country data and, thereby, building a multinational community of citizen scientists”⁴. Since the problem of upscaling in CS is not new, several academics and practitioners have tackled it to-date. However, across disciplines, the term scaling has been used inconsistently or interchangeably as a synonym of replicating and spreading (Maccani et al., 2020; Radicchi, 2022).

The Joint Research Centre (JRC) proposes a distinction between scaling and spreading in CS (Maccani et al., 2020) whereby:

- “Scaling refers to the extension of existing approaches from a smaller geographical area to a larger one - for example from a neighborhood to an entire city, and then to a region”, and
- “Spreading [...] is understood as the ability to successfully replicate and carry over CS approaches from one location to another at the same geographic scale - for example from one neighborhood, city or region to another”.

For the scope of CROPS, we argue that both represent mechanisms and dynamics of interest, as both scaling and spreading as defined above can potentially entail a movement “from small-scale to Europe-wide level”. Radicchi (2022) reflects on the concept of spreading as replication arguing that this is a more sustainable scenario of scaling. Furthermore, inspired by the literature on

4

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-widera-2023-era-01-08>

social innovation, she defines scalability in CS (as opposed to the business discipline) as being: (1) driven by social value (as opposed to profits); (2) context dependent (as opposed to homogenous).

With respect to the latter, the vast majority of studies point towards the concept of adaptability (to different contexts) as instrumental for scaling since CS is often rooted in complex cultural, political, environmental, economic, and social settings. Adaptability is therefore an “added value” for CS projects willing to scale and is defined as follows: “*the capacity of a project or an initiative to reproduce the methodology/approach/protocol on a local/regional/national/European level in accordance with the context and needs of the local stakeholder groups so as to have much more space for creativity and co-design*” (Radicchi et al., 2023, p.10). As a result of the work, three dimensions of scaling are proposed (see Figure 1)⁵:

Figure 1: Dimensions of Scaling (Radicchi et al., 2023)

1. **Scale-Up:** “*institutional changes achieved through the upscaled CS projects, which can become an integral part of a policy or approach*” (p.11). The example proposed is that of Plastic Pirates⁶ which became an integral part of the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters.
2. **Scale-out:** “*refers to replication and dissemination of CS projects/initiatives, according to specific dimensions such as the geographic and the temporal spread, the research scope, the*

⁵ Also a fourth dimension named “scale-down” is proposed to consider degrowth of projects. Given the scope of CROPS, this was excluded a priori.

⁶ <https://www.plastic-pirates.eu/en>

communities engaged, the amount of data collected, the technology/methodology deployed” (p. 11).

- 3. Scale-deep:** *“CS projects that have an impact on cultural changes and beliefs such as trust in science by the citizens and trust in citizen science by the scientists” (p. 12).*

In CROPS, given its objectives of creating transnational communities through upscaling, all these paradigms, Scale-Up, Scale-Out, and Scale-deep appear to be relevant. In light of these reflections from the existing literature, we adopt the following definition:

Upscaling refers to extending the outcomes of a given CS project or initiative through replication, growth, or a combination of these models.

In this way, upscaling refers to enabling changes driven by citizen science activities, along with the replication and expansion of citizen science initiatives, methodologies, technologies and related aspects. It can also include shifts in cultural beliefs or a combination of all these factors.

Such a general definition accommodates both the objectives of CROPS as well as the models encountered in the literature. Importantly the view of upscaling emphasised in this definition is towards achieving a greater impact of the CS discipline on the 5 EU Missions, i.e. consistent with the central goal of the CROPS project.

2.2 Across the spectrum of citizen participation, what do we recognise to be CS projects?

The literature has substantially debated what is CS, and what it is not, e.g. in the spectrum of citizen participation’s levels (Vohland et al., 2021). One of the most acknowledged and cited contributions in this way is provided by Haklay (2013) where CS is defined across a typology of four different participation dynamics, i.e.: *“crowdsourcing, distributed intelligence, participatory science, and extreme citizen science”*. These are characterised by an increasing active role of citizens across the different levels. Additionally, Shirk et al. introduced the term “Public Participation in Scientific Research (PPSR)” as an alternative to citizen science, defining it as *“intentional collaborations in which members of the public engage in the process of research to generate new science-based knowledge.”* Their framework includes projects with five levels of participation: (i) contractual projects, where communities request researchers to investigate a specific issue; (ii) contributory projects, typically designed by scientists, with volunteers mainly contributing data; (iii) collaborative projects, where scientists design the study and volunteers contribute data, as well as assist in project design, data analysis, or dissemination; (iv) co-created projects, jointly designed by scientists and

volunteers, with volunteers actively participating in most or all research stages; and (v) collegial projects, where volunteers conduct research independently, seeking varying degrees of professional recognition. Haklay et al. (2021a) proposed an extensive systematic analysis of the definitions of CS. This work presents evidence about several dozens of dimensions and different interpretations of the term CS across EU countries and institutions. In this way, Cooper et al. (2021) addressed the efforts to "rebrand" citizen science as "community science" in the United States as the term "citizen" can act as a barrier to inclusion. The authors proposed that discussions should emphasise strategies and practices that promote inclusivity, rather than merely changing the name. In short, the extant literature shows that an agreement around a single and an agreed definition or terminology for CS has not been reached yet and this may not be even necessary. As Haklay et al (2021b) showed that the context-specificity, openness, and the fluidity of definitions are crucial in reflecting the diversity of the field CS, creating space for methodological advancements, interdisciplinary collaboration, and the overall growth of CS as a platform for scientific innovation.

For the development of the CROPS research, we decided to adopt an inclusive approach and define citizen science as active participation of individuals and communities in addressing scientific inquiries or generating knowledge by voluntarily sharing their expertise, resources and skills. Our definition closely aligns with the ECSA 10 Principles of Citizen Science and the ECSA Characteristics of Citizen Science⁷. We adopted this definition and approach to encompass a diverse and broad range of initiatives, leading to a deeper understanding of the contributions of the CS discipline to the 5 EU Missions.

2.3 What do we mean by “CS Project”?

The next decision revolved around what constitutes a CS project (i.e. the CROPS' unit of analysis), a pilot, an experiment and how these relate to each other.

This discussion is relatively simple for EU-funded CS endeavors. Here typical CS projects promote the development, implementation and use of certain principles, technologies or approaches. These are usually subsequently tested across different contexts through pilots or local experiments. In these cases, we consider these pilots as part of the same project, set to augment the generalisability of the proposed solutions (i.e. to foster the adaptability concept described above). For example, the WeCount EU-funded project⁸ focused on co-creating and testing a low cost traffic counting sensor through CS. This was done across 5 pilots in 5 different cities. Still, the pilots remain instantiations of the main concept of the project (i.e. exploring, enabling, and fostering CS-based traffic counting) and the

⁷ <https://eu-citizen.science/resource/88>

⁸ <https://we-count.net/>

pilots served as experimentation of the solution across different socio-political-cultural contexts.

This reflection becomes more complex in those cases where a central project (typically a platform) exists and it serves as an infrastructure for other, independent, projects. The typical example in this space refers to iNaturalist⁹, a central platform that hosts thousands of CS projects, ranging from one day actions organised in schools, to endeavors that have been active for more than two decades. For these cases, a more qualitative criteria is established in CROPS. Projects under an umbrella program or infrastructure (e.g. iNaturalist itself) are considered separately in CROPS if they entail a clear contribution to one or more of the 5 EU Missions, and if this contribution is clearly linked to the individual endeavour.

2.4 What fields and disciplines do we consider?

Another criteria to define the scope of this work was established to ensure that the projects considered are actually related to the 5 EU Missions. Projects in other fields than the 5 EU Missions have not been included in our review.

However, some other known CS projects may be of great relevance, despite not being directly connected to the 5 EU Missions. These are more general CS projects whose aims are typically to advance the discipline as a whole, through the provision of overarching frameworks, methodologies, and other resources, among others. They can be considered as relevant since they can potentially be instrumental in upscaling the impact of other existing projects to the 5 EU Missions. An example is WeObserve¹⁰, a project devoted to fostering the creation and maintenance of CS-based observatories (COs), although it does not include a specific 'project' where active participation of the public takes place. It also tackles three key challenges that COs face: awareness, acceptability and sustainability - and aims to improve the coordination between existing COs and related regional, European and international activities. These types of projects are therefore included in the review, but considered separately from those directly connected with the 5 EU Missions and those where active involvement of the public took place.

2.5 What geographical scope do we consider?

We mainly focus on assessing projects that are established or that have been developed within the EU and associated countries, but also consider CS projects that have been developed or are established in other continents. Going beyond EU borders was decided for two main reasons:

⁹ <https://www.inaturalist.org/>

¹⁰ <https://www.weobserve.eu/>

1. In the effort of upscaling CS, instances of projects from outside Europe could be either replicated in the EU, or upscaled through adoption by EU transnational communities that integrate these projects' principles and/or technologies and/or methodologies, etc.
2. Many of the issues covered by the 5 EU Missions represent global problems, and, as such, require global solutions. All in all, we acknowledge that open science and data, as well as communities in the context of CS addressing global issues should not have borders. The agenda on mitigating the effects of climate change should not be the independent work of a country or a continent. Likewise for the restoration of the oceans and waters. These are pressing global issues. CROPS therefore also focuses on upscaling each stage of local-to-global solutions, considering a global geopolitical spectrum of CS projects.

2.6 What do we aim to upscale?

Another important question to be addressed at the forefront of CROPS relates to what is the actual subject of upscaling tackled in this work.

In Maccani et al. (2020), when studying the role of technology in upscaling CS, two different mechanisms have been identified: (1) *Scaling of technology*; and (2) *Scaling by technology*. The former identifies situations whereby a specific platform, application, or other system is scalable and can be potentially adopted and adapted to several, often different, situated contexts. The latter instead focuses on those scenarios where a given technology is leveraged to enable upscaling of a CS project. For example, in a world where emerging technologies like AI are expanding rapidly, they can also be leveraged to scale up citizen science initiatives and enhance their impact, provided that they are used responsibly and ethically.

However, it can also be argued that methodologies can be upscaled. For example, D-Noses¹¹ established a multi-step CS methodology tested in the context of odour pollution across a number of pilots globally. This could potentially be reused in other fields, such as in air or noise pollution, for the effective engagement of the public in scientific environmental research through a quadruple helix approach. In these cases, one of the principal focuses should be on disseminating such methodologies (and the supporting resources available) and fostering their adoption or adaptation across contexts. In other instances, upscaling can be in the context of community growth, including around a scalable platform or technology. Plastic Pirates¹² is a typical example of these dynamics.

¹¹ <https://dnoses.eu/>

¹² <https://www.plastic-pirates.eu/en>

Since we believe that all these are relevant for the scope of CROPS, to encompass all aforementioned mechanisms and scenarios, **we focus on upscaling the impact of CS to the 5 EU Missions.**

In this perspective, technologies, methodologies, and existing communities shift from being the main focus of upscaling to being considered as instrumental for upscaling the impact of given CS projects to the EU Missions. The unit of analysis therefore becomes the CS projects themselves (or a conjunction of projects) each characterised by their elements, namely their own methodologies, technologies, communities etc. As a hypothetical example, we consider a local CS project that has demonstrated impact in reducing the effect of climate change in a given neighborhood. In CROPS, we will assess its suitability for upscaling its impact to the transnational level. This may entail a focus on its methodology, technology, community or all of these combined. The elements that influence this upscaling potential (i.e. what we actually assess) are discussed and presented next.

2.7 What are the key factors to be considered when assessing upscaling potential? The CROPS Upscaling Framework

The key question addressed here is: what are the factors that influence upscaling of CS projects? In other words, what elements should be searched, ordered, and considered when assessing the upscaling potential of CS projects? The framework adopted in CROPS and extensively presented in the proposal, refers to Maccani et al., (2020).

The main assumption behind this approach is that upscaling in its most basic form entails: (1) an original CS project to be upscaled; (2) an upscaling process; and (3) a target context where the original CS project upscales. As a consequence, from a theoretical perspective, the framework acknowledges that upscaling can be the result of Diffusion of Innovations (Rogers, 2010) - e.g. through the willingness of the people and entities behind the original CS project - and/or Adoption of Innovation (Venkatesh et al., 2003) - e.g., in the case of replication in another context - and/or as a result of organic growth and growing appropriation (Le Dantec and Di Salvo, 2013). As a result of combining the constructs of the different theories, nine factors are established as influencing upscaling in CS. These are presented in Figure 2, and defined below.

Figure 2: Upscaling Constructs (Maccani et al., 2020)

Intrinsic elements of the original CS project:

1. **Proof of Value:** this construct postulates that CS projects for which impact can be demonstrated are more likely to upscale. In other words, this first driver acknowledges that for a CS project to upscale, the value of its outcome must be present or emerging, clear, demonstrated, and understood. According to the theories considered, this is by far the most influencing construct. Proof of Value is defined in CROPS as demonstrated or emerging impact on one or more of the 5 EU Missions.
2. **Easy to Use and Understand:** this second construct stresses that the easier the subject or key components of the CS project are to use (e.g. in the case of technology or specific practices) and understand (e.g. in the case of the core subject of an existing project), the more likely it is to upscale.

With respect to the former, a useful concept to discuss this is that of “task granularity”, originally defined as the smallest individual investment necessary in order to make a contribution (Benkler, 2006). Our review indicates that CS projects differ significantly in the task granularity that is required for citizen scientists to contribute. This is often related to the technologies that are typically put in place to mediate the relationship between participants and science. It is noted however that the framework does not argue that projects that make use of more complex technologies are less likely to upscale. Rather, these may require a different approach and resources, and it has to be kept in mind that different types of technologies leveraged in a project might attract different types of

participants and co-design/creation practices are crucial in these cases (Balestrini et al., 2014).

Concerning the latter, the theories underpinning the framework (Venkatesh et al., 2003; Rogers, 2010) strongly stress that upscaling of projects tackling simple concepts (e.g. mapping quiet places in urban spaces¹³) are more likely to upscale than those tackling scientific problems that are way too complex to be common knowledge (e.g. the impact of certain Radio Frequency Electromagnetic Fields - e.g. in the Seawave EU project¹⁴).

3. **Openness:** this construct states that the more the outputs of a given CS project are open, the more likely the project is to upscale (Fraisl et al., 2023). It is well known that community-based projects that deliver open documentation (methodologies, resources, technologies etc.) have increased engagement with the project (Teli et al., 2015), fostered its scalability (Marttila and Botero, 2013), shareability (Lessig, 2004) and workability (Balka, 2011). Here, we consider the level of openness of resources to support: (1) the process (e.g. open educational materials and guides); (2) its tools (e.g. open source software and open hardware); and (3) the access and interpretation of its results (e.g. open data, open access). Furthermore, CROPS is committed to foster the diffusion of open science principles where possible (Fraisl et al., 2022), and this construct assumes therefore a crucial importance.

Elements of the upscaling process:

4. **Community and Champions:** this construct acknowledges that upscaling is not simply about dropping a technology and a methodology into a new (or an extended) context. Rather, these must be supported by an artful work of aligning actors around the shared concern and fostering continuous engagement (Maccani et al., 2020). The extent to which communities are developed and established, as well as the presence of Champions¹⁵ within this “ecosystem of agents” (Bristol Approach to Citizen Sensing Programme, 2016), influence upscaling of CS projects. The creation of transnational CS communities, as well as identifying and engaging CS Champions, are part of the work conducted in CROPS (in WP5 and Task 5.3 respectively).
5. **Knowledge Sharing and Transfer Resources:** this dimension acknowledges the role that resources play in sharing and transferring

¹³ Like in the case of the Hush City project - <https://opensourceoundscapes.org/hush-city/>

¹⁴ <https://seawave-project.eu/>

¹⁵ Defined as: individuals with interest, aptitude, and experience and that thus have developed higher levels of knowledge to provide support and advice to potential adopters (Rogers, 2010).

knowledge from one context to another, i.e. to facilitate the upscaling process. In the context of CS, three types of Knowledge Sharing and Transfer Resources exist at different levels of detail: (1) Inventories and Catalogs; (2) Best Practices, Education, and Training; and (3) Tools, Guidelines, and Tutorials. The first level refers to knowledge resources typically made available as organised textual explanations of projects. The second level refers to a more elaborated set of content such as best practices frameworks and actions in the space of education and training. Finally, the most articulated examples of Knowledge Sharing and Transfer Resources refer to what is commonly known as toolkits.

The extent to which these resources are available and accessible, influence the upscaling potential of a given CS project. These resources typically provide access to tools and methods on how to: involve citizens in CS processes; collectively plan and design research studies; and even assemble environmental sensors and interpret complex data. These may also include educational material about the topic at hand.

6. Narratives and Communication: this construct supports that the extent to which one CS project and its results are communicated and disseminated, influence its potential to upscale. While this may seem obvious, too often a given CS project cannot be upscaled or replicated simply because its information is not (publicly) available. This includes documentation of the project's methodology, principles, and results, in an appropriate way, consistent with the open science principles that are central to CROPS.

Elements of the target context:

7. Alignment of Matter of Concern: this element stresses the importance for the new context to be facing and experiencing similar issues as those tackled in the original CS project (i.e. the one to be upscaled), and for its individuals to perceive these as actual matters of concerns relevant to them. It is important to notice that for some CS projects, the discussion on upscaling to the transnational level is simply not applicable. Some CS projects tackle problems and/or opportunities that are very context specific. As a basic example, Tick Radar¹⁶, is simply not suitable for upscaling by nature in those areas where ticks do not exist. As emerged during the ECSA 2024 conference, some other projects may not be at a sufficient level of maturity to be ready to upscale. For example, projects in early stages are experimental in nature, may require time and resources to design, test and validate certain technologies or approaches before being ready to upscale. Also, some projects may not have an intrinsic motivation to address

¹⁶ <https://www.wur.nl/en/show/Tekenradar.nl-Tick-radar.htm>

EU-wide or global goals. Rather, they focus on solving local issues, and this is their main goal and scope. In these cases however, upscaling can happen through replication mechanisms, whereby other stakeholders may adopt the legacy of a given project, and extend its outcomes to different contexts.

8. **Alignment of Legal Norms:** this element considers the role played by the regulatory environment and the need for these to be aligned between the initial context and the one within which upscaling will take place. An example comes from WeCount¹⁷. This CS project promotes the usage of a camera-based sensor technology to enable citizen-driven traffic counting. The project has been implemented in five cities in the EU. The lack of alignment on CCTV-based regulations across EU countries posed a legal challenge for implementing the technology (i.e. for delivering the CS project) in all cities.
9. **Alignment of Social Values:** similarly to the previous, social values, e.g. a culture of participation in democratic processes, should be aligned between the original and target contexts. To clearly show the relevance of this driver, an extreme example is given by the usage of Citizen Generated Data for the development of the so-called Social Credit System in China¹⁸. As part of this national program, the central government collects data generated by citizens to develop individual “credit scores” to be coupled with people’s ID. Such a credit score is derived from a multitude of data about individuals’ behaviors in society. Such initiative is not replicable, for example in Europe, as this would be inconsistent with the shared social values being promoted of, for example, equality and inclusion.

All in all, these nine constructs define the factors considered that influence upscaling of a given CS project. These have been adapted to the CROPS project and its specific scope by informing the data to be extracted and analysed in this review. This is detailed (and related to these constructs) in section 3.3.

The goal of this review is then to extract and assess the suitability for upscaling of at least 500 CS projects. Clearly, gathering all information related to the nine constructs for all 500 projects is practically not feasible in CROPS. We therefore defined different rounds of analysis, whereby in each round only a subset of projects are selected and considered further. This specific strategy will be presented more in detail as part of Deliverable 2.2, dedicated to the actual upscaling assessment.

¹⁷ <https://we-count.net/>

¹⁸ 国务院关于印发社会信用体系建设规划纲要(2014—2020年)的通知. Central Government of China https://www.gov.cn/zhengce/content/2014-06/27/content_8913.htm (in Chinese).

3 The Review

This third section of this report focuses on the techniques and processes followed as part of the actual review, i.e. how CS projects have been searched, selected, and what data has been extracted from each.

3.1 Search strategy

After defining the scope and general protocol for the review (see section 2), the next step involved searching for (at least) the 500 CS projects to be identified and analysed. These projects were gathered from a wide variety of sources that can be clustered in four groups:

1. **Consortium knowledge:** the CROPS is composed of 5 organisations that have considerable experience working in the field of CS (IIASA, Earthwatch, OutBe, INOVA+, and Ideas For Change). This knowledge has been leveraged to start setting up a database to collect and store instances of projects, both on an ongoing and a periodic basis (e.g. during the kick-off meeting, a workshop has been organised where part of the activity was to collect the consortium knowledge about existing CS projects relating to the 5 EU Missions).
2. **Review citizen science databases:** existing CS repositories have been crucial to identify CS projects. Some of the databases we reviewed include: EU-Citizen Science¹⁹, SciStarter²⁰, Zooniverse²¹, Git-Hub repositories²², and Digital Tools for Citizen Science²³.
3. **CROPS Workshop at ECSA Conference 2024:** in April 2024, the CROPS consortium took part in the ECSA Conference and organised a workshop session to collectively explore what is the impact of the CS discipline on the 5 EU Missions. Thirty participants have actively contributed to the workshop, including diverse profiles ranging from EU Commissioners, to well - acknowledged theorists and practitioners from the CS discipline, as well as other individuals with experience either in specific projects or in related organisations and institutions.

¹⁹ <https://eu-citizen.science/>

²⁰ <https://scistarter.org/>

²¹ <https://www.zooniverse.org/>

²² It is noted that these are usually repositories of open source codes for tools employed in CS projects. This source was therefore leveraged to identify additional projects behind the tools presented in the repository.

²³ <https://github.com/dylanrees/citizen-science>

Figure 3: CROPS Workshop at ECSA 2024

The session involved creating five discussion groups for each of the 5 EU Missions. After an overview of the missions was presented, each group discussed, based on their experience and wisdom, the key contributions of the CS discipline towards achieving the missions and provided examples of projects. Those contribution elements that were agreed through each group's discussion were transcribed in post-its, presented, and discussed in the overall workshop.

Figure 4: CROPS Workshop at ECSA 2024 - Projects

From this workshop over 50 projects were added to our database to be reviewed. In addition, initial ideas of clusters of CS contributions within each mission were outlined.

4. **Academic Literature:** Existing literature has also been considered as a source of projects. Both academic and the so-called “grey literature” have been searched, ordered, and included. With respect to both, the process started with the consortium collectively suggesting key papers and articles to be considered. This was followed by a more systematic search of the literature.

Google Scholar²⁴ has been used as the search database for academic papers. First we defined keywords to be searched. We soon realised that the searches led to too many results to be all considered. The decision was therefore taken to consider papers that had the key search terms in the title or keywords. The table below provides an overview of the results obtained for each search term included.

Search terms	Results
<i>“Citizen Science Scaling / Upscaling / Up-scaling / Scale Up / Scaling Up”</i>	7
<i>“Citizen Science Climate”</i>	17
<i>“Citizen Science Water”</i>	61
<i>“Citizen Science River / Ocean / Sea / Coast”</i>	13
<i>“Citizen Science Soil”</i>	10
<i>“Citizen Science Cancer”</i>	2
<i>“Citizen Science Health”</i>	43
<i>“Citizen Science Smart Cities”</i>	2

Table 1: Search terms

While this search led to a considerable number of results, most papers were found not to be useful for the scope of the review, i.e. to identify projects related to the 5 EU Missions. Rather, the vast majority of studies focus on theoretical contributions from specific research questions. Those presenting general reviews were considered further. For example, Pino et al. (2022) present and analyse 55 CS soil-related projects, and Fraisl et al. (2023) in the context of health and the SDGs. With respect to the Ocean

²⁴ https://scholar.google.com/schhp?hl=en&as_sdt=0.5

and Water mission, Kirschke et al. (2023) assess the impact of the discipline through a review of 85 related CS projects. Similarly, Earp and Liconti (2020) reflect on an agenda for the CS discipline to address marine research and conservation, through analysing 120 projects. Clearly, not all have been added (see selection and inclusion criteria in section 3.2).

5. **Grey Literature:** In addition to the existing databases (see above) and the academic literature, sources of data were collected also from other formats such as blog posts, white papers, and other non-academic articles. This was achieved through searching the keywords outlined in Table 1 above in traditional search engines.

Overall, combining these search strategies and sources, we were able to find evidence about more than the targeted 500 CS projects. However, for most projects encountered, especially those from the literature reviews, no further information was found. In addition, specific inclusion criteria had to be defined consistent with (Okoli, 2015).

3.2 Selection/Inclusion criteria

The search step provided us with a considerable amount of projects to be included in the review and, subsequently, in the scalability assessment. Since the scope of the review is broad (i.e. at least 500 projects in total to consider), and as extensively discussed above, three inclusion criteria were established at the beginning. Projects identified have been included if and only if: (1) they are consistent with the definition provided above for CS projects; and (2) they contribute to one or more EU Missions; and (3) they collectively provide diversity across missions. With respect to the latter, to the extent possible, we attempted a balanced representation of projects across the missions. As detailed below, the scarcity of projects related to Cancer, led to a lower number compared with other missions.

3.3 Data extraction²⁵ - what data we extracted and why

At the proposal stage, we aimed at collecting basic evidence (i.e. a list of names and links) for (at least) 500 CS projects across the missions. However, in order to select appropriately projects that are suitable for upscaling, more information was required. We therefore decided to extend the data collection for the first round of review and analysis (i.e. Round 1 on the 500 projects). Twelve clusters have been defined:

²⁵ The data has been collected from January to December 2024. There is a possibility that this data may become outdated if the database is examined in the years following 2024.

1. **Name and Link:** The name of the project (with the signals if needed) and a direct link to the project's website.
2. **Purpose:** A description of the main mission and vision of the project.
3. **Mission(s) Tackled** (see next paragraph): A selection of the main mission(s) tackled from the 5 European Missions.
4. **Active / Completed and Timeline:** An overview of the current status (active / no active) of the project in 2024, including the start and end year if known.
5. **Funding and Funder:** This element refers to the origin of the funding of the project, and also the name of the organisation(s) or institution(s) involved. The possibilities are: (1) Public, (2) Private, (3) Public and private, (4) Donations, (5) Self funded by a community, (6) Foundation, (7) Crowdfunded, (8) No information available, and (9) Research or university. When available, the original call(s) are also listed.
6. **Leader:** This cluster refers to the organisation(s) that are leading the project. A general cluster is available, along with the name of the organisation(s). The cluster possibilities are: (1) Citizen communities, (2) NGO, (3) Public agencies, (4) Research institute / universities, (5) Private organisations, (6) European consortium, (7) Public and private consortium, (8) Independent individual(s).
7. **Geographical Scope:** It refers to the current geographical area scale where the project takes place.
8. **Outputs:** A list of the outputs developed by the project. The outputs typically include: open source hardware and software, toolkits, video tutorials and educational materials, dashboards, monitoring mappings, apps, reports, and datasets among others. Open outputs are highlighted.
9. **Outcomes:** A list with the outcomes of the project that have proven to create an impact on the development of one or more of the 5 EU Missions. The outcomes typically appear in the form of either scientific discovery, raising awareness, informing public policies, or a combination of these.
10. **Evidence of Impact on the Missions:** Any evidence available to prove that impact has been achieved on one or more of the EU Missions.
11. **Relevance of Issue Tackled:** To highlight how and where the specific issue tackled is relevant (e.g. to understand if and where the project can be upscaled).
12. **Legal Alignment:** This cluster refers to the alignment of the project with local or European legislation. If the project takes place outside the European regions and associated countries, it assesses whether the project aligns with European legislation and norms.
13. **Engagement Level and Tasks:** An overview of the type of citizen engagement in the project, which can be categorised into three main levels: (1) Contribution, (2) Collaboration, and (3) Ownership. This overview includes an explanation of the main tasks conducted by the citizens at each level, to infer the task granularity required.

For consistency, Table 2 below, relates the categories of data collected with the constructs of the CROPS Upscaling Framework (see section 2.7). All constructs are addressed. Some (e.g. Ease of Use and Understanding) will be tackled more in-depth during Round 2 of the analysis, i.e. when managing a smaller amount of projects.

Original Construct	Data Collected in Round 1	Description
Proof of Value	Outcomes (impact on the missions)	Impact statement(s)
	Evidence of impact on the missions	Publicly available material or publications that demonstrate impact achieved.
	Outputs	List of all outputs
Ease of Use and Understanding	Outputs	List of outputs for further investigation in Round 2.
	Participation tasks	Outline level of task granularity
Openness	Outputs	List of all open outputs produced
Knowledge Sharing and Transfer Resources	Outputs	List of all resources (guides, educational, and others) left as legacy of the CS projects
Community and Champions	Outcomes (partially covered)	Initial indication of number of people that actively participated.
	CS Champions	Specifically covered in WP5, Task 5.3 of CROPS
Communication and Dissemination	Project URL	Further analysis to be conducted for projects selected for Round 2.
Alignment of Matter of Concern	Incidence of the issue tackled	Whether the CS project tackles a global, national, regional, or local issue
Alignment of Legal Norms	Alignment of Legal Norms	Highlight whether potential regulatory constraints may be present
Alignment of Social Norms	Area of focus	To be considered in Round 2

Table 2: Categories of Data Extracted and Related Constructs

Assigning Projects to the 5 EU Missions

A significant challenge in this phase was to assign projects to one of the EU Missions, for two main reasons. First, several CS projects simply cover more than one mission. Second, some of the missions overlap between themselves. For example, it can be argued that monitoring certain bacteria in urban gardens can contribute to three missions simultaneously, i.e. Soil, Adaptation to Climate Change, and Smart Cities. It has been therefore decided that in these cases both the “Main Mission Tackled” and “Other Missions” have been outlined in the review. Furthermore, specific topics where overlap is identified were assigned to the most relevant missions only. The table below provides an overview of these topics and the reasons why they have been assigned to their specific missions.

Field	Missions Tackled	Mission Chosen	Rationale
Biodiversity Monitoring	Adaptation to Climate Change, Smart Cities, Soil, Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change ²⁶	Projects typically focused on monitoring effects of climate change through mapping biodiversity longitudinally.
Pollinators Monitoring	Adaptation to Climate Change, Soil	Adaptation to Climate Change	Projects typically focused on monitoring pollinators for conservation purposes and to monitoring effects of climate change.
Flood Monitoring (Rain and Snow)	Adaptation to Climate Change, Smart Cities, Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change	Projects typically oriented towards improving resilience to climate-change related events either through anticipating flood events or through understanding historical patterns.
Water pollution Monitoring (e.g. Rivers, Sea, Lakes)	Adaptation to Climate Change, Smart Cities, Ocean and Waters	Ocean and Waters	Projects typically focused on monitoring Freshwater and Seas/Ocean properties and related events.
Pollution clean up (coasts, waters)	Adaptation to Climate Change, Smart Cities, Ocean and Waters	Ocean and Waters	Projects typically focused on enhancing public awareness and enabling actions on water pollution and supporting the clean up of certain adjacent areas.
Marine food chain monitoring	Adaptation to Climate Change, Ocean and Waters	Ocean and Waters	Projects typically focused on collecting local/regional/global data about the habitats, plants and animals that can be seen underwater, to track the health and conservation of the marine environments.

²⁶ Unless specifically conducted in marine environments or for soil-related purposes such as sustainable agriculture or gardening.

Meteorology	Climate Neutral Smart Cities, Adaptation to Climate Change	Adaptation to Climate Change	Projects typically focused on predicting climate events, monitoring climate change based on meteorological events and trends.
Sustainable Agriculture and Permaculture	Adaptation to Climate Change, Soil	Soil	Projects typically focused on promoting sustainable practices of agriculture to address climate change related issues on soils.
Mapping and monitoring soil's attributes	Adaptation to Climate Change, Soil	Soil	Projects typically aimed to monitor soil attributes at various levels (from bacteria, fungi to insects) for conservation and regeneration purposes.
Traffic monitoring	Adaptation to Climate Change, Smart Cities	Smart Cities	Projects typically focused on monitoring traffic data of vehicles, cyclists, pedestrians, and more in cities and regions.
Noise Monitoring	Adaptation to Climate Change, Smart Cities	Smart Cities	Projects typically focused on monitoring and mapping noise pollution. Issues are prevalent in urban environments.
Air Quality Monitoring	Adaptation to Climate Change, Smart Cities	Smart Cities	Projects typically focused on monitoring and mapping air quality. Issues are prevalent in urban environments.
Climate adaptation in cities	Adaptation to Climate Change, Smart Cities	Smart Cities	Projects typically aimed to enable co-creation for problems and solutions related to climate adaptation in cities.
Lifestyle (Transport, Food, Clothing, Recycling, Housing)	Adaptation to Climate Change, Smart Cities	Smart Cities	Projects typically focused on analysing lifestyles, and promoting literacy about more sustainable lifestyles in cities towards being 'climate neutral'.
Nature-based solutions	Adaptation to Climate Change, Smart Cities, Water and Oceans	Smart Cities	Projects typically focused on green infrastructures in cities.

Table 3: Mission assignment

This third section provided the details of the methodological processes designed for this review effort. This led to the identification of a total of 518 projects across the 5 EU Missions. An overview of these projects and the associated preliminary findings from this review is presented in the next section.

4 Preliminary Findings

This deliverable outlines the methodology and the scalability framework designed and adopted in CROPS, along with the preliminary findings from the initial review. The main objective of this document is to present the findings in terms of the identification of CS projects and their alignment with each of the 5 EU Missions that they address. While the actual scalability assessment is ongoing since M6, its results will be presented in Deliverable 2.2, due in M18. In summary, this section presents: (1) an overview of the projects identified within the review, their alignment with the EU Missions, as well as some additional insights; and (2) initial reflections within each of the 5 EU Missions. Regarding the latter, we present: an overview of the Mission; a preliminary typology of CS projects within these Missions, and some insights that are currently emerging from the ongoing scalability assessment according to the framework presented above.

All in all, 518 CS projects have been identified, listed and initially categorised across the 5 EU Missions. A full list of these projects is available in Appendices 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 for each Mission respectively.

Figure 5: Overview of projects identified across the 5 EU Missions

Although we aimed for an even distribution of projects across the Missions, those addressing the Missions Cancer and Climate Neutral Smart Cities are less represented as primary focus in the field of citizen science compared to the other three. The Cancer Mission has simply the least number of CS projects directly contributing to it. Regarding Climate Neutral Smart Cities, the lower number could be due to our classification choices, especially when we had to take a decision on whether a project should be assigned to Adaptation to Climate

Change or to Climate Neutral Smart Cities (see section 3.3). Finally, projects labelled as “others” are those that appear to be relevant for upscaling to transnational level, but do not directly contribute to any of the 5 specific EU Missions based on our analysis so far.

It is important to note that our results are preliminary since only a subset of the identified projects has indeed been assessed with respect to their scalability potential. In particular, of the 518 projects listed (see Appendices), 368 have been assessed at the time of writing this deliverable (i.e. November 2024).

Additionally, we emphasise that as each Mission is different in nature, a tailored approach was necessary throughout the review process. In other words, it was clear at the beginning that a “one strategy fits all” approach is not applicable. We tackle each Mission separately in the dedicated sections below.

4.1 A Soil Deal for Europe

4.1.1. Introduction to the Mission

The Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' stands as a critical initiative in Europe's pursuit of sustainable environmental management, specifically aimed at achieving healthy soils across the continent by 2050. Considering that between 60% and 70% of EU soils are currently unhealthy²⁷, the central objective of this Mission is to establish 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards soil restoration and health by 2030. Soils, as vital yet fragile resources, are essential to ecosystem services, agriculture, and overall environmental stability. However, soil degradation (whether through erosion, contamination, or unsustainable agricultural practices) poses significant risks, as just one centimeter of soil can take centuries to form, yet can be lost in a matter of moments due to industrial accidents or extreme weather events.

This mission aligns with the European Green Deal's overarching goals and plays a pivotal role in implementing the EU's Soils Strategy²⁸ and Soil Health Law²⁹, which set the ambitious target of ensuring all European soils are in a healthy condition by mid-century. At the heart of this mission lies the integration of digital tools, including precision agriculture, space-based observations, and artificial intelligence, to monitor and manage soil health. These innovative technologies not only offer substantial promise in terms of enhancing soil restoration efforts but also underscore the transformative potential of the mission for citizen engagement and local action.

²⁷

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/soil-deal-europe_en

²⁸ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/soil-and-land/soil-strategy_en

²⁹ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/proposal-directive-soil-monitoring-and-resilience_en

The Mission is drawn upon and operationalised through 8 main objectives:

- reduce desertification;
- conserve soil organic carbon stocks;
- stop soil sealing and increase re-use of urban soils;
- reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration;
- prevent erosion;
- improve soil structure to enhance soil biodiversity;
- reduce the EU global footprint on soils;
- improve soil literacy in society.

These objectives are addressed and pursued through four main classes of actions promoted by the EU. These include:

- funding an ambitious research and innovation programme with a strong social science component;
- putting in place an effective network of 100 living labs and lighthouses to co-create knowledge, test solutions and demonstrate their value in real-life conditions;
- developing a harmonised framework for soil monitoring in Europe;
- raising people's awareness on the vital importance of soils.

Clearly, CS has great potential to contribute towards the implementation of these actions.

4.1.2 CS Projects contributing to the Soil Mission

Our review (see Appendix 1) comprises 111 CS projects related to the Soil Mission. For about one third of these (i.e. 36) the scalability assessment has been performed at the time of writing this deliverable.

From our analysis of the projects, it became clear that different clusters exist, and these deserve separate attention and consideration. This is because projects tackle different objectives and pursue different impacts to the Mission. Three clearly different clusters of projects have been identified in the analysis so far:

1. Projects focused on mapping and monitoring soil's attributes (n=20).
2. Projects whose main focus is on education, i.e. about educating the public about the importance of soil and how to address it (n=2).
3. Projects focused on different aspects of sustainable agriculture and related actions and practices (n=9).
4. Other (n=5) projects whose focus is not covered in the clusters above such as generally exploring soil related threats and reporting them to the scientific and policy making communities.

These are discussed separately below.

Soil Mapping

The vast majority of projects assessed aims at developing CS observatories and maps of soil attributes, typically soil moisture. A common characteristic among most of these is the development of soil attributes maps, showcasing GIS information on participants' soil sample measurements. Sometimes accompanied by an open data platform for others to access the data for different purposes in machine readable formats. One example is presented in Figure 6 below from the Grow Observatory³⁰ project.

Figure 6: Soil Sensors Map from grow Observatory

Projects in this category vary substantially with respect to what attributes they consider (see Table 4). These results demonstrate the breadth of projects even within the same category (i.e. Soil Mapping) and raise questions about the importance of each of these elements at the transnational level. Some of these projects tackle local issues, such as the sudden presence of certain fungi at a certain location (e.g., the US based *What's in Your Backyard?*³¹, etc.). Others focus on elements that are by nature more “global issues” and thus with a broader potential impact or relevant to different contexts, such as soil acidity and biodiversity

³⁰ <https://growobservatory.org/grow-observatory-sensor-location-map/>

³¹ <https://shareok.org/handle/11244/28096>

CS project	Soil moisture	Soil Biod.	Soil pH	Fungi	Soil Cover	Organic content	Other	Metals	Geo Magnetic
Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP)									
Soils for Science									
Summer Solstice									
UKSO MySoil App							texture, temperature		
What's in Your Backyard									
SoilSkin La Piel Viva del Suelo									
Proyectos Nuestros Suelos							CaCO ₃ , MO, As		
Romania Geomagnetic App									
Vigilantes del suelo							compaction		
Acid-soils-testing-blitz									
DustAnalysis (Garden and Veg Safe)									
Programas de Conservación-Suelos							pesticides		
QUBS									
The CS Soil Health Project							Haney PLFA		
The Tea Bag Experiment							decomposition		
Grow Observatory									

Table 4: Overview of Soil Mapping CS Projects

While this table gives some initial insights into the variety of contributions of CS towards monitoring and mapping soil quality and attributes, it also demonstrates significant challenges in comparing the identified projects for the purpose of this work in CROPS, i.e. to select CS projects that are suitable for upscaling. These challenges are currently being reflected upon and will require particular attention during the upcoming validation efforts to be undertaken.

In the context of this task and consistent with the CROPS Upscaling Framework (see Section 3), the soil mission related citizen science projects are analysed on the basis of the outputs they produce, their relevance to the Mission, their level of openness and other characteristics. A closer look of these soil mapping projects allows us to distinguish among three types of common outputs, which are typically considered as enablers for replication and upscaling:

1. **Applications:** several projects produced mobile (or more rarely web) applications which remain usable even after the projects finish. Depending on the licenses applied (many seem to be open source so far), these outputs can be considered as important elements enabling upscaling (Maccani et al., 2020).
2. **Sensors / kits:** a second type of outputs refers to DIY (Do It Yourself) sensors and kits typically used by participants in the CS projects to perform soil sample measurements according to the attributes required. If based on open hardware principles and supported by associated resources and tutorials, these can be an important element to augment upscaling potential, mostly in the form of replication of one project in other contexts.
3. **Open Educational Resources:** finally, another common output, refers to ensemble of educational resources that, on the one hand, support the effective implementation of the projects and actions (e.g. tutorials, step-by-step guides etc.) and, on the other hand, propose learning opportunities around soil in general, and the specific focus of the project at stake.

The table below gives an overview of Soil Mapping CS Projects' Outputs across these three categories. It is noted that those indicated as (x) under the App column refer to situations where even though an application has been developed and is available open source, it is not usable by current versions of operating systems as it has not been recently updated. Under the "Sensors / kit" column, those highlighted in orange need further analysis with respect to the level of openness and accessibility of these resources. This is currently ongoing.

All in all, the scalability assessment will inform what projects are suitable for upscaling, and these will be investigated further and presented in D2.2 (M18).

Name of the project	App	Sensor / kit	Open resources
Vigilantes del suelo	x	x	x
Acid-soils-testing-blitz		x	
DustAnalysis (Garden and Vege Safe)		x	
Programas de Conservación - Suelos		x	x
QUBS			x
The CS Soil Health Project		x	x
The Tea Bag Experiment			x
Grow Observatory	(x)	x	x
Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP)			x
Soils for Science	x	x	x

Summer Solstice			
UKSO MySoil App	x		
What's in Your Backyard		x	
SoilSkin La Piel Viva del Suelo	(x)		x
Proyectos Nuestros Suelos		x	
Romania Geomagnetic App	x		

Table 5: Soil Mapping Projects' Outputs

Sustainable Agriculture

The second cluster includes CS projects where the focus is primarily on enabling sustainable agricultural practices. Once again projects vary substantially in their nature and scope ranging from fostering certain practices and behaviours that are more respectful for the environment among farmers, to promoting certain types of cultivations. As an example of the latter, Share the Bean³² embeds actions, support and education to establish a decentralised approach to genetic resources conservation with respect to food legumes.

Figure 7: Share the Bean Homepage

Seed Library³³, as another example, leverages public libraries as places where citizens can share and exchange home grown seeds as well as getting access to educational material on sustainable agriculture. Considering the former, i.e. sustainable agricultural practices, an example refers to One Million Voices in Agroecology³⁴, a CS platform where participants co-create and share agroecological practices. These are then made openly available through a digital map and related datasets (Figure 8).

³² <https://www.pulsesincrease.eu/experiment>

³³ <https://www.gkfb.si/za-uporabnike/knjiznica-semen>

³⁴ <https://onemillionvoices.agroecologymap.org/>

Figure 8: Data Map One Million Voices in Agroecology

Soil Education and Awareness

The third and last cluster of projects assessed so far refers to those whose main purpose relies around raising awareness about the importance of considering soil, and preserving its attributes and biodiversity. Importantly, CS projects included here typically leave open educational resources (ranging from PowerPoint presentations to more articulated webinar series or even MOOCs) as a legacy for others to reuse, making upscaling of these initiatives as a matter of adopting, disseminating, and fostering use of these resources.

Projects in this category vary still in their scope, and can be considered complementary. For example, *In My Backyard*³⁵ is a CS project where the scope is to raise awareness about sustainable home farming practices to ultimately steer behaviours of people towards not using certain fertilizers and pesticides. Others are more general in nature and propose different levels of modules to study soil science, also including some dedicated to children such as the *Elementary GLOBE Soil Module*³⁶ project.

³⁵ <https://actionproject.eu/citizen-science-pilots/in-my-backyard/>

³⁶ <https://www.globe.gov/web/elementary-globe/overview/soils>

Figure 9: Soil Modules for Children - Elementary GLOBE Soil Module

4.1.3 CS and Soil Mission: A Summary So Far

In this section, we presented an overview of CS projects contributing to the Soil Deal for Europe Mission. The insights presented are based on both the general descriptions of the 111 projects identified in total (see Appendix 1), as well as from the 36 for which the scalability assessment has been performed.

All in all, evidence so far shows that CS plays a significant role in the Soil Deal for Europe. This occurs mainly through facilitating bottom-up participation and fostering greater public awareness about the critical importance of soil health. By engaging citizens in soil monitoring, education, and advocacy, the mission helps build a more informed society while contributing to the scientific data needed for sustainable soil management practices. The projects evaluated under the CROPS initiative illustrate how citizen science can actively contribute to the development of robust frameworks for soil monitoring, enhancing literacy around soil health issues and supporting ongoing research efforts. Through this synergy of scientific research and grassroots participation, CS strengthens the mission's broader goals, driving collective action toward a resilient and sustainable future for European soils.

However, issues for upscaling and for performing the scalability assessment start to emerge. Below we present some preliminary challenges and aspects to be investigated further in the upcoming months based on those projects we have assessed so far:

1. **Breadth versus depth dilemma:** the wide variety of focuses encountered across the Soil Mapping projects points towards an important question: are projects that cover several aspects of soil broadly more relevant or those

that tackle one aspect more in-depth? While the ongoing analysis identifies which of these are actually suitable for upscaling, we expect important input and advice in these directions from the actual validation stage with domain experts.

2. **Lack of synergies and joint efforts:** one finding emerging from this initial analysis is that it occurs often that each project relies on its own resources and produces and promotes results in dedicated channels and platforms. The consequence of this is a lack of unified effort towards the mission, a missed opportunity to exploit synergies (e.g. among all projects focused on monitoring soil moisture in the EU). One possible interpretation of this resides in the actual funding structures upon which these projects are implemented, at least in the EU. The fact that most projects rely on public funding schemes (e.g., EU Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe, National Funding Schemes, etc.) put similar efforts and projects in competition with each other, as opposed to fostering joint efforts for achieving the Mission objectives. We emphasise that these aspects should be considered carefully when reflecting on upscaling to the transnational level.

Evidence found is primarily on Outputs rather than Outcomes: most projects when describing their impact tend to focus on the actual outputs they have produced as opposed to the outcomes, i.e. what these outputs enabled in terms of addressing the objectives of the Soil Mission. This is valid across all types of outputs. Some examples include: reporting on the number of participants in workshops or community members, which is arguably not a sufficient condition for impact; showcasing data platforms and maps, without describing how these data and outputs are used and leveraged to improve sustainability in soil management and agriculture; reporting on number of classes delivered as opposed to evaluating the knowledge and awareness gained by the participants. This points towards an important challenge for the scalability assessment, since Proof of Value and Impact on the Mission is a key driver of upscaling according to the CROPS framework (see Section 2). We expect that a more in-depth analysis will uncover these dynamics, e.g., through interviewing project leaders, etc.

4.2 Adaptation to Climate Change

4.2.1 Introduction to the Mission

As climate change accelerates, its impacts are increasingly evident in rising sea levels, extreme weather events, and disruptions to ecosystems and water cycles.³⁷ Adapting to these changes is not just a necessity but a shared global

³⁷ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/climate-change/consequences-climate-change_en

responsibility. In Europe and beyond, proactive adaptation measures are crucial to safeguard communities, economies, and natural resources.

The EU Missions on Adaptation to Climate Change and Ocean and Water Restoration reflect this urgency, aiming to restore vital ecosystems, protect biodiversity, and build resilience against climate-related challenges. These initiatives embody a vision of sustainability and collaboration, paving the way for more resilient emergent futures, and becoming a key element in pursuing the objectives of the European Green Deal.

Adapting to climate change involves taking proactive steps to prepare for and respond to its current impacts while anticipating and addressing future challenges. Even with ongoing efforts to reduce emissions and achieve carbon neutrality, a warmer climate is not unavoidable³⁸. To face this reality, it's necessary to adjust our way of producing, consuming and living, and enhancing our ability to cope with the effects of climate change.

The Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change is focusing its efforts on supporting EU regions, cities and local authorities in their efforts to build resilience against the impacts of climate change, by putting into practice the EU's Adaptation Strategy³⁹. A Strategy that has four principle objectives: to make adaptation smarter, faster, and more systemic, and to step up international action on adaptation to climate change. This strategy supports regions in gaining a deeper understanding of the climate risks they currently face and those anticipated in the future. It helps them design pathways to enhance preparedness and adapt to a changing climate while testing and implementing innovative solutions to build resilience. By 2030, the mission aims to guide at least 150 European regions and communities toward achieving climate resilience. According to the Mission's main webpage⁴⁰, achievements across these regions should be addressed through three main, interrelated, set of actions and principles:

1. better understand the climate risks they are and will be confronted with in the future;
2. develop their pathways to be prepared and cope with climate change;
3. test and deploy on the ground innovative solutions needed to build resilience.

38

<https://www.carbonbrief.org/explainer-will-global-warming-stop-as-soon-as-net-zero-emissions-are-reached/>

39 https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/adaptation-climate-change/eu-adaptation-strategy_en

40

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/adaptation-climate-change_en

Furthermore, an integrated portal⁴¹ is made available for this Mission, as a “one-stop-shop” for resources, projects, solutions and knowledge exchange opportunities related to enabling and/or fostering EU regions in achieving climate resilience and the Mission’s overarching objectives.

Explore the Portal

Figure 10: Adaptation to Climate Change Mission Platform

4.2.2 CS Projects Contributing to the Adaptation to Climate Change Mission

Within the review performed about the Adaptation to Climate Change Mission, a total of 108 CS projects have been identified and selected to date. Of these, 76 projects have been analysed using the CROPS Upscaling Framework with respect to their upscaling enablers, as outlined in Section 3.

Given the mission's complexity and its engagement with a wide range of stakeholders, this preliminary analysis has identified 10 clusters. These clusters serve to categorise the thematic areas and approaches adopted by the CS initiatives contributing to the mission's objectives and to focus this review and assessment further. Indeed, projects differ substantially across these clusters, which therefore require a dedicated and tailored approach.

1. **Biodiversity (n=35):** The majority of projects assessed within the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change are connected to biodiversity. A prominent example of a citizen science movement for improving our understanding and monitoring of biodiversity within this cluster is *iNaturalist*⁴², a globally recognised platform addressing biodiversity-related concerns. Since its inception in 2008, *iNaturalist* has evolved into a digital meeting space that fosters the development of localized and contextualised projects. It enables citizens and nature enthusiasts to contribute observations about diverse

⁴¹ <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission>

⁴² <https://www.inaturalist.org/>

ecosystems, thereby advancing research efforts by individual and collective scientists worldwide.

CS contributions to these projects typically involve observations of natural and faunal ecosystems, with the resulting data often displayed via apps, digital platforms, maps, or dashboards. As many of these projects originate from grassroots efforts, they also provide valuable insights to the academic research community. Specifically, they help identify the taxonomy of topics related to climate change and biodiversity that are most relevant or noticeable to citizens and other participants in the citizen science community.

Figure 11: iNaturalist Citizen Science Projects Dashboard

2. **Pollinators (n=5):** Among the CS projects dedicated to observing nature and biodiversity, a distinct cluster focuses on encouraging individuals to create, maintain, and monitor pollinator-friendly habitats, thereby fostering their role as pollinator stewards within society. These projects typically produce outputs such as apps and dashboards to facilitate the exploration of observations, as well as annual reports that provide insights derived from collected data. A good example of a CS project within this cluster is BeeWatching.it⁴³, a project which takes place in Italy, and focuses on monitoring bees and butterflies. By supporting research efforts, these initiatives contribute to the preservation of various pollinator ecosystems, including those of bees and butterflies.

⁴³ <https://www.beewatching.it/>

Figure 12: BeeWatch.it Dashboard, Monitoring of Bees and Butterflies

3. **Climate Assembles (n=3):** Likely due to the prominence of open and public discussions about climate change in societal discourse and the importance of engaging citizens to enhance their awareness of current challenges, several CS projects within this mission have adopted innovative participatory approaches. Some of these projects have organised citizen assemblies, such as the CARE Citizen Arenas project⁴⁴, providing platforms for knowledge exchange and discussion on the complexities of climate change, typically between local residents and the related public sector agencies. These assemblies foster dialogue about individual and collective responsibilities in addressing these challenges and exploring more democratic pathways toward global solutions, by collectively influencing policy making.

4. **Digitise Information (n=1):** One project within this mission stands out for its focus on collective action to transcribe handwritten letters received by the Botanic Garden of the University of Coimbra between 1870 and 1928, the Plant Letters project⁴⁵. These letters, written by more than 1,100 correspondents from around the world, offer valuable historical insights and contribute to a deeper understanding of global botanical networks and environmental knowledge during that period. The contribution of CS in this instance is about providing volunteers' time and effort to digitise previously printed material.

⁴⁴ <https://citizenarenas.eu/en/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/catedraunesco/plant-letters>

Figure 13: Plant Letters landing

5. **Education for Behavioral Change (n=9):** Several projects have been identified that address climate change by focusing on the creation of literacy and educational resources to raise societal awareness about these global challenges. The aim of these CS initiatives such as the GreenSCENT project, is typically to empower individuals by providing knowledge and tools to understand their environmental impact and to encourage behaviour, lifestyle, and consumption changes that contribute to environmental improvement. Typically, these projects develop surveys and apps that allow citizens to assess the sustainability of their lifestyles. They also offer practical suggestions for adopting less impactful habits, beginning with small, everyday actions that collectively lead to meaningful change.

GreenSCENT Knowledge Graph

Knowledge management (KM) is a multidisciplinary approach that involves creating, sharing, using, and managing knowledge and information within an organization. It has been recognized as a discipline since 1991 and is taught in various fields such as business administration, information systems, management, library science, and information science. KM aims to leverage knowledge to enhance organizational performance, gain a competitive advantage, foster innovation, facilitate the sharing of lessons learned, promote integration, and drive continuous improvement. One aspect of KM is personal knowledge management, which focuses on managing knowledge at the individual level. It emphasizes the importance of people, their behaviors, and learning processes in knowledge management efforts. Early case studies highlighted the dimensions of strategy, process, and measurement in managing knowledge effectively. Measurement, benchmarking, and incentives are essential to drive cultural change and ensure successful knowledge management at the personal level.

Figure 14: GreenSCENT “Knowledge Graph” tool page

6. **Energy (n=1):** One project assessed within this mission focuses on facilitating data exchange between photovoltaic installation owners and scientists while fostering the development of a solar energy community. The Generation Solar⁴⁶ initiative aims to bridge the gap between practitioners and researchers, promoting collaborative efforts to optimise solar energy use and advance renewable energy solutions.
7. **Indigenous Knowledge (n=2):** Two projects have been identified that aim to integrate insights from indigenous and local knowledge into climate research. For instance, the OpenTEK⁴⁷ project has developed a CS platform designed to document climate change impacts as reported by local communities and researchers. By bringing together these diverse data sources, the project seeks to enhance understanding of how climate change affects both people and ecosystems, fostering a more comprehensive and inclusive approach to climate research.
8. **Land use and land cover (LULC) Monitoring (n=4):** Several projects within this cluster address climate change through the lens of land use land cover

⁴⁶ <https://generationsolar.ies.upm.es/about-sider>

⁴⁷ <https://opentek.eu/licci>

monitoring. These initiatives engage citizens in collecting evidence of rapid changes in land, such as *POC21 - Harnessing the power of Crowdsourcing for Mountain Monitoring*⁴⁸, a Swiss-based project that leverages CS to monitor the evolution of glaciers and rock-fall events.

9. **Meteorological Data (n=5):** Some projects are advancing the understanding of climate change by monitoring meteorological patterns and changes and, in some cases, the impact on the environment. For example, MySnowMap⁴⁹ is a CS initiative that generates a snow map using a physically-based model to estimate snow evolution, based on the energy and mass balance of the snowpack. The model incorporates input data from numerical weather predictions and in-situ snow measurements performed by citizen scientists, providing valuable insights into snow dynamics and their relationship to climate change.
10. **Monitoring Ecology (n=11):** this last cluster includes CS projects that typically have a wide scope, often including multiple elements of the previous categories. In this way, we identified 11 projects focused on advancing research on long-term ecosystems through ecological monitoring. These initiatives bring people together to monitor the impacts of natural hazards, such as floods, while also providing an essential source of non-traditional data for tracking progress in understanding climate change. Additionally, these projects highlight the capacity of citizen science to foster social innovations that contribute to furthering climate change research and resilience efforts. A popular example from the CS community is GroundTruth 2.0⁵⁰ an EU-funded project covering several environmental indicators in urban and rural areas (e.g. water quality and quantity, air quality, phenology, biodiversity, heat, human-wildlife incidents). These are then related to a variety of issues ranging, for example, from spatial planning to land and natural resources management.

4.2.3 CS and Adaptation to Climate Change Mission: A Summary So Far

The breadth of the Mission and the high number of fields and topics covered, led us to identifying a wide variety of projects. These arguably differ in terms of their approach, their intended impact, and the scientific fields surrounding them. The 76 projects reviewed (of the total 108 listed - see full list in Appendix 2) were clustered across 10 groups whereby projects within the same cluster are aligned in terms of their intended impact and contribution to the Mission. These will become the, more manageable and consistent, units of analysis for the ongoing scalability assessment being performed. In other words, we will focus on each

⁴⁸ <https://www.mountainow.net/en/community/>

⁴⁹ <https://eu-citizen.science/project/118>

⁵⁰ <https://gt20.eu/>

cluster of project under each Mission separately in order to improve the consistency of the approach. When decisions will have to be made with respect to cross-clusters upscaling potential, this high variety of projects may inhibit a coherent comparison among them. Like for the previous Mission, we expect the validation efforts with domain experts to provide important inputs in this direction.

All in all, monitoring biodiversity evolution appears to be the dominant contribution of CS to the Mission. It is also noted that several biodiversity projects have not been included in the analysis. *iNaturalist* is, by far, the dominating platform and standard for this effort, and in itself, it includes thousands of projects and initiatives. This overarching platform is however actively considered as one key example of joint effort towards a common global goal of monitoring and understanding biodiversity.

More broadly, the same ‘breadth versus depth’ challenge explained regarding the Soil Mission is relevant here both within the clusters and across.

This Mission, interestingly, also shows variety when the funding models leveraged by the projects are considered. In particular, while public funding is dominant, it is less prevalent when compared to the other four Missions (64% of the total). The remaining is distributed among public/private models (14%), donations (6%), private (5%) and other funding mechanisms.

4.3 Climate Neutral Smart Cities

4.3.1. Introduction to the Mission

Climate change affects all of us, making transformative action both necessary and inevitable. Currently, cities account for over 65% of global energy consumption and more than 70% of CO₂ emissions. Despite occupying only 4% of the EU’s land area, cities house 75% of its population⁵¹, positioning them as key players in achieving the European Green Deal objectives. Consequently, cities have the potential to lead in advancing sustainable and resilient urban futures.

Aligned with this vision, the European agenda emphasises engaging citizens in the co-creation and support of the Climate Neutral Smart Cities Mission, often indicated as the Cities Mission. At its core, the Mission aims to foster inclusivity while addressing environmental challenges. The Cities Mission currently focuses

51

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/climate-neutral-and-smart-cities_en

on two primary goals⁵²: (1) achieving 100 climate-neutral and smart cities by 2030, and (2) transforming these cities into innovation hubs to inspire and enable all European cities to achieve similar outcomes by 2050.

The success of this Mission relies also on active citizen engagement and social innovation, thus opening potential for CS to contribute to it. National and regional support has been mobilised through the 112 cities (100 cities in the EU and 12 cities in countries associated) selected from the 377 applications received in response to the April 2022 Call for Expressions of Interest to join the mission.

A key instrument for implementing this mission is the **NetZeroCities** platform⁵³, which aids cities in developing **Climate City Contracts (CCC)**⁵⁴. These contracts are described as “governance innovation tools” designed to help cities overcome barriers, accelerate transformative action, and achieve climate neutrality by 2030. The CCC provides a comprehensive overview of a city’s current emissions, the required actions to achieve climate neutrality, and the associated investment needed. This makes the CCC a key tool for engaging stakeholders in climate action, as it provides a clear, structured framework for planning and collaboration.

The Mission’s Platform also serves as a collaborative channel, enabling cities to exchange best practices, and establish connections with other cities in their respective countries. This has led to the creation of a “community of ambitious cities” driven to accomplish the goals of the Cities Mission. This platform facilitates the discussion of common challenges related to accelerating climate-neutral solutions.

4.3.2 CS Projects Contributing to the Smart Cities Mission

From the searching step, 81 CS projects have been included in this review with respect to the Climate Neutral Smart Cities Mission. Of these, at the time of writing this document, 60 have been assessed with respect to their suitability for upscaling.

The projects clustered under this Mission represent, if compared with the other four, a much wider variety of scopes. Like for the other Missions, for the purpose of this review, it is useful to extract different categories of projects to enable a more consistent analysis and comparison. In total, in the context of Smart Cities, 15 different topics, or areas of intervention, have been identified and are presented next⁵⁵.

⁵²

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/climate-neutral-and-smart-cities_en

⁵³ <https://netzerocities.app/signin>

⁵⁴ <https://netzerocities.eu/climate-city-contract/>

⁵⁵ It is noted that four of these clusters are presented together under “Other Pollution Monitoring”.

1. **Sustainable Mobility** (n=11): 11 of the 60 projects assessed address aspects of sustainable mobility, from different perspectives. These can be broken down into at least three main categories of projects.

First, CS has proven effective in contributing to sustainable mobility outcomes through generating and providing quantitative and qualitative data as evidence to inform policy making. One example is Telraam⁵⁶ CS Sensor and its associated platform (Figure 15), which has been leveraged in several projects, e.g. WeCount⁵⁷. The sensor provides quantitative data on traffic counting, showcasing in near real time how many cars, bicycles, pedestrians, and trucks pass in front of the sensor and at what speed. Interestingly, traffic counting in itself can be used in several related fields such as urban planning, road safety, traffic management, air and noise pollution, to mention a few. In other words, Telraam allows local projects and communities to adapt the intervention to the topics that are more relevant for them.

Figure 15: Telraam CS Data Platform on Traffic Counting

A second type of project refers to those focused on co-creating and co-designing services and applications that allow for more sustainable mobility behaviours. The idea of these is usually to provide citizens with accessible information to promote the use of sustainable means of transportation, mainly bicycles, or to minimise their exposure to pollution as they travel in their urban environment, e.g., the so called “green routes” provided by projects such as *Every Walk You Take*⁵⁸, etc.

⁵⁶ <https://telraam.net/>

⁵⁷ <https://we-count.net/>

⁵⁸ <https://ciencia-ciudadana.weebly.com/>

Third, CS in mobility has also been leveraged to enable citizens to effectively report their experiences as they move in their cities, in an attempt to establish evidence-based policy debates with the local authorities or to prompt certain public services (e.g., road management). This is for example the case of BiciZen⁵⁹ which consists of a collaborative platform that allows users to share data and information about cycling. This information includes aspects such as: bicycle parking, theft, safety, conflicts with other road users, or obstructions in cycle paths, and more.

2. **Air Quality** (n=12): the most common focus of the 60 projects assessed in this Mission is about monitoring air quality in urban environments. Unlike the previous cluster, the main aims of these projects are well aligned. These revolve around generating granular data about air pollution, sometimes enriched by qualitative experiences of the participants. The main enablers are (both digital and analog) low cost air quality sensors that allow much more granular deployment if compared with more traditional air quality measurement systems formally adopted by public authorities. The outcomes of these projects are also somewhat aligned and typically span across four elements: provide evidence for policy making; raise awareness of people about air pollution; provide a new source of data to science; and advance innovation of low cost technologies and open data platforms through continuous agile experimentation.
3. **Other Pollution Monitoring:** several other projects, in a similar fashion as for the air quality ones (i.e. low cost measurement technology/processes to generate GIS pollution data showcased in an open platform), focus on monitoring other types of pollution. These include: **Odour Pollution** (n=1) in D-Noses⁶⁰ for the development of citizen-generated odour maps and an integrated observatory; **Noise Pollution** (n=3) where the focus is on measuring and reporting noise levels; **Light Pollution** (n=1) in the case of *Globe at Night*⁶¹; and **Water Pollution** (n=1) link in the case of the RISE-Program⁶² focused on water sanitation and management in urban settings.
4. **Promoting Sustainable and Healthy Lifestyles** (n=7): these seven CS projects employ different strategies and tools to ultimately foster cultural and behavioural change in order to mitigate negative environmental impacts on both individuals and communities. While certain aspects are covered within other clusters (e.g. foster sustainable mobility behaviours, recycling practices etc.), these projects typically have multiple focuses. One common pattern

⁵⁹ <https://www.bicizen.org/>

⁶⁰ <https://dnoses.eu/>

⁶¹ <https://globeatnight.org/>

⁶² <https://www.rise-program.org/>

across these 7 projects is fostering cultural and behavioural change from education and awareness. The description of one of these projects, PS Lifestyles⁶³, summarises this concept: “*The project is closing the gap between climate awareness and individual action. Its aim is to inspire citizens to adopt a positive, sustainable, and healthier lifestyle by helping reduce their environmental impact*”.

Figure 16: PS Lifestyle Homepage

5. **Food Systems** (n=1): one project, i.e., *Urban Food Resilience*⁶⁴, focuses specifically on food systems in cities. Even though a big part of this project is to foster more sustainable behaviours when buying and consuming food, this project is considered separately given its wider scope in terms of mapping and understanding local food systems. CS in this way adds to the actual food system a layer of how it is perceived and experienced. This ultimately aims at generating data informed policies to foster more sustainable systems across all actors of the food supply chain in cities.
6. **Enabling Participatory Democracy Processes** (n=6): similar to the case of Climate Assemblies in the Adaptation to Climate Change Mission (see Section 4.2 above), 6 of the CS projects encountered focus on enabling dialogues and participatory decision making processes between citizens communities and public authorities or policy makers more generally. Projects vary in terms of scope and level of engagement. For example, *Opush*⁶⁵ is a project whereby librarians, scientists, community managers, city administration and members of the general public work together toward building a community of practice for sustainable urban development. Others, such as *Balaguer Citizen Science Kiosks*⁶⁶, are about giving locals the opportunity to provide input into existing

⁶³ <https://fulfill-sufficiency.eu/>

⁶⁴ <http://www.urbanfloodresilience.ac.uk/>

⁶⁵ <https://opush.net/>

⁶⁶ <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/14/6/2544>

problems and enriching existing data and knowledge with bottom up experiences and opinions. In this case, this is achieved through the establishment of physical kiosks with questionnaires and surveys for participant inputs on sensors and other data about the city and its functioning.

7. **Weather and Extreme Events Monitoring in Cities** (n=4): although partially related to the Adaptation to Climate Change Mission, four CS projects on weather and extreme events were clustered here since the main scope is argued to be more around improving resilience of cities, i.e. an integrated component of cities becoming “smart”. Interestingly, the four projects have distinct focusses across them: *Trusted Spotter Network Austria*⁶⁷ complements national weather data with observations from citizens, including photos; *On the Trail of Springs*⁶⁸ focuses specifically on preserving springs from monitoring occurrence and consequences of extreme weather events; *Urban Heat Stories*⁶⁹ to structure data about the impact of global warming in different neighbourhoods of a city through qualitative storytelling and experiences shared by the locals; and finally *Fire Database*⁷⁰, a collectively developed database and GIS map of fire observations (it is noted that this operates both within and outside urban places and spaces). All four projects originated in Austria.
8. **Floods Monitoring** (n=5): this cluster includes five projects focused on augmenting cities’ resilience to flooding events. As an example the US-based project *ISeeChange*⁷¹ enables citizens to report flooding events in real time. These observations and data are then transformed into actionable insights using AI and sensor data. These insights can enable cities, engineers, and utilities to prioritise infrastructure investments and design resilient solutions. In a more preventive fashion, *FloodCitySense*⁷², leverages similar data but for enabling early warning systems, and being able to react more promptly to flooding events. The peculiarity of these projects, compared with other ‘events monitoring’ ones, is that there is usually a more collaborative setting between the citizen communities and the public sector (or those accountable for flood risk management in the city). In other words, data is most commonly used to improve existing services, rather than for advocacy actions.
9. **Energy** (n=2): two more projects were found to be active in the Energy domain in cities. First, *Twinergy*⁷³, a recently completed EU project, focused on

⁶⁷ <https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/wettermelden-at-trusted-spotter-network-austria-649>

⁶⁸ <https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/on-the-trail-of-springs>

⁶⁹ <https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/urban-heat-stories>

⁷⁰ <https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/fire-database-536>

⁷¹ <https://www.iseechange.com/>

⁷² <http://www.floodcitisense.eu/>

⁷³ <https://www.twinergy.eu/>

exploring with citizen communities new twin-based solutions to improve renewable energy integration and explore the concept of energy communities as a whole. The second, *Power Poor*⁷⁴ is another EU-funded project covering energy poverty aspects in this transition to renewable conversation and process. Both projects are about local interventions to steer behavioural change. Importantly in the context of upscaling, the pilots in which both projects had been implemented had to have an already mature and widely adopted renewable energy infrastructure in place at the start, since creating this infrastructure was beyond their scope. Therefore, these projects may have greater upscaling potential only to those places and contexts where these infrastructures already exist.

10. Waste Management (n=1): one project, i.e. *Recycling Heroes*⁷⁵, leverages CS to tackle issues related to waste generation in cities, with a specific focus on e-waste. Unlike other projects that have a more prominent aim of shaping policies or improving public services, *Recycling Heroes* focuses more on individual and collective behaviours and actions to enact circular economy principles. It also includes hands-on activities to create new products from e-waste.

11. Nature Based Solutions (n=3): the last cluster within this Mission refers to three CS projects that tackle the creation of ecological spaces in urban areas through Nature Based Solutions (NBS). The level of involvement of citizens across these three projects vary. It spans from a marginal role in creating an overarching framework centered on NBS for renaturing urban spaces like in the case of *Upsurge*⁷⁶, to instances like the EU-funded *Just Nature Project*⁷⁷, where participants contribute to the planning and implementation of NBS with a more active and central role. In all three projects, the ultimate goal is to reduce cities' carbon footprints and improve air quality. However, none provides convincing evidence that these outcomes have (or have not) been achieved.

4.3.3 CS and the Climate Neutral Smart Cities Mission: A Summary So Far

The findings to-date within the Climate Neutral Smart Cities one also indicate the need to develop a tailored approach. This led to identify 11 clusters of projects as the subsequent units of analysis for the actual (ongoing) scalability assessment.

All in all, the contribution of CS to the development of Smart Cities has been in the EU agenda for more than a decade (Craglia and Granell, 2014). Already then, “*lack of reproducibility of results and longitudinal analysis*” were already

⁷⁴ <https://powerpoor.eu/>

⁷⁵ <https://www.recyclingheroes.at/>

⁷⁶ <https://www.upsurge-project.eu/>

⁷⁷ <https://justnatureproject.eu/>

considered one of the key challenges for CS to effectively realise its potential. This is usually traced back to funding structures (mainly relying on public funding - 72.3% of those assessed so far) and data quality, including interoperability, accessibility, and reliability. These will be therefore considered with particular attention during the assessment of the upscaling potential. Beyond this reflection, three additional challenges have emerged from the research so far:

1. **One platform per project as opposed to one platform per theme:** unlike the Mission Adaptation to Climate Change and specifically the example of iNaturalist as the main hub and platform for CS biodiversity related projects, the Smart Cities Mission currently lacks this reference architecture and (digital) infrastructure. Each project, e.g. in the context of air quality, tends to have its own map, platform, standard, and approach to measurements. The result is a scattered ecosystem of projects, rather than a unified and integrated effort to map and understand air quality across EU countries.
2. **Uptake from public sector agencies and policy makers appears so far to be the most prevalent success factor,** for these projects to ultimately generate outcomes that actively and directly contribute to the Mission. With respect to considerations on upscaling potential, this means that the dynamics and enabling factors that allowed this fruitful collaboration between citizen scientists and policy makers in the project at stake need to be carefully understood. This is because establishing this link in an effective way may take significant time and effort to be accomplished. Also, this factor may be dependent on local cultures, with some EU countries that are knowingly more prone to citizen engagement in policy making than others.
3. **Evidence from data use for research is lacking:** another potential, and explicitly argued in several projects, contribution to the Mission may come from new scientific discoveries enabled by the data generated as part of the CS projects themselves. Several projects considered here generate open data on certain relevant phenomena (e.g. noise, air quality, light pollution etc.). The main value of this novel source of data, compared with existing one, is typically increased granularity and (sometimes) richness through embedding people's perspectives and experiences. However, evidence of effective use of these data for research is often lacking, making it more difficult to explore the actual contributions of these projects in terms of outcomes addressing the Mission.

These aspects are tackled carefully during the ongoing scalability assessment.

4.4 Restore our Ocean and Waters

4.4.1. Introduction to the Mission

The health of our Oceans and Waters is fundamental to life on Earth, providing -among others- essential resources, regulating the climate, connecting countries and supporting a multitude of diverse ecosystems. Yet, the Ocean and Waters are currently facing unprecedented challenges, including pollution, overfishing, ocean acidification, climate change, habitat destruction, freshwater scarcity, which threaten biodiversity, human livelihoods, and global sustainability, to mention a few.⁷⁸

In Europe and globally, the urgency to restore aquatic ecosystems has become a critical common mission. The EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters” recognises this need, aiming to protect and regenerate the health of marine and freshwater environments, through research and innovation, citizen engagement and the so called blue investments. The mission takes an integrated approach, fostering cooperation among governments, industries, communities, and researchers. Its vision is to address the health of the ocean and waters as a key role in achieving climate neutrality and restoring nature. This initiative represents a collective commitment to healing our planet’s heart and securing a sustainable future.

Considering the amount of chartered projects, partners and funding schemes, the Restore Our Ocean and Water Mission⁷⁹ is arguably the most developed and articulated among all 5. It includes a portal as a one stop shop for all information and resources related to the Mission, such as access to funding, opportunity to engage with peers and other stakeholders, and monitor progress towards the Mission’s objectives. The mission plays a vital role in advancing the European Green Deal and achieving its 2030 objectives, including protecting and restoring biodiversity, preventing and eliminating pollution, and transforming the blue economy to a carbon-neutral and circular model. Through its lighthouses, the mission fosters collaboration and ensures effective coordination at both EU and regional levels, driving impactful actions towards these goals.

To make ocean knowledge readily available to citizens, entrepreneurs, scientists and policymakers, the Mission is enabling cross-cutting actions, in particular a digital ocean and water knowledge system, known as Digital Twin Ocean⁸⁰, which

⁷⁸ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/how-climate-change-impacts>

⁷⁹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters_en

⁸⁰ More information available at: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters_en

aims to simulate the complexity of components of the ocean, offering insights into its past and present states, while generating reusable predictions about its future ecosystem behaviour. It encompasses understanding how the system functions, its interconnected elements, and the broader network of related initiatives and projects contributing to this innovative approach. In doing so, the mission specifically supports the engagement of citizens, providing a direct endorsement for marine & freshwater CS initiatives in enhancing Ocean knowledge and health to achieve climate neutrality and restore nature's ecosystems.

4.4.2 CS projects contributing to the Ocean and Waters Mission

The Mission on Restoring Our Ocean and Waters (indicated here as “Ocean and Waters Mission”) has the highest number of projects (120) identified in our analysis. According to the CROPS Upscaling Framework discussed in Section 2.7, CS projects that are “easy to use and understand” and “Aligning with matter of concern” are more likely to be successfully scaled up compared to those that are not. Currently, CS projects addressing the urgent challenges facing our oceans and waters are particularly popular among the public. This popularity may stem from the widespread coverage of these issues in news media and on social platforms, which fosters empathy and enhances public understanding, making these topics more accessible and engaging for citizens. These aspects are expected to play an important role when fostering upscaling of CS impact on the Ocean and Waters Mission.

So far, 104 out of the 120 total projects have been reviewed and assessed within this period. From a first analysis of the ensemble of projects collected, it is possible to define 8 clusters to categorise them further and to enable meaningful analysis and comparisons.

1. Monitoring water ecology (n=19)
2. Marine Biodiversity Monitoring (n=60)
3. Litter and Waste (n=14)
4. Water Quality (n=6)
5. Meteorological events monitoring (n=2)
6. Sea Safety (n=1)
7. Ocean Radioactivity (n=1)
8. Art for Awareness (n=1)

Consistent with the structure adopted in this deliverable, these are tackled separately below.

open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters/european-digital-twin-ocean-european-dto_en

Monitoring water ecology

The second most populated cluster found from this Mission is the one we generally labelled as Monitoring Water Ecology. The projects that have been assessed under this cluster are typically projects with a broad scope, with a focus on monitoring several elements and variables of both seas and freshwaters.

Common elements are found within projects under this cluster. First, the scope is typically broad and includes tackling several elements of interest (e.g. biodiversity, evolution, pollution, plastic etc.) in seas and freshwater ecosystems within the same project. Second, the majority of these are contribution-based projects, where citizens observe the marine environment, collect and submit sightings or small monitorings through a download application on a mobile phone or laptop. Other projects -similar in their scope (i.e. understanding as many variables as possible) - are in fact based on contributions where specific hardware is needed, such as the example of the Smartfin project⁸¹, where the citizen scientists need to install a smart fin sensor technology in the surf board for generating measurements and data. The data collected by the participants are typically visible in open dashboards, but not always.

A good example is FLOW⁸², a CS project featured as an initiative that helped different German regions to show that small agricultural streams are in poor ecological status. As argued in one of their papers⁸³: 137 samples were conducted in small stream monitoring sites across Germany, 83% of which were located in agricultural catchments, with more than 900 citizen scientists in 96 groups. Such citizen-driven monitoring of the status of watercourses could play a crucial role in monitoring and implementing the objectives of the European Water Framework Directive, thus contributing to restoring and protecting freshwater ecosystems.

⁸¹ <https://www.surfrider.org/programs/smartfin>

⁸² <https://www.flow-projekt.de/>

⁸³ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0048969724013226?via%3Dihub>

Figure 17: Front page of FLOW project

Marine Biodiversity Monitoring

This cluster is the most represented in our sample as it includes 60 CS projects. As argued earlier in this chapter, the goals and objectives driving the Ocean and Waters Mission, are well-aligned with the ones of the Mission on Adaptation Climate Change. Arguably, a total of 4 of 5 EU Missions are systematically interconnected and aligned within the realm of the European Green Deal, among other European strategies for a more resilient and sustainable emergent future in Europe. In this sense, the projects categorised within the cluster of Marine Biodiversity Monitoring, are also supporting the Mission of Adaptation to Climate Change. The scope is similar as to what argued on Monitoring Biodiversity in section 4.2.2, i.e. mapping and monitoring biodiversity in marine environments and their evolution. To show the variety of focuses in this cluster, we propose three examples: SeaSearch⁸⁴, Reef Check⁸⁵, and Seagrass Spotter⁸⁶.

Figure 18: Front page of Seasearch project

SeaSearch (see Figure 18 above) is a UK-based initiative enabling divers and snorkelers to record marine life, habitats, and changes in underwater environments, supporting marine conservation and sustainable management efforts. Reef Check Med empowers volunteer divers and snorkelers to monitor and protect Mediterranean marine ecosystems by surveying underwater biodiversity, identifying threats, and promoting conservation through CS, education, and community engagement initiatives.

⁸⁴ <https://www.seasearch.org.uk/>

⁸⁵ <https://www.reefcheckmed.org/>

⁸⁶ <https://seagrassspotter.org/>

Welcome to the Mediterranean Sea

This website is about the monitoring protocols for the Mediterranean Sea developed by the Reef Check organizations working in this geographic area since 2008. To know more about the Reef Check Foundation and its worldwide activities please visit:

<http://reefcheck.org/>

To know more about the activities carried out by each national organisations please visit their websites.

Figure 19: Front page of Reef Check Med project

SeagrassSpotter is a global CS platform enabling individuals to map and monitor seagrass meadows, supporting marine conservation efforts by enhancing knowledge of these vital underwater ecosystems and their role in biodiversity.

Figure 20: Front page of SeagrassSpotter project

An important common denominator among these projects is their need for appropriately training participants before they can generate data and observations. Participants must typically attend a specific training program in order to participate. An analysis of what these trainings are and what they entail (both for trainers and trainees) is currently being undertaken.

Litter and Waste

Water pollution is a critical global issue that directly impacts ecosystems, human health, and the sustainability of freshwater and marine ecosystems. Addressing

this challenge is essential. Waste streams originate from various human activities, including industrial processes, agricultural practices, urban runoff, fishing activities, domestic wastewater and more. Tackling water pollution requires understanding of the different sources of waste, and implementing targeted strategies to reduce their impact. This is where CS projects which are mapping ocean and water pollution have an influence on, supporting solutions for this global challenge. Within the realm of this cluster, projects cover one or more of a chain of activities:

1. **Collect (action)**, i.e. engage citizens in waste collection campaigns and organised actions typically at seaside.
2. **Monitor and Track (data input)**, as waste is collected, citizen scientists may engage in producing data about the waste encountered, e.g. through photos and observations or dedicated mobile apps.
3. **(Open) Data Platform**, sometimes the data generated from the waste collected is showcased in open data platforms. The purpose is to provide open data, with the intention of enhancing the awareness of the public on the topic, who take part in these activities. With respect to the actual open data generated and made available, there are mainly two possible outcomes enabled by using it:
 - a. Use for Science, in those cases where the data are adopted by researchers for scientific endeavours.
 - b. Use for Policy and Advocacy, in other cases where the data are adopted by public service providers and/or policy makers, e.g. to establish protected areas, or to label places in relation to their safety.

Figure 21: Spectrum of contributions of CS projects addressing Litter and Waste

As clarified above, not all projects cover all activities, but only a subset of these. Others tend to cover part of this spectrum. In line with these differences, based on the project's scope, we have classified the CS initiatives in this cluster into different groups.

First, five CS projects included in this review focus on the entire spectrum of activities depicted in Figure 21 above. Probably the most popular example where

all the activities and outcomes are approached and that has potentially proven the impact on the Mission based on the CROPS Upscaling Framework (see Section 2.7) is Plastic Pirates⁸⁷. This is a CS project engaging youth and others across Europe to collect and analyse plastic waste in rivers and waterways, raising awareness and contributing data to combat plastic pollution in the European seas, waters, and environments more generally. However, *Plastic Pirates* is one of the compelling examples for conceptualising upscaling, a subject that will be thoroughly addressed in the upcoming CROPS work and deliverables, including the protocols for upscaling.

Figure 22: Front page of PlasticPirate project

Three further projects focus on all activities, without entailing waste collections actions. For example, Debris Tracker⁸⁸ has developed an open app where citizens can upload their litter observations worldwide, providing open data about water pollution to inform research, raise awareness and drive actions against plastic pollution.

Figure 23: Scheme contribution CS projects addressing Litter and Waste II

These types of projects typically happen in those places where the actual collection of waste is either dangerous or challenging, e.g., in rivers, etc.. In these

⁸⁷ <https://www.plastic-pirates.eu/en>

⁸⁸ <https://debristracker.org/>

three projects, data are (argued to be) used for both policy makers and scientific research.

Figure 23: Front page of Debris Tracker project

Within this cluster we also find projects where both the activity “Collection (action)” and the outcome “Use of Science” are not covered - i.e. focused on generating and publishing waste and litter data for policy advocacy. An example of this category is the National Plastic Watch⁸⁹ CS project, based in the Netherlands and led by the TU Delft’s WaterLab, which involves citizens in monitoring plastic pollution in Dutch waterways, fostering awareness, data collection, and solutions to address plastic waste in aquatic ecosystems.

Figure 24: Scheme contribution CS projects addressing Litter and Waste III

⁸⁹ <https://www.tudelft.nl/scd/waterlab/doe-mee-aan-onderzoek/project-6-nationale-plasticwatch>

Figure 25: Front page of National Plastic Watch project

Finally, there are projects within this cluster where the primary activity involves waste collection but does not include data monitoring, and, as a consequence, its publication in open data platforms. Rather, these types of projects (two in total have been found so far) tends to be focused primarily on raising awareness among participants, as they engage directly with the issue during waste collection efforts. The analysis of the collected waste contributes to scientific research on the topic and has the potential to support policy development and advocacy efforts.

Figure 26: Scheme contribution CS projects addressing Litter and Waste

As an example, the MCS Wild Bottle Sightings⁹⁰ consists of a series of campaigns encouraging people to report discarded plastic bottles collected in nature, helping track pollution patterns, raise awareness, and support policy efforts to reduce plastic waste in the environment.

⁹⁰ <https://naee.org.uk/wildbottlesighting/>

Figure 27: Front page of MCS Wild Bottle Sightings project

As a preliminary insight from the analysis of this cluster, we argue that the upscaling of these projects will entail a significant effort based on community growth and communication, since its success and extent of contributions largely depends on coverage and participation. Second, raising awareness on the topic is an inherent factor to most of the projects, but is rarely measured.

Water Quality

The fourth cluster within this Mission refers to CS projects focused on monitoring the quality of waters, to enhance the public understanding of the importance of restoring the ocean and waters, to preserve the aquatic ecosystems and to combat its negative impact on natural and human health. Within this cluster, 6 projects have been analysed. One of the most popular and long-lasting examples is the Fresh Water Watch⁹¹ CS project. This project trains communities around the world to measure and monitor the health of their rivers, lakes, streams, ponds and wetlands, so that they can collaborate on restoring freshwater resources. It includes an open measurement kit and substantial supporting resources. Importantly, connected with the discussion on the importance of adaptation when considering upscaling (see Section 2), Fresh Water Watch demonstrates its potential to be applied and adapted to different challenges experienced in different contexts.

⁹¹ <https://www.freshwaterwatch.org/>

Figure 28: Front page of Freshwater Watch project

Meteorological events monitoring

The fifth cluster underlining the fundamental importance of our Ocean and Waters in determining the weather and climate, many CS projects have set out to monitor meteorological events in water basins. One of these projects is the Ice Watch⁹² project, a program coordinating routine visual observations of sea-ice, including icebergs and meteorological parameters. Over 5.600 records have been contributed to date, from numerous ship voyages. Also, this platform is complementary to the Antarctic platform ASPeCt⁹³. At this stage of the analysis, questions regarding the influence of this typology of projects in the Mission arises, wondering whether to consider further or not this topic and approach.

⁹² <https://icewatch.met.no/>
⁹³ <https://aspectssouth.org/>

Figure 29: Front page of Ice Watch project

Sea Safety

The sixth cluster identified within this mission is related to monitoring the safety of the seas and shores. Only one project has been identified within this cluster, i.e. the BEACH Program⁹⁴, which monitors the safety of saltwater swimming beaches from Memorial Day to Labor Day in the US. The project has developed a map of beaches and safety, and also detailed protocols for beach samples, and works annually on a report to present insights on the findings.

Figure 30: The BEACH Program, a Sea Safety project

⁹⁴ www.ecology.wa.gov/Water-Shorelines/Water-quality/Saltwater/BEACH-program

Ocean Radioactivity

One further project has been encountered in relation to monitoring ocean radioactivity. The project Our Radioactive Ocean⁹⁵ helps scientists at the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution understand the ongoing spread of radiation across the Pacific and its evolving impacts on the ocean of Fukushima. We anticipate that the specificity and uniqueness of the issue tackled makes the potential of upscaling less relevant if compared with other projects in this Mission.

Figure 31: Front page of Our Radioactive Ocean project

Art for Awareness

The last cluster assessed within this Mission related to the use of art, as a driver of awareness about challenges related to the aquatic ecosystems within cities. Only one project has been found within this cluster: From Sea to Street⁹⁶. It consists of a CS initiative that collects ocean-themed murals across Europe and investigates which emotions they evoke in the viewer. The goal of this project is to create a stronger relationship and awareness about the sea among participants. This is a key goal of the overall Mission.

⁹⁵ www.ecology.wa.gov/Water-Shorelines/Water-quality/Saltwater/BEACH-program

⁹⁶ <https://equalsea.eu/ongoing-projects/from-sea-to-street/>

Figure 32: Front page of From Sea to Street project

4.4.3 CS and Ocean and Waters Mission: A Summary So Far

This section provided an overview of CS projects that contribute to the Restore Our Ocean and Waters Mission. The insights come from the general descriptions of all 120 identified projects, as well as from the 104 projects that have been assessed with respect to their suitability for upscaling.

Collectively, the CS projects identified in this review address some of the most significant issues currently affecting the ocean and water ecosystems on our planet, such as pollution, climate change and ocean acidification, habitat destruction, loss of biodiversity, invasive species, and freshwater scarcity, among others. However, based on these assessments, we have identified some preliminary insights, somewhat similar to the ones outlined in section 4.1.3 relating to the Soils Mission. At this point, we can identify trends in the challenges and areas that need further investigation in the coming months, which are:

1. **Breadth versus depth dilemma:** as mentioned in the previous chapter, the majority of projects in the Marine Biodiversity Monitoring cluster focus on monitoring specific species and animal inhabitants of aquatic ecosystems. Comparing the impact on the Mission of these projects with those that take a more general approach to observations raises the question of which should be prioritised when considering the potential for scaling up citizen science projects.
2. **Lack of synergies and joint efforts:** The projects assessed within this Mission have, for the vast majority of cases, developed their own methodologies, databases or apps to display the data collected by participants. This may be due, in part, to many projects being developed by local grassroots communities committed to monitoring and finding solutions to preserve specific species of flora and fauna in aquatic ecosystems. This output's

fragmentation makes these projects less comparable, less scalable to other communities, and most of all, less impactful on a policy level.

3. **Training activities:** it has been identified that, to ensure qualitative data collection within the projects supporting the mission to restore our oceans and waters, it is often mandatory for participants to undergo a training program before collecting water samples or filling out surveys. This ensures that participants acquire the basic knowledge and skills needed to accurately record their observations and contribute valuable data to scientific research. This appears to be more prominent in this Mission and particular attention to training resources and processes will be placed in the next phases of the analysis.
4. **Awareness for long-term engagement:** As discussed at the beginning of the chapter on the Ocean and Waters Mission, the topics addressed by the citizen science projects are already familiar to the public, i.e. tend to be common sense and acknowledged as an important priority. According to the CROPS Upscaling Framework discussed in section 3, sharing “a matter of concern” has an influence on the upscaling potential. In this context, most of these projects inherently raise awareness by providing participants with opportunities to engage directly with the issue, such as collecting trash from beaches or water streams. This enhances the understanding of the challenge and empowers participants, encouraging their long-term engagement with the projects.

Furthermore, some factors that will limit the potential scalability in this Mission have been identified as related to the complexity and the need of specific elements during the contribution process of some projects. Examples are projects whereby data is collected through complex sensor systems to be attached to, e.g., people’s boats or water sport equipment, etc. These will be further analysed and discussed during the development of Task 2.2.

Finally, focus on outputs rather than outcomes is also prominent here. For instance, it has been difficult to find evidence of the impact created by different observations made by the contributors to marine biodiversity platforms. Also, in the context of this cluster, we can relate to the dilemma described above on chapter 4.1.3. in terms of breadth and depth of project scopes. In fact, the vast majority of projects assessed are researching specific marine animals and fauna, to better understand how climate change is affecting the species (e.g., turtles, gelatinous organisms, whales and mammals, sharks and rays, seabirds, crabs, manta, coral reefs, mangroves, etc). The contributions to these projects are generally based on collection and submission of data via a specific app or website portal. However, evidence of use of these data is typically lacking.

4.5 Cancer Mission

4.5.1. Introduction to the Mission

Cancer is one of the leading causes of death globally, affecting millions of lives each year and placing an immense burden on individuals, families, and healthcare systems. In Europe, cancer is the number one cause of death for citizens under 65 and the second cause of death for all EU citizens⁹⁷. Cancer affects 2.7 million individuals annually in Europe, with 1.3 million people succumbing to the disease each year.⁹⁸ Without additional interventions, due to the aging population and lifestyle factors, the number of new cancer diagnoses is projected to exceed 3.24 million by 2040. Worldwide, it remains a critical challenge, with disparities in presentation, diagnosis, and treatment across regions.

Addressing cancer is not just a medical necessity but a societal one, demanding innovative research, early detection, equitable healthcare access, and intentional collaboration. Recognising this, the European Union has launched the Mission on Cancer, to foster research on understanding, treating, and ultimately preventing cancer, working towards a healthier and more resilient future for all.

The primary objective of this mission is to enhance the lives of over 3 million people by 2030, focusing on prevention, treatment, and improving the quality of life for those affected by cancer, including their families, so they can live longer and healthier lives⁹⁹.

4.5.2 CS projects contributing to the Cancer Mission

The fifth EU Mission is the least represented in this review. In total, 31 projects that directly contribute to the Cancer Mission have been identified and listed.

As a general strategy for the review within this Mission, we collectively decided to complement these projects with others from the wider healthcare domain. This decision was motivated by the fact that by looking at the actual current contributions of CS to the Mission, projects tackling other diseases and healthcare more generally could be either instrumental for upscaling Cancer-related projects, or could extend their area of intervention and include cancer-related situations.

As an example, a number of Cancer-related projects focus on supporting patients and their families as they experience various phases of their diseases (e.g. diagnosis, recovery etc.). Looking at projects from the wider healthcare domain

⁹⁷ <https://cancer-inequalities.jrc.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/ECIR-inequalities-factsheet-2040-cancer-estimates- May-2023.pdf>

⁹⁸ https://health.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-02/eu_cancer_plan_en_0.pdf

⁹⁹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/eu-mission-cancer_en

may suggest other CS initiatives that pursue the same scope but for other diseases, e.g. diabetes.

Therefore, a two-stage review process has been implemented:

1. Identify all CS projects that directly contribute to the Cancer Mission, and define clusters of similar projects.
2. Target search for healthcare related CS projects from the clusters previously identified.

In total, this process led to listing 77 CS projects, 31 related to Cancer and 46 to healthcare more generally.

Of the 31 projects identified, 29 have been assessed. These collectively belong to 6 clusters as depicted in the table below. These are tackled separately next.

Cluster	Outcomes	Citizens involvement	#
Game or image analysis for collaborative cancer research	Typically for science, with some focus on users gaining awareness	Typically individual tasks. Flexible commitment	15
Care and Recovery	Typically for people (patients, carers, family), self care and/or self screening	Share practices and experiences with other users, consume content	3
Donate Health Data/Records/Samples	For science	Varies from donating samples once, to engage in longitudinal studies	6
Advocacy	For raising awareness and raise funding and/or commitments	That part in ad hoc actions / demonstrations	2
Computational Power	For science, increased analytics potential	Download an app, and share computational power	2
Curating documents	For science	Read and classify documents	1

Table 6: Cancer Mission Projects Clusters

Game or Image Analysis for Collaborative Cancer Research

As the first cluster of CS projects, we found over 50% of those identified focus on engaging people in collaborative cancer research, through leveraging volunteers' analytical contributions - most times through a gaming experience. Their focus is typically well defined within one type of cancer and participants usually contribute with individual tasks of image analysis, e.g. to spot stains, to reconstruct protein structures, to perform DNA analysis etc. In particular, of the 15 projects that belong to this category, the following cancers are tackled: tissue (n=3), breast (4), brain (1), bladder and lung (1), proteins for cancer biology research (1), and 3D genomes cancer cells (1). Four more were found to be similar in nature, but with slightly different outputs and outcomes. Of these, one was found to be focused on cancer research in general, and three more as leveraging the

contributions to feed AI algorithms to be subsequently used in cancer related research.

One of the most famous examples refers to Foldit¹⁰⁰, a CS initiative led by University of Washington and is ongoing since 2007. Foldit consists of a game-like platform where citizens can help researchers by solving puzzles related to protein folding. Although not directly focused on cancer, the initiative upscaled to a situation where it is used also for cancer related research, with several demonstrated value reported over time.

Figure 33: Foldit Main Page and Evidence of impact on cancer Mission

Care and Recovery

The second cluster refers to CS projects where the ultimate goal is to help patients, their families and other carers, going through the often challenging life cycle of a cancer disease. Unlike the previous, where the main, direct, beneficiaries of the projects are researchers, projects in this cluster are often aimed at those affected by cancer and their important others.

¹⁰⁰ <https://fold.it/>

As shown in Table 6 above, three projects belong to this category. Of these, one, i.e. MyPeBS (My Personal Breast Cancer Screening)¹⁰¹, focuses on enabling self screening practices. The additional two are devoted to improving self care.

These typically take the form of knowledge exchange platforms, or dedicated social networks. This is the case of both Citizen Health¹⁰² and Patient Innovation¹⁰³ whereby the projects foster participation of patients and carers to share experiences and practices, practically forming a virtual community of best practices and support mechanisms.

Figure 34: Front page of Citizen Health Project

Donate Health Data / Records / Samples

This third cluster identifies CS projects where the scope is to enable the donation of data or samples for improving cancer related research.

Within the six projects included in this category, one important factor of differentiation refers to the extent of engagement, which translates here to the quantity and the frequency of data or sample donation.

For example, two of these projects, i.e. Rare Cancers Europe¹⁰⁴ and DataSavesLives¹⁰⁵, focus on enabling participants to share medical records, or

¹⁰¹ <https://www.mypebs.eu/the-project/>

¹⁰² <https://www.citizen.health/>

¹⁰³ <https://patient-innovation.com/>

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.esmo.org/policy/rare-cancers-working-group>

¹⁰⁵ <https://datasaveslives.eu/case-colorectal-cancer>

specific medical data, over time, typically to enable a more in-depth and longitudinal study of antecedents and evolution of certain types of cancers.

Others such as Gut Instinct¹⁰⁶ focus on sample donations once, making the participation task granularity significantly lower.

Finally, the last project encountered in this cluster, i.e. EuCanImage¹⁰⁷, relies on participants' donation of health images to feed AI algorithms. The outputs developed is a cancer imaging platform to ultimately enhance AI-based cancer research.

Figure 35: EuCanImage Frontpage

Donating Computational Power

Two of the identified projects are peculiar due to their approach to participation and outputs as they involve participants donating unused computing power to feed into cloud analytics through an application. Both projects are led by foundations related to big corporations, namely Vodafone and IBM, DreamLab¹⁰⁸ and Mapping Cancer Markers¹⁰⁹ respectively. A more in-depth analysis of these two projects will reveal their level of openness and the use and impact from these wide CPU donations.

Others: Advocacy and Curating Documents

In this last cluster, two more types of projects are included. First, two projects were found which focus on organising advocacy actions, typically for more investments

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.gutinstinct.org/>

¹⁰⁷ <https://eucanimage.eu/>

¹⁰⁸ <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=au.com.vodafone.dreamlabapp&hl=es>

¹⁰⁹ <https://www.worldcommunitygrid.org/research/mcm1/overview.s>

and attention to cancer related research and healthcare. One example is the European Cancer Patients Coalition¹¹⁰.

One further project encountered refers to Mark2Cure¹¹¹, a CS platform where volunteers read scientific literature and help categorise information related to diseases, including cancer. In other words, this project leveraged volunteers' contributions in terms of classifying existing medical literature. It lasted for one year (from 2018) when it was interrupted as the leading team acknowledged that it did not produce the expected results (see figure below).

Figure 36: Mark2Cure

4.5.3 CS Projects from the wider healthcare domain

As described above, to compensate for the lower number of projects (compared with the other EU Missions) contributing to Cancer, this list was extended to also include projects with similar focus, although not necessarily focused on cancer-related diseases. This phase of the search was therefore targeted at projects that aim at addressing similar aspects of cancer-related diseases (see clusters above) but for other medical and healthcare issues.

This search led to the inclusion of an additional 28 CS projects (26 of which have been reviewed at the time of writing this deliverable). These relate to:

- Care and Recovery (n=5): inspirations for upscaling cancer related impact of CS is considered from similar projects in the health domain. As an example, Lives¹¹² focuses on vascular liver diseases and support to patients and families, similarly to e.g. Citizen Health described above for the cancer field. The idea is to explore the possibilities for these projects to be extended to

¹¹⁰ <https://ecpc.org/>

¹¹¹ <https://mark2cure.org/>

¹¹² <https://www.livesproject.eu/>

those affected by cancer. In principle, opportunities for upscaling CS for the Cancer Mission may come from leveraging elements of these projects, such as a specific platform or technology for enabling interactions among patients and/or carers, or certain methodologies among other elements.

Figure 37: LIVES Project Homepage

- Collaborative Research (n= 10): although not all projects considered here involve image analysis or gamification (like in the case of the Neureka Project¹¹³), CS in healthcare contributes with several projects that broadly enable collaborative research. For example, in the context of environmental epidemiology, Cities-Health¹¹⁴ in their Barcelona pilot leveraged CS to investigate the relationship between exposure to air pollution and mental health. Again, like in the previous case, projects of this kind are explored for their various elements to be upscaled, or to be instrumental in upscaling other projects.

¹¹³ <https://www.neureka.ie/>

¹¹⁴ <https://www.citieshealth.eu/>

HOW IT WORKS

01

Become a Citizen Scientist

At neureka, we think that everyone should be able to participate in science, that's why we are taking research experiments out of the lab, and into your smartphone! Neureka contains fun games and questionnaires that contribute directly to brain health science. Download neureka for free to become a "Citizen Scientist" and participate in one of the biggest neuroscience studies of all time!

02

Unlock the Science Challenges

Explore Science Challenges which contain combinations of games and questionnaires that tell us things about how your brain works and interacts with the world around you. Take part in the 'Risk Factors' challenge to contribute to the science of early dementia diagnosis or 'Multi-Mood' to contribute to the neuroscience of depression. The more you play, the more we learn! Unlock achievement medals for your contribution to brain health science while learning how to keep your brain healthy!

03

Play Games Daily

With thousands of people already involved, this 'big data' approach to brain health research helps researchers figure out new ways of keeping mental health problems at bay, and promoting resilience to late life cognitive decline. Every minute you completing science challenges in the neureka app helps us move the needle forward in the global fight against brain health disorders. Join us and make a difference to science and to people's lives across the world. We can only make a difference with your help!

Figure 38: Neureka Project

- Sample Donation (n=4): in light of the challenges of upscaling these types of projects in the Mission Cancer (see reflection on infrastructure required), we explored other instances whereby citizens donate samples or health data to advance research. This is to learn further about the possibility to upscale these types of projects, or to even leverage their infrastructures and extend their scope towards also including cancer-related research. To provide some examples, Stick Your Tongue¹¹⁵ (originally in Spanish *Saca la Lengua*) was a CS campaign where people donated saliva samples (together with answering a survey) for medical research; TransBiome¹¹⁶ relies on new transwomen to donate samples of their neovaginas, to gain a better understanding of their microbial diversity and composition of their microbiomes.

4.5.4 CS and the Cancer Mission: A Summary So Far

In this section we focused on reporting the projects reviewed to-date within the Mission Cancer (and wider healthcare domain).

A total of 77 CS projects have been identified and listed and their scalability assessment is currently undergoing. The four main objectives of the Cancer Mission are established as: (1) Understanding of cancer; (2) Prevention and early detection; (3) Diagnosis and treatment; and (4) Quality of life for patients and their

¹¹⁵ <https://www.sacalalengua.org/sobre-el-proyecto/>

¹¹⁶ <https://www.transbiome.org/accueil>

families. Based on the findings presented in this section it emerges that CS's impact on the Mission does not cover all objectives to the same extent. Rather, this section showed how CS (intended) contributions are primarily based on: augmenting research for an increased understanding of cancer - objective (1); and supporting patients and their families / carers to improve their quality of life - objective (4). While only a few instances were found in terms of early detection (see self screening related projects above), as expected the discipline's contribution to Diagnosis and Treatment is minimal in our sample. Finally, it should be considered that some aspects about the prevention of cancer are tackled in CS projects categorised within other missions in this review. For example, antecedents of cancer such as exposure to air pollution, are considered within the Climate Neutral Smart Cities Mission (see section 3.3 for all overlaps and the related decisions taken in this work).

Notwithstanding the fact that the assessment is currently ongoing, the work so far has exposed some preliminary challenges that may play important roles when considering upscaling some of these projects and their outcomes to the transnational level. These are:

1. **Low Level of Openness:** the level of openness of the projects considered here is typically low when compared to other missions. Collaborative research projects from image analysis, for example, are often not supported by open source solutions. AI algorithms supposedly developed from CS endeavors are not transparent, often even with respect to the purpose they serve and for whom. Open data from research (i.e. CS data reused by researchers) is usually not available, not shared, and outputs, or key resources, are rarely fully open for reuse. Typically CS projects are described in detail for the actual participation task to, e.g., donate samples. However, from the other side of the spectrum it appears they enter a form of “blackbox” where little is known about what data is used, how, by whom, and what scientific discoveries are achieved. While this is understandable given the sensitivity of the data at stake, this may have implications on upscaling that will be carefully considered.
2. **Care and Recovery:** the instances of projects tackled within this category raise an important question: where do boundaries lie between social networks and CS? To what extent a platform for knowledge exchange between families of patients can be considered CS? These questions are being discussed internally and explored further.
3. **Clinical Trials:** depending on the channels leveraged, certain participatory projects for cancer related research are described as CS while in fact they are “traditional” pharmaceutical-business driven clinical trials. These typically rely on patients' participation in terms of giving consent to share their medical records. However, these are used e.g. for new drugs discovery

and for business opportunities, rather than open science. For these reasons, these projects are not considered in this review.

4. **Uniqueness:** the vast majority of projects encountered are individual endeavours as opposed to be part of the same narrative and discussion. CS projects in this mission are often based on specific research questions and methodologies crafted around those. As a result, these appear as a scattered ensemble of projects, rather than an integrated effort for CS to directly contribute to the mission. One of the consequences is that the results of such research are often hard to be adopted and reused effectively due to the lack of interoperability, both from the point of view of data attributes, standards, and formats, and from a methodological perspective.
5. **CS a component of bigger projects:** unlike the other missions, it is very common for projects considered here to be large programs. In these, CS is not always the main protagonist, but often a complementary source of insights or a component of bigger projects. This identifies cases whereby upscaling this CS component would entail upscaling of the whole project or program, which is arguably more challenging and beyond the scope of CROPS.
6. **Complex infrastructures are often required for these CS to be implemented:** although partially related to the previous point, this is also the case for those projects that rely on sample and health data donation. These typically require establishing places where people can safely donate their data, a logistical and physical infrastructure to keep the samples scientifically valid from the donation to the lab, and the labs themselves. These requirements clearly lower the scalability potential in terms of the ability to replicate these experiments elsewhere, i.e. at the translational level.

Section 4 describes the findings to-date within each of the 5 EU Missions as well as some preliminary insights from the scalability assessment, i.e. the next phase of the work in this WP.

5 Conclusions, Limitations and Future Work

In the context of WP2 of the CROPS project, this deliverable reports the activities and findings to-date with respect to Task 2.1 (completed) and, partially, Task 2.2 (ongoing). Consistent with the proposal, this document focused on two main elements of this work.

First, we argued and presented both the foundational definitions and framework adopted in CROPS scalability assessment, and the overarching methodology designed. Section 2 clarified some critical questions guiding this study, establishing its boundaries and clearly defining what falls within the scope of CROPS review and assessment (and what does not). This is concluded with the adaptation of an existing upscaling framework to the CROPS project. In particular, the CROPS Upscaling Framework outlines nine factors that influence upscaling in CS. These factors are divided in three thematic clusters and are both theoretically grounded and empirically tested (Maccani et al., 2020). These are currently guiding the data extraction from existing CS projects and serve as the main input for the initial upscaling assessment that is currently ongoing.

Second, we presented the preliminary findings from the review. The diversity and wide variety of focuses within and across the 5 EU Missions, led to the need of adopting a tailored approach. Each Mission has been therefore tackled separately. These further clusters have been identified and presented. This work is consistent with the overall scope of this review: to identify CS projects that are suitable for upscaling impact to the 5 EU Mission. As argued in section 2, the focus is on upscaling impact. This clustering work is therefore an important stepping stone for the ongoing work.

5.1 Next Steps

The next phases of this research will involve three main activities.

Figure 39: Overview and Timeline of Tasks 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3

First, we will complete the scalability assessment for the 150 remaining projects (368 of the 518 have already been assessed at the time of writing this document). A first round of analysis will aim to reduce the number to approximately 100 projects, ideally around 20 per mission. At this point, exclusion criteria will be primarily based on consistency (or not) with open science principles, availability of information, and incidence of the issue(s) tackled. These aspects will be carefully discussed at the project level. Results from this process will be presented in M18 as part of Deliverable 2.2: Scalability Ranking Report Based on Potential.

Second, a more in-depth assessment will be undertaken with respect to those projects that will be selected as suitable for upscaling. According to the proposal, we aim at undertaking approximately 20 semi-structured interviews. These interviews will allow us to gather more granular qualitative data to serve multiple purposes. First, we will investigate whether other relevant factors exist that may enable or inhibit upscaling of respective projects that may be either not considered in the framework, or that have to be clarified based on insufficient publicly available information. Second, importantly, we will discuss the potential interest of the project leaders in actually upscaling their projects to a transnational level. We're doing this as it ensures that the selected projects are genuinely interested in scaling up and confident in their ability to meet participant needs and expectations while maintaining the quality of their scientific practices throughout the upscaling process. However, it is reminded that this is not a necessary condition for upscaling since others could adopt resources, methods, and technologies and replicate scalable projects in their own contexts (see reflections on adaptation and upscaling in section 2). However, helping project leaders, as long as they are interested, to upscale their projects remains an important focus of CROPS as a whole. Third, as part of Task 2.3 (entitled: Evaluation of Stakeholder Involvement, and Potential Involvement of Quadruple Helix Stakeholder Groups - M12-M20), these interviews will be leveraged to explore and understand what stakeholders are instrumental for the project implementation and explore how this translates beyond their original contexts, i.e. at the transnational level. Finally, the interviews will be helpful for other tasks in CROPS, i.e. to investigate in-depth the scientific validity of their contributions (Task 2.4), or their approach to open data (Task 4.1), or their funding experiences and/or plans (Task 4.3).

At this point, i.e. at M20, we aim at having as an output a list of between 5 and 10 projects (or clusters of projects) for each of the 5 EU Missions that are selected as suitable for upscaling. These will be enriched with all the information and knowledge acquired during the previous phases of this assessment and interviews, as well as from the findings from other tasks and WPs. These will inform specific aspects of the projects (e.g. scientific validity, data management, funding, etc.) and also provide infrastructures and resources for enabling the actual upscaling process.

These projects will be the input of the final phase of this review and assessment study: the validation workshops. One workshop per EU Mission will be organised, also with the support of the advisory board and, if possible, of the EU Joint Research Centre.

5.2 Limitations

Given the wide scope of this review and the task of undertaking a scalability assessment of over 500 diverse CS projects, we do acknowledge some limitations of our work. While most of these are particularly relevant for the actual upscaling assessment (presented in Deliverable 2.2 in M18), so far we argue that some limitations can be already outlined.

First, enabling factors included in the CROPS Upscaling Framework may not be exhaustive. The findings to date show that CS projects are rarely the discrete sum of elements, such as methodologies and given technologies. Rather, these are often socially constructed realities, based on actions and interactions among individuals and groups. These are typically settled in specific cultures and socio-political settings and situations. All these aspects appear to be equally important when implementing most CS projects and are, at the same time, hard to capture in more positivist frameworks like the CROPS Upscaling one. To address this potential limitation, a particular focus on extracting and learning from these rich experiences and information will be made available during the interviews to those projects that will be selected as suitable for upscaling.

Second, this first deliverable already shows the variety of projects even within the same EU Mission. This makes it more challenging the task of quantitatively ranking and comparing CS projects based on their scalability potential, considering that the focus is upscaling the impact of CS on the missions. This is one of the main reasons why dedicated validation workshops will be implemented with respect to each of the 5 EU Missions. Domain experts will help substantially in interpreting the CS project contributions to the Missions especially by providing an expert and overarching view (i.e. beyond CS) about the Missions themselves, their priorities, and the complementary contribution of CS towards their achievements. Also, consistent with the proposal, we underline once again that the scope of this work is to employ robust methods and techniques to identify projects that are suitable for upscaling. This may create the possibility of leaving other projects outside of the scope of CROPS with equal or greater potential. Once again, consulting with experts throughout the research minimises the probability of excluding relevant projects from the review and the assessment.

Third, the inclusion criteria for projects revolved around the definition of CS adopted in CROPS (see Sections 2.2 and 2.3). In the ongoing debate in both scientific and practitioners literature on what is (and what is not) CS, we have

adopted a wider definition, to ensure not to leave relevant projects and initiatives behind in the rapidly growing field of citizen science. The experience so far shows that only a subset of projects label themselves (or are labelled by others) as CS. Others are consistent with the definition adopted, but are often phrased differently, e.g. participatory project, citizen engagement, co-creation and co-design, citizen participation, among others. For some of these projects, the line between being within or outside the scope of the CROPS definition is very fine. In these cases, a solid criteria is nearly impossible to establish. To address this limitation, these projects are highlighted during the review and discussed internally during a dedicated WP2 monthly meeting with the overall consortium.

Fourth, we consider primarily projects whose information is provided in English, or where it could be automatically translated. This may imply not having considered local or small scale projects in other languages. The reviewers involved in this work could cover English, Spanish, and Italian.

Finally, as argued at the beginning of this document, both the terms CS and upscaling are used in different ways and forms and well-acknowledged definitions are currently lacking in the literature. Specifically, within the field of CS, there is no universally agreed definition of upscaling, which presents challenges in conceptualizing our approach for identifying and selecting projects suitable for upscaling. While we developed our own definition of upscaling in the context of CROPS building on the literature and the EU frameworks and definitions, as well as based on the text of the call for proposals under which the CROPS project has been funded, this lack of consensus in the field remains a noteworthy constraint.

6 References

Balestrini, M., Rogers, Y., Hassan, C., Creus, J., King, M., & Marshall, P. (2017). A City in Common: a Framework to Orchestrate Large-Scale Citizen Engagement around Urban Issues. In Proceedings of the 2017 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (pp.2282-2294), ACM.

Balestrini, M., Bird, J., Marshall, P., Zaro, A. and Rogers, Y., 2014, April. Understanding sustained community engagement: a case study in heritage preservation in rural Argentina. In Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (pp. 2675-2684). ACM.

Balka, K. 2011. Open Source Product Development. The Meaning and Relevance of Openness. Gabler, Wiesbaden.

Benkler, Y. 2006. The wealth of networks: How social production transforms markets and freedom: Yale Univ Press.

Bristol Citizen Sensing Programme, 2016. A Future in Common: Understanding and Framing Commoning Strategies for Bristol.

Cooper, C.B., Hawn, C.L., Larson, L.R., Parrish, J.K., Bowser, G., Cavalier, D., Dunn, R.R., Haklay, M. (Muki), Gupta, K.K., Jelks, N.O., Johnson, V.A., Katti, M., Leggett, Z., Wilson, O.R., Wilson, S., 2021. Inclusion in citizen science: The conundrum of rebranding. *Science* 372, 1386–1388. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abi6487>

Craglia M, Granell Canut C. Citizen Science and Smart Cities. EUR 26652. Luxembourg (Luxembourg): Publications Office of the European Union; 2014. JRC90374

de Sherbinin, A., Bowser, A., Chuang, T.R., Cooper, C., Danielsen, F., Edmunds, R., Elias, P., Faustman, E., Hultquist, C., Mondardini, R. and Popescu, I., 2021. The critical importance of citizen science data. *Frontiers in Climate*, 3, p.650760.

Earp, H.S. and Liconti, A., 2020. Science for the future: the use of citizen science in marine research and conservation. In *YOUMARES 9-The Oceans: Our Research, Our Future: Proceedings of the 2018 conference for YOUng MARine REsearcher in Oldenburg, Germany* (pp. 1-19). Springer International Publishing.

Fraisl, D., Campbell, J., See, L., Wehn, U., Wardlaw, J., Gold, M., Moorthy, I., Arias, R., Piera, J., Oliver, J.L. and Masó, J., 2020. Mapping citizen science contributions to the UN sustainable development goals. *Sustainability Science*, 15, pp.1735-1751.

Fraisl, D., Hager, G., Bedessem, B., Gold, M., Hsing, P.Y., Danielsen, F., Hitchcock, C.B., Hulbert, J.M., Piera, J., Spiers, H. and Thiel, M., 2022. Citizen science in environmental and ecological sciences. *Nature Reviews Methods Primers*, 2(1), p.64.

Fraisl, D., See, L., Bowers, R., Seidu, O., Fredua, K.B., Bowser, A., Meloche, M., Weller, S., Amaglo-Kobla, T., Ghafari, D. and Bayas, J.C.L., 2023. The contributions of citizen science to SDG monitoring and reporting on marine plastics. *Sustainability Science*, 18(6), pp.2629-2647.

Fraisl, D., See, L., Estevez, D., Tomaska, N. and MacFeely, S., 2023. Citizen science for monitoring the health and well-being related Sustainable Development Goals and the World Health Organization's Triple Billion Targets. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11, p.1202188.

Haklay, M. (2013). Citizen Science and Volunteered Geographic Information: Overview and Typology of Participation. In: Sui D., Elwood S., Goodchild M. (eds) *Crowdsourcing Geographic Knowledge*. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-4587-2_7

Haklay, M. (2015). *Citizen science and policy: A European perspective*. Washington, DC: Woodrow Wilson International Center for Scholars.

Haklay, M., Fraisl, D., Greshake Tzovaras, B., Hecker, S., Gold, M., Hager, G., Ceccaroni, L., Kieslinger, B., Wehn, U., Woods, S. and Nold, C., 2021. Contours of citizen science: a vignette study. *Royal Society open science*, 8(8), p.202108.

Haklay, M., Dörler, D., Heigl, F., Manzoni, M., Hecker, S., Vohland, K., Vohland, K., Land-Zandstra, A., Ceccaroni, L., Lemmens, R. and Perelló, J., 2021. What is citizen science? The challenges of definition. *The science of citizen science*, 13.

Hecker, S., Bonney, R., Haklay, M., Hölker, F., Hofer, H., Goebel, C., Gold, M., Makuch, Z., Ponti, M., Richter, A., Robinson, L., Iglesias, J.R., Owen, R., Peltola, T., Sforzi, A., Shirk, J., Vogel, J., Vohland, K., Witt, T. and Bonn, A., (2018). Innovation in Citizen Science – Perspectives on Science-Policy Advances. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 3(1).

Kirschke, S., Bennett, C., Ghazani, A.B., Kirschke, D., Lee, Y., Loghmani Khouzani, S.T. and Nath, S., 2023. Design impacts of citizen science. A comparative analysis of water monitoring projects. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 11, p.1186238.

Le Dantec, C.A. and DiSalvo, C., 2013. Infrastructuring and the formation of publics in participatory design. *Social Studies of Science*, 43(2): 241-264.

Lessig, L. 2004. *Free culture: How big media uses technology and the law to lock down culture and control creativity*. Penguin.

Maccani G., Goossensen M., Righi V., Creus J. and Balestrini M., *Scaling up Citizen Science - What are the factors associated with increased reach and how to lever them to achieve impact*, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2020, ISBN 978-92-76-25157-6, doi:10.2760/00926, JRC122219.

Marttila, S. and Botero, A., 2013. The 'Openness Turn' in Co-design. From Usability, Sociability and Designability Towards Openness. In Smeds & Irrmann (eds.). *CO-CREATE 2013 - The Boundary-Crossing Conference on Co-Design in Innovation*, 99-110. June 16-19, 2013, Espoo, Finland.

Okoli, C., 2015. A guide to conducting a standalone systematic literature review. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 37.

Pino, V., McBratney, A., O'Brien, E., Singh, K. and Pozza, L., 2022. Citizen science & soil connectivity: Where are we?. *Soil Security*, 9, p.100073.

Radicchi, A. (2022). *Scaling up citizen science, Mutual Learning Exercise on Citizen Science Initiatives - Policy and Practice Topic Five Discussion Paper: Scaling up citizen science*, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2022 Available at: https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/rio/report/disc_paper_topic_5_final.pdf

Radicchi, A., Leo, G., Haklay, M., Irwin, A., Mazzonetto, M., Heigl, F., Dörle, D. (2023) *Mutual Learning Exercise on Citizen Science Initiatives: Policy and Practice Fifth Thematic Report – Scaling up citizen science*, ISBN 978-92-76-61952-9 doi: 10.2777/527361, available at: <https://apre.it/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/mutual-learning-exercise-on-citizen-science-initiatives-KIAX23003ENN.pdf>

Rogers, E.M., 2010. *Diffusion of innovations*. Simon and Schuster.

Shirk, J.L., Ballard, H.L., Wilderman, C.C., Phillips, T., Wiggins, A., Jordan, R., McCallie, E., Minarchek, M., Lewenstein, B.V., Krasny, M.E. and Bonney, R., 2012. Public participation in scientific research: a framework for deliberate design. *Ecology and society*, 17(2).

Sprinks, J., Woods, S.M., Parkinson, S., Wehn, U., Joyce, H., Ceccaroni, L. and Gharesifard, M., 2021. Coordinator perceptions when assessing the impact of citizen science towards sustainable development goals. *Sustainability*, 13(4), p.2377.

Teli, M., Bordin, S., Blanco, M. M., Orabona, G., and De Angeli, A., 2015. Public design of digital commons in urban places: a case study. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 81, 17-30.

Venkatesh, V., Morris, M.G., Davis, G.B. and Davis, F.D., 2003. User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view. *MIS quarterly*, pp.425-478.

Vohland, K., Land-Zandstra, A., Ceccaroni, L., Lemmens, R., Perelló, J., Ponti, M., Samson, R. and Wagenknecht, K., 2021. *The science of citizen science* (p. 529). Springer Nature.

Appendix 1 “A Soil Deal for Europe” Mission’s projects

Nº	Name of the project	URL	Project focus	EU Mission	Other EU Missions tackled
1	Vigilantes del suelo	https://vigilantesdelsuelo.es/	The "Vigilantes del Suelo" project engages citizens in monitoring soil health through education and data collection. It aims to enhance awareness and sustainable soil management practices across communities in Spain.	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change
2	Elementary GLOBE Soil Module	https://www.globe.gov/web/elementary-globe/overview/soils	The Elementary GLOBE "Soils" project introduces young students to soil science through interactive educational resources. It teaches soil's role in ecosystems, fostering environmental awareness and scientific curiosity.	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change
3	Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP)	https://www.citizenscience.gov/smap-globe-soil-moisture/#	Complement spacecraft soil moisture measures with CS based soil moisture monitoring.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
4	Soils for Science	https://imb.uq.edu.au/soilsforscience	Finding new antibiotics needed to fight against the scourge of drug-resistant bacteria known as superbugs.	A Soil Deal for Europe	Climate Neutral Smart Cities

5	acid-soils-testing-blitz	https://gwlap.org.au/project/acid-soils-testing-blitz/	Blitz! Landowners engaged ones for a measurement campaign. Address soil acidity in South Australia State soils with landowner that avail of a kit for measuring and learning.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
6	DustAnalysis (Garden and Veg Safe)	https://www.360dustanalysis.com/	The 360 Dust Analysis project engages citizens in analysing household dust to identify environmental contaminants and allergens. It aims to enhance awareness of indoor air quality and environmental health.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
7	Summer Solstice	https://www.ceh.ac.uk/news-and-media/blogs/	This project monitors the resistance of fungicidal drugs. Volunteers are asked to send soil samples from their gardens on the Summer Solstice (June 21) to the Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (CEH) and Imperial College.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
8	UKSO MySoil App	https://www.ukso.org/static-maps/mysoil.html	The UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (UKCEH) blog showcases insights on environmental research, citizen science, and sustainability projects, fostering understanding of ecosystems, climate challenges, and innovative ecological solutions.	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change
9	What's in Your Backyard/The CS Soil Collection Program	https://shareok.org/handle/11244/28096	This initiative searches for new soil fungi across the USA which might produce drug-like compounds or natural products. The project brings together biomedical researchers with citizen scientists.	A Soil Deal for Europe	Cancer
10	Programas de Conservación - Suelos	https://www.vitoria-gasteiz.org/wb021/was/contenidoAccion.do?idioma=es&uid=2498e010_162d6fd8d27_7e82	A soil conservation program that aims to assess the soil status in croplands together with citizens. It makes use of the so-called "TSEA" (Agricultural Ecosystem Health Cards) and soil kits. Specialists distribute these cards and kits to collect data about soil health according to	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

			agricultural practices.		
11	1000 Gardens	https://vib.be/en/research-and-impact/grand-challenges/societal-impact/citizen-science	Engaged more than thousand citizens in a 6-month gardening project aiming at facilitating sustainable soybean cultivation in Belgium.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
12	INCREASE	https://www.pulsesincrease.eu/experiment	Citizens to voluntarily contribute to and test an innovative decentralised approach to seed conservation, multiplication and sharing in order to conserve agro-biodiversity.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
13	QUBS	https://anrbises.cefe.cnrs.fr/en/citizen-science/	Citizen science program accessible to all to assess the diversity and abundance of invertebrates indicating soil quality.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
14	In My Backyard	https://actionproject.eu/citizen-science-pilots/in-my-backyard/	Map the use of pesticides and fertilizers in the context of home farming and gardening. Simultaneously, it aimed to disseminate information on the topic with the final aim of reducing the use of pesticides and fertilizers.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
15	SoilSkin La Piel Viva del Suelo	https://ebryo.com/soilskin/	Collect data for science on biological soil covers in Spain.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
16	Proyectos Nuestros Suelos	https://suelosustentable.cl/noticias/nuestros-suelos-usando-ciencia-ciudadana-para-conocer-y-evaluar-suelos-degradados-en-chile/	Aims to develop a methodology to qualitatively assess soil degradation via citizens. The project is primarily collecting data about fertility and heavy metals. It distributes low-cost kits for measuring CaCO ₃ , MO, pH, As, Cu, and textural class.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

17	The Citizen Science Soil Health Project	https://soilhealthproject.org/index.html	<p>10 year long project to help Colorado Front Range growers prove they are improving their soil.</p> <p>We offer each participating grower one FREE soil health test, every year for the 10 years of the project. Growers can also buy extra tests whenever they want. Growers gather their own soil samples. We send the samples in to the lab, track the results, and pass the results on to our growers.</p>	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
18	Romania Geomagnetic App	https://noapteacercetatorilor.ro/nc/participa-la-harta-magnetica/experiment/	<p>Generate magnetic maps and identify and study geomagnetic anomalies as well as low and high values.</p>	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
19	The Tea Bag Experiment	https://forskarfredag.se/massexperiment/tepaseforsoket-2015/	<p>Study decomposition of plant materials in soil. Here, participants bury tea bags for a certain amount of time, and then dig up and weigh the tea bags to see how much plant material has decomposed during this time.</p>	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change
20	Grow Observatory	https://growobservatory.org/	<p>Supports a movement of citizens generating, sharing and using information on growing and the land.</p>	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change
21	Seed Library	https://www.gkfb.si/za-uporabnike/knjiznica-semen	<p>The Seed Library seed collection is open to all residents (over 15 years of age) in the local communities where the libraries are located. An individual donates home-grown seeds to the collection, which are described with predefined metadata.</p>	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change
22	Living underground	https://zivo.podzemlje.si/	<p>The main aim of the Living Underground campaign is to raise public awareness of the importance of accessible data on subterranean animals for nature conservation.</p>	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change

23	Earthworm Watch	https://www.earthwormwatch.org/	To assess how the abundance and diversity of earthworms respond to different land uses and land management as well as to other environmental conditions and how three ecosystem benefits provided by earthworms – soil carbon storage, soil productivity and flood protection – vary across the UK.	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change
24	One Million Voices of Agroecology	https://onemillionvoices.agroecologymap.org/	The aim of the project is to develop a tool that enable farmers, producer organisations, consumers and other potential end users around the world to inclusively participate in agroecology movements, support sustainable adoption of agroecology, and contribute to the collection, co-creation and sharing of information to fill key knowledge gaps on the performance of agroecology.	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change
25	PataFest	https://www.patafest.eu/	The project focuses on sustainable Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies to treat and control the presence of <i>Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum</i> (CLso) pest and its vector in plants, and address the incidence of soil-borne pathogens during potato postharvest storage.	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change
26	Soil Health Guards	https://cuvarizemljista.com/	2-years program for monitoring physical, chemical and biological indicators of soil health in Serbia.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
27	SoilCare	https://www.soilcare-project.eu/	identify and promote soil-improving cropping systems and agronomic practices that boost soil health, biodiversity, and crop yields. It involves farmers and local communities in implementing and monitoring these systems in different European regions.	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change

28	AgriAdapt	https://agriadapt.eu/	engages farmers in testing and implementing climate-resilient agricultural practices that protect soil health. The project focuses on adapting farming systems to climate change while improving soil quality and productivity.	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change
29	SOILution	https://www.soilutions-project.eu/	tackle soil degradation. The focus lies in optimising four different bio waste valorisation routes to develop advanced soil improvers.	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change
30	Soil4Life	https://soil4life.eu/	The Soil4Life project promotes sustainable soil management to combat degradation and enhance soil health. It involves citizen engagement, policy advocacy, and education to protect soils across Europe.	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change
31	RE CARE	https://www.envista.it/archive/recare-hub.eu/	Develop effective prevention, remediation and restoration measures using an innovative transdisciplinary approach, actively integrating and advancing knowledge of stakeholders and scientists in 17 Case Studies, covering a range of soil threats in different biophysical and socio-economic environments across Europe.	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change
32	SoilWatch	https://soilwatch.eu/	Ecosystem restoration and food system transformation with transparent and science-based evidence throughout the project cycle.	A Soil Deal for Europe	
33	UK Soil Observatory	https://www.ukso.org/	The UK Soil Observatory (UKSO) provides accessible soil data and tools, supporting research, education, and sustainable land management. It fosters collaboration to address soil health and environmental challenges.	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change

34	SoilRise	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/soilrise-en	The SOIL-RISE project involves citizens in soil analysis to understand land use impacts and promote sustainable soil management. It aims to enhance awareness of soil health and ecosystem services.	A Soil Deal for Europe	Adaptation to Climate Change
35	City-Zen Boden	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/city-zen-boden-en	The CITY-ZEN Boden project engages citizens in soil research to assess soil quality in urban areas, promoting sustainable practices and raising awareness about soil's vital role in urban ecosystems.	A Soil Deal for Europe	Climate Neutral Smart Cities
36	SoilPlastic	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/soilplastic-947	The SoilPlastic project explores the impact of microplastics on soil health and biodiversity. It engages citizens in collecting data to better understand plastic pollution's effects on terrestrial ecosystems.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
37	Echosoil	https://echosoil.eu/es/	ECHO is a Horizon Europe project that engages citizens in soil knowledge and data collection, promoting sustainable land management. It includes ECHOREPO, an open-access repository linking citizen science data to the European Soil Observatory, supporting informed soil conservation decisions.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
38	Solenville	https://solenville.fr/	SOLenVILLE is a citizen science project based in Strasbourg that focuses on urban soil biodiversity. It aims to enhance knowledge of soil life, including macrofauna and microorganisms, through participatory research. The initiative fosters public engagement with environmental issues, helping to promote soil conservation and ecological sustainability in cities.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

39	Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité (OAB)	https://www.observatoire-agricole-biodiversite.fr/	The Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité (OAB) is a platform that promotes biodiversity monitoring on agricultural lands. It encourages farmers to participate in five observation protocols, covering species such as bees, butterflies, and bats, to assess ecosystem health and support sustainable farming practices.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
40	LeguCon	https://legucon.pt/	LeguCon is a consortium focused on increasing legume production in Portugal for sustainable consumption. The project promotes participatory agriculture by engaging farmers in the cultivation of legumes, offering practical training and technical support to improve soil health, reduce carbon footprints, and foster sustainable farming practices.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
41	Ephytia	https://ephytia.inra.fr/fr/P/165/jardibiodiv	Ephytia is a participatory observatory that engages citizens in monitoring soil biodiversity, focusing on soil invertebrates. It offers tools for data collection, species identification, and gardening tips to promote soil health, contributing to scientific research on urban ecosystems and biodiversity conservation.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
42	Bodemdierendagen	https://bodemdierendagen.nl/	Bodemdierendagen is a citizen science initiative in the Netherlands that invites people to explore and report on soil-dwelling creatures. Participants observe and document soil biodiversity, promoting awareness of its importance for healthy ecosystems and sustainable agriculture.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

43	500 ENI monitoring program	https://ecophytopic.fr/pic/exposition-et-imacts/reseau-500-eni-biovigilance	The Réseau 500 ENI Biovigilance network monitors the environmental impacts of plant protection products, focusing on the health of ecosystems. It tracks biodiversity and evaluates the effects of pesticides through citizen science and scientific collaboration.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
44	AGROMix	https://agromixproject.eu/	AGROMIX is a European project focused on transforming agricultural landscapes through agroecological practices like agroforestry. It involves farmers, researchers, and policymakers in co-designing resilient systems, creating tools, and offering immersive learning experiences for sustainable land use across Europe.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
45	Beweisstück Unterhose/ Proof by Underpants	https://www.beweisstueck-unterhose.ch/	"Beweisstück Unterhose" is a citizen science project where participants bury cotton underwear to assess soil health. The project highlights biodiversity and soil activity, with degradation of the fabric indicating healthier soil ecosystems. Participants engage via an app to track results, promoting awareness of soil conservation.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
46	Curieuzeneuzen	https://curieuzeneuzen.be/	Curieuzeneuzen is a large-scale citizen science initiative in Belgium that collects data on environmental issues such as air quality, heat, and drought. Thousands of citizens contribute measurements, enabling detailed scientific insights into climate change and urban planning. The project promotes awareness of environmental challenges.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

47	QUBS Participatory monitoring of soil biological quality	https://www.mnhn.fr/en/soil-biological-quality-observatory-qubs-observe-the-biodiversity-of-the-soil	The Soil Biological Quality Observatory (QUBS) is a citizen science project that invites participants to observe and report on the biodiversity within the soil. By doing so, contributors help researchers better understand soil ecosystems and their health, as these environments are vital but often overlooked in biodiversity studies	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
48	TeaBag Index	http://www.teatime4science.org/about/the-project/	Teatime4Science is a global citizen science project that uses tea bags to measure soil decomposition rates. Participants bury tea bags and track their degradation, providing data to study the effects of climate change on soil health and carbon cycling.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
49	Open Soil Atlas	https://www.mitforschen.org/sites/default/files/assets/projekte/user-4879/pdf/OSA%20Final%20Paper%20(Englisch).pdf	The Open Soil Atlas project aims to generate a biodiverse, self-sustaining and organically growing Soil Data Atlas, enriched by citizens working together to balance and heal the Earth.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
50	Soil Care	https://www.soilcare-project.eu/	SoilCare aimed to identify and evaluate soil-improving cropping systems across Europe, enhancing agricultural sustainability and profitability. It provided research-based solutions for farmers, policy-makers, and researchers, promoting eco-friendly practices for long-term soil health and productivity.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
51	People4Soil	https://citizens-initiative.europa.eu/initiatives/details/2016/000002_en	People4Soil was an international campaign, supported by European NGOs, research institutes, farmers associations and environmental groups, lobbying for the protection of soil at legislative level within the European Union.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

52	Worm Watch Lab	https://www.wormwatchlab.org/	Worm Watch Lab was a citizen science project where volunteers observed nematode worms to identify egg-laying behavior. The research aimed to understand how genes influence behavior, with insights applicable to human genetics.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
53	Solsvivants	https://www.solsvivants.org/en/	Sols Vivants promotes soil regeneration by partnering with farmers and local actors to improve soil fertility. The initiative focuses on enhancing biodiversity, carbon sequestration, and crop productivity, contributing to sustainable agriculture and climate regulation.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
54	SOLO	https://soils4europe.eu/	SOLO aims to bridge knowledge gaps in soil health by creating a strategic research and innovation roadmap for the European Soil Mission. It establishes a knowledge hub, promotes strategic partnerships, and involves stakeholders in a transparent process.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
55	SOIL association	https://www.soilassociation.org/	The Soil Association promotes organic farming, sustainable food systems, and soil health. It advocates for policies supporting biodiversity, climate action, and health, while offering certification for organic businesses and supporting regenerative practices across agriculture.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
56	iSQAPER-is	https://www.isqaper-is.eu/	The iSQAPER project provides a mobile app (SQAPP) for assessing soil quality, offering data on sustainable land management practices. It aims to support farmers, policymakers, and researchers in improving agricultural productivity and environmental resilience.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

57	SoliGrids	https://www.isric.org/exploration/soilgrids/ // https://soilgrids.org/	<p>SoilGrids is a global digital mapping system that uses machine learning to predict soil properties, providing maps for pH, carbon content, texture, and other key factors at high spatial resolution. These maps support sustainable land management practices worldwide.</p>	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
58	WOCAT	https://wocat.net/en/about-wocat/	<p>WOCAT is a global network focused on documenting, sharing, and promoting sustainable land management (SLM) practices. It provides tools, knowledge, and training to support adaptation, innovation, and decision-making for land-based solutions to combat land degradation and climate change.</p>	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
59	SoilSCAN	https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/ac8300/pdf // https://www.plymouth.ac.uk/research/centre-for-research-in-environment-and-society-ceres/soilscan	<p>The SoilSCAN citizen science programme aimed to test the potential for using handheld AgroCares soil scanners as a tool for mapping whole community soil characteristics at a resolution beyond that achievable in conventional research, with the ultimate objective to deliver research that empowers stakeholders to create sustainable community landscape plans.</p>	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
60	Bridges	https://www.piroggetto-bridges.it/	<p>The BRIDGES project focuses on transdisciplinary research to address ecological challenges, particularly soil fertility. It engages researchers, artists, and citizens in collaborative efforts, including creating biological probes and analysing soil through metagenomic sampling. The project fosters public participation and awareness through workshops and community-driven data collection.</p>	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

61	Garden Roots	https://citizensciencepartnerships.com/community-agency/garden-roots/	The Garden Roots project engages community members in citizen science, focusing on arsenic contamination in homegrown vegetables near a Superfund site in Arizona. Participants collect samples to assess health risks and promote safe gardening practices.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
62	HeavyMetal Citizen	https://cityzenboden.com/	City-Zen Boden is a research platform focused on soil health in Vienna, collaborating with community gardens to explore sustainable practices. It raises awareness about soil science and invites citizens to engage in experiments on urban soil quality.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
63	CiDéSol	https://www.cocreate.brussels/projet/cidesol/	The CiDéSol project focuses on the remediation of polluted soils in Brussels. It engages citizens in co-creating solutions for soil decontamination through phytoremediation and mycoremediation, promoting sustainable and community-driven environmental practices.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
64	Using citizen science to develop solutions for healthy soils through phytomining	https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/research-area/industrial-research-and-innovation/eu-valorisation-policy/knowledge-valorisation-platform/repository/using-citizen-science-develop-solutions-healthy-soils-through-phytomining	The project uses citizen science to identify soil contaminants and develop solutions for soil regeneration through phytomining. It led to the creation of Phyona Ltd, a spin-off focused on soil decontamination and nanoparticle supply.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

65	Showcase	https://showcase-project.eu/about	The SHOWCASE project integrates biodiversity into farming practices, focusing on synergies between agriculture and ecosystems. It develops tools, incentivises farmers, and builds a network of biodiversity areas to support sustainable farming and wildlife protection.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
66	Collectifs	https://collectifs-biodiversite.universite-lyon.fr/	The COLLECTIFS project promotes urban biodiversity by involving citizens in scientific studies of green spaces in collective housing. It combines ecological research with participatory actions to enhance local biodiversity and improve residents' quality of life.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
67	FARM NET ZERO and Farm Carbon Toolkit	https://farmcarbontoolkit.org.uk/farm-net-zero/monitor-farms/	The "Farm Net Zero" initiative helps farms monitor and reduce carbon emissions by integrating sustainability practices, supporting farmers in achieving net-zero carbon footprints. It focuses on improving resource efficiency and reducing environmental impact.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
68	TeaComposition	https://teacomposition.sydneyn.edu.au/	The TeaComposition project engages schools in New South Wales to study soil health using tea bags. It aims to analyse soil decomposition rates, contributing to soil science research and raising awareness about soil health.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
69	Citizen Science project on soil health and soil awareness as part of the Science Year 2020 Bioeconomy	https://forschung-sachsen-anhalt.de/projekt/citizen-science-projekt-bodengesundheit-23954	This Citizen Science project, part of Germany's 2020 Bioeconomy Science Year, engages the public in gathering data on soil health through simple field experiments. The collected data supports research on soil functions and contributes to international projects like Tea4Science.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

70	TeaComposition Initiative	https://www.teacomposition.org/	The TeaComposition project involves citizens in monitoring soil health by observing tea bag decomposition. It provides valuable data for studying carbon cycling, soil biology, and environmental conditions, with a focus on global collaboration.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
71	Bodemleven	https://bodemleven.be/	Bodemleven is a citizen science project engaging 1,000 gardeners in Limburg, Belgium, to monitor soil health. Using tea bags and IoT technology, it collects data to better understand soil biodiversity and its importance.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
72	Expedition Erdreich	https://expedition-erdreich.bonares.de/	The "Expedition Erdreich" project, part of Germany's Bioeconomy Year 2020/21, engaged participants nationwide in exploring soil health using scientific methods. It gathered valuable data on soil ecosystems and supported soil-related research efforts.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
73	TeaTime4App	https://www.teatime4school.at/teatime4app	TeaTime4App allows citizen scientists, especially students, to observe soil health by analysing tea bag decomposition. The app tracks soil carbon dynamics, connecting citizens with global environmental goals and enhancing education on soil science.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
74	Soil Your Undies Challenge - University of New England	https://www.unediscoveryvoyager.org.au/soilyourundies/	The "Soil Your Undies" initiative encourages individuals to bury a pair of cotton underwear to measure soil health and promote awareness of sustainability. It helps monitor soil quality by observing decomposition rates.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

75	Plante ton slip	https://librairie.ademe.fr/sols-pollues/653-plante-ton-slip.html	"Plante ton slip" is a citizen science initiative promoting soil health by encouraging participants to bury cotton underwear in the soil to observe natural degradation. This method reveals microbial life activity and soil condition.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
76	Alsóban az élet	https://www.elkh-taki.hu/hu/taxonomy/term/139 // https://meetin.gorganizer.com/pernicus.org/EGU22/EGU22-5094.html	The "Life in Undies" project is a Hungarian citizen science initiative assessing soil health by burying cotton underwear. Participants track decomposition rates, providing valuable data on soil biology and activity across various land types.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
77	360 Dust Analysis	https://www.360dustanalysis.com/gardensafe	GardenSafe is a citizen science initiative in Victoria, Australia, that helps residents assess soil quality. Participants send soil samples for analysis, identifying contaminants and offering guidance to reduce pollution and enhance garden safety.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
78	Indiana Collaboration for Lead Action and Prevention	https://www.mapmyenvironment.com/iclap/	The ICLAP initiative empowers communities to map soil and dust lead levels through citizen science. Participants contribute environmental samples for analysis, promoting awareness and solutions to address lead contamination and improve public health.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
79	SoilSafe Aotearoa	https://soilsafe.auckland.ac.nz/	Soilsafe Aotearoa is a citizen science project by the University of Auckland helping communities assess soil health. Offering free soil testing, it educates participants on soil composition, contamination risks, and sustainable gardening practices.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

80	Latrobe Valley Dust Research	https://www.epa.vic.gov.au/for-community/get-involved/citizen-science-program/citizen-science-projects/latrobe-valley-dust-research	The Latrobe Valley Dust Research project engages the community in monitoring dust levels to assess air quality. Citizens collect data to help identify sources and reduce environmental health risks in the region.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
81	Observatoire de la Qualité Biologique des Sols (QUBS)	https://www.qubs.fr/	QUBS (Qualité Biologique des Sols) is a citizen science program exploring soil biodiversity. Participants observe organisms like earthworms and snails, contributing data to enhance understanding and promote healthy soil ecosystems.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
82	Bodemdierendagen	https://bodemdierendagen.nl/	The Bodemdierendagen project invites citizens in the Netherlands to observe and document soil animals in their gardens. It raises awareness about soil biodiversity and its role in ecosystem health.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
83	MINAGRIS	https://www.minagris.eu/	MINAGRIS examines the impact of plastic debris on agricultural soil health, biodiversity, and ecosystem services. It develops sustainable strategies for plastic use in farming to promote safe, resilient, and economically viable food systems in Europe.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
84	Expedition Boden	https://expedition-boden.eah-jena.de/	The Expedition Boden project engages citizens in soil exploration to raise awareness about soil biodiversity and health. Participants collect data to contribute to sustainable soil management.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
85	CALeDNA	https://ucedna.com/	The CALeDNA project uses environmental DNA (eDNA) to assess and monitor California's biodiversity. Volunteers and researchers collaborate to collect soil, sediment, and water samples, analysing species diversity to	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

			support conservation efforts.		
86	OPAL Soil & Earthworm Survey (UK)	https://www.imperial.ac.uk/opal/surveys/soilsurvey/	The OPAL Soil and Earthworm Survey engages citizen scientists in exploring soil properties and earthworm diversity to understand soil health and its ecological significance. Activities include sampling, soil testing, and species identification.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
87	CurieuzeNeuzen in de tuin (CNIDT)	https://www.uantwerpen.be/nl/projecten/global-change-ecology/burgerwetenschap/cnidt/tuinrapport/	The "CurieuzeNeuzen in de Tuin" project investigates how gardens and green spaces can combat climate challenges like heat and drought. It involves citizen science to gather data and inform sustainable strategies.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
88	Soil Sampling Toolkit by Citizen Science Community Resources	https://www.cresources.org/projects	Citizen Science Community Resources (CSCR) empowers local communities by engaging them in environmental projects like soil testing, community gardening, and youth education. These initiatives aim to improve environmental health and foster active citizenship.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
89	Programa de Conservación de Suelos	https://www.vitoria-gasteiz.org/wb021/was/contenidoAction.do?lang=en&locale=en&idioma=en&uid=u_2498e010_162d6fd8d27_7e82	The Vitoria-Gasteiz Soil Conservation Program involves citizen scientists monitoring soil health using simplified "Ecosystem Health Cards" to promote sustainable farming, protect biodiversity, and combat climate change, encouraging public participation.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
90	MO DIRT (Missourians Doing Impact Research Together)	https://modirt.danforthcenter.org/soilhealthsurveys	MO DIRT invites citizens to conduct soil health surveys across Missouri. Participants gather data on soil conditions, contributing to climate research, land management, and educational purposes, promoting community involvement in scientific discovery.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

91	MicroBlitz	https://scistarter.org/microblitz	<p>MicroBlitz is a citizen science initiative across Western Australia, focusing on mapping microbial DNA in soil to assess environmental health.</p> <p>Volunteers collect samples, contributing to vital research on biodiversity and ecosystem monitoring.</p>	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
92	Knoxville-Tennessee Environmental Soil and Stream Testing (K-TE SST)	https://sites.google.com/vols.utk.edu/k-tesst/home	<p>The K-TE SST (Tennessee Environmental Sampling and Survey Tool) project engages volunteers in collecting environmental data, focusing on water and soil samples.</p> <p>The initiative aims to enhance community-based environmental monitoring and education.</p>	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
93	Gärtnern für den Umweltschutz	https://www.h-brs.de/de/izne/gaertnern-umweltschutz	<p>The "Gärtnern für den Umweltschutz" (Gardening for Environmental Protection) initiative by Hochschule Bonn-Rhein-Sieg offers DIY workshops and experiments focused on soil health, climate protection, and biodiversity.</p> <p>Participants learn how to improve soil fertility, manage water, and enhance biodiversity, with practical activities for urban gardeners.</p>	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
94	Citizens of the Crust: a biocrust assessment project (Desiccation & Diversity in Dryland Mosses)	https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/citizens-of-the-crust-a-biocrust-assessment-project	<p>The "Citizens of the Crust" project invites participants to help assess and monitor biocrusts—critical components of ecosystems. Volunteers collect and document data to track these organisms' biodiversity and health.</p>	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
95	NOCMOC	https://www.nocmoc.eu/#predstavitev	<p>The "Noč ima svojo moč" project aims to engage the public, especially young people, with science by organising events during the European Researchers' Night. It promotes research through interactive workshops, experiments, and educational activities.</p>	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

96	Grower CS Project	https://grower-citizenscience.wordpress.com/	The Grower Citizen Science project supports agricultural communities by engaging growers in collecting data on soil health to improve water retention and resilience against climate extremes. It connects researchers with farmers for better climate adaptation strategies.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
97	Land-Potential Knowledge System (LandPKS)	https://landpotential.org/	LandPKS offers a mobile app that helps landowners assess and monitor land potential, soil health, and vegetation. It aids in sustainable land management, tracking changes, and supporting data-driven decision-making across various environments.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
98	HoliSoils	https://holisoils.eu/	HoliSoils is a European project focused on enhancing forest soil management through holistic practices, modeling, and monitoring. It aims to mitigate climate change, support sustainability, and protect biodiversity in forest ecosystems.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
99	LUCAS Soil	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/lucas/overview	LUCAS (Land Use/Cover Area Frame Survey) is a European in-situ survey providing detailed data on land use, land cover, and environmental parameters, helping to monitor and manage EU land resources.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
100	SOIL Bon	https://soilbonfoodweb.org/	The Soil BON Foodweb initiative, launched in 2021, focuses on assessing soil animal biodiversity and interactions in soil food webs globally. It fosters collaboration among soil zoologists to monitor and conserve soil biodiversity.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

101	Best4Soil Project	https://www.best4soil.eu/	Best4Soil is a European project focused on improving soil health through innovative practices and research. It promotes sustainable land management, soil restoration, and biodiversity conservation to ensure future soil productivity and environmental resilience.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
102	EdiCitNet (Edible Cities Network Integrating Edible City Solutions for social resilient and sustainably productive cities)	https://www.edicitnet.com/essbare-schule-hellersdorf/	The "Essbare Schule Hellersdorf" project integrates sustainable and healthy eating education into the school curriculum. It includes hands-on activities like gardening, cooking, and bee-keeping, aiming to foster community engagement in food education.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
103	UK-SCAPE programme (SOC-D project)	https://uk-scape.ceh.ac.uk/	UK-SCAPE is a UK-wide environmental monitoring program focused on integrating data across biodiversity, air, soil, and water. It helps understand environmental changes, supports landscape interventions, and provides open access to data for research and policymaking.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
104	LIFE mySoil	https://lifemysoil.eu/es/sobre/	The "LifeMySoil" project aims to engage citizens in understanding soil health through citizen science. It focuses on soil biodiversity, health monitoring, and improving sustainable land management across Europe.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
105	Benchmarks	https://soilhealthbenchmarks.eu/about-us/	The Soil Health Benchmarks project develops and promotes tools for assessing soil health across Europe, offering benchmarks to guide sustainable farming practices and improve soil management for better agricultural productivity.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

106	HuMUS	https://humus-project.eu/about-humus/	The HUMUS project promotes soil health through innovative methods, focusing on understanding soil management practices, monitoring biodiversity, and supporting sustainable agriculture. It aims to enhance soil quality and ecosystem services across Europe.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
107	LOESS	https://loess-project.eu/	The LOESS project focuses on studying loess soils, exploring their characteristics, preservation, and role in global environmental change. It promotes sustainable land management and ecosystem restoration across Europe.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
108	NBSOIL	https://nbsoil.eu/	The NBSOIL project focuses on advancing natural-based solutions (NBS) for improving soil health and sustainability. It aims to integrate NBS into soil management practices, supporting environmental and agricultural resilience.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
109	ORCaSa - Impact4Soil	https://irc-orc-asa.eu/about/	The IRC-ORCASA project focuses on improving soil quality, ecosystem services, and sustainable agriculture. It emphasises collaboration, research, and innovation in soil management to address environmental and agricultural challenges.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
110	AI 4 Soil Health	https://ai4soilhealth.eu/	The AI4SoilHealth project leverages artificial intelligence to improve soil health monitoring and management. It integrates advanced technologies for better soil data analysis, promoting sustainable farming practices and improving soil ecosystem services.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No

111	Prepsoil	https://prepsoil.eu/	PREPSOIL focuses on developing effective strategies for soil protection, enhancing sustainability in agricultural practices. It integrates research and innovations to optimize soil management and improve resilience to environmental challenges.	A Soil Deal for Europe	No
-----	----------	---	---	------------------------	----

Appendix 2. “Adaptation to Climate Change” Mission’s projects

N°	Name of the project	URL	Project focus	EU Mission	Other EU Missions tackled
1	Fotoquest Go	https://fotoquest-go.org/en/	Collect evidence of how quickly the landscape is changing, providing scientists with a crucial source of data.	Adaptation to Climate Change	A Soil Deal for Europe
2	iNaturalist	https://www.inaturalist.org/	Online social network of naturalists, citizen scientists, and biologists based on the concept of mapping and sharing biodiversity observations across the world.	Adaptation to Climate Change	A Soil Deal for Europe
3	iChange	https://ichange-project.eu/	Empower citizens through knowledge and tools to understand their individual impact to improve the environment through their behavior, lifestyle and consumption.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
4	Aurora	https://www.aurora-h2020.eu/	APP: Participants to monitor their own behavioural patterns of heating and cooling, transport and use of electricity. In return, they will receive tailored suggestions on how they can lower their energy demand and reduce their costs.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Climate Neutral Smart Cities
5	Green Scent	https://www.green-scent.eu/	educate and empower the people of Europe to change their behaviour towards the environment by fostering empathy for the planet.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No

6	X-Polli	https://xpollination.org/about/	citizen science project, that encourages everyone to create, maintain and monitor pollinator-friendly habitats and act as pollinator stewards in society. Divided in smaller focuses	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
7	LTER-Italia	http://www.lteritalia.it/wordpress/?page_id=1034	Promoting research on long term ecosystem, socio-ecology. Citizen engagement does not seem crucial or key part of it	Adaptation to Climate Change	A Soil Deal for Europe
8	LIFE4pollinators	https://www.life4pollinators.eu/	Bioblitzs (CS element) to improve pollinator conservation.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
9	SPRING	https://www.ufz.de/spring-pollination/	CS for butterfly and pollinators monitoring.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
10	BEEWATCHING	https://www.beewatching.it/	Bee monitoring / GIS based pictures and digital open map.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
11	BUTTERFLY MONITORING	https://butterfly-monitoring.net/	CS Network for the European Butterfly Monitoring Scheme - eBMS.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
12	MeteoTracker	https://meteoTracker.com/	A mini-weather station designed for weather measurements on the move - based on a patented technology (RECS).	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
13	Minka	https://minka-sdg.org/	A platform for collecting biodiversity and environmental data, with a focus on the Sustainable Development Goals.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Restore our Ocean and Waters
14	National Plant Monitoring Scheme	https://www.npms.org.uk/	Survey plant species across different habitats in the UK.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
15	Amai!	https://amai.vlaanderen/	Questions on societal issues --> meeting with AI experts and co-design open calls --> 4 AI solutions funded (one category is environment and climate)	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
16	Climas	https://www.climas-project.eu/	Climate assemblies and living labs for deliberative democracy in climate policy	Adaptation to Climate Change	No

			making.		
17	CitSci4All	https://citsci4all.eu/	The Citizen Science For All (CitSci4All) project brings to the fore the participation of the Deaf and Hard of Hearing community in citizen science, in monitoring effects of climate change.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
18	Agora	https://adaptationagora.eu/	dynamic, pan-European community that creates and shares advanced tools to enhance awareness on climate change and adaptation solutions.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
19	Siren	https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/siren-project/siren-project	Recover meteorological data through crowdsourcing for digitising analog data from the past.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Restore our Ocean and Waters
20	On Drought (Nasuchu)	https://www.vlastnimpudu.cz/	Citizen science project investigating the current state of the agricultural landscape.	Adaptation to Climate Change	A Soil Deal for Europe
21	BeaverMap	https://beavermap.com/	Collect occurrence data of beavers, and also document experiences and perceptions of people about beaver effects.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
22	National French Glowworm and Firefly Observatory	http://www.astereilla.eu/NEOKIPOS/ovl.php	The NEOKIPOS project fosters sustainable urban gardening by empowering citizens to grow plants ecologically, enhancing green spaces and biodiversity.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
23	Crowd4SDG	https://crowd4sdg.eu/	Research the extent to which Citizen Science (CS) can provide an essential source of non-traditional data for tracking progress towards the SDGs, as well as the ability of CS to generate social innovations that enable such progress.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Climate Neutral Smart Cities
24	Naturens kalender	http://www.naturenskalender.se/	Collect phenological observations of plants and birds in Sweden.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No

25	IMPETUS	https://climate-impetus.eu	Creating packages of climate-change adaptation measures that other communities can use as a pathway towards a climate-neutral and sustainable future.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
26	FloodUp	https://www.floodup.ub.edu/ingles/ingles.htm	Collect observations of the impacts of natural hazards, such as floods, good practices of adaptation and bad practices or vulnerable zones.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Restore our Ocean and Waters
27	The Autumn Experiment	https://forskarfredag.se/massexperiment/hostforsoket-2013/	How climate change affects the autumn leaf development of different tree species.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
28	WeObserve	https://www.weobserve.eu/	An Ecosystem of Citizen Observatories for Environmental Monitoring –improves the coordination between Citizen Observatories and regional, European and international activities to tackle and research three key challenges that Citizen Observatories face: awareness, acceptability and sustainability.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Climate Neutral Smart Cities
29	GenerationSolar	https://generationsolar.ies.upm.es/about-sider	Solar energy community and promote data exchange between photovoltaic installation owners and scientists.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
30	POC21 - Harnessing the power of Crowdsourcing for Mountain Monitoring	https://www.mountainow.net/en/community/	Relevant crowdsourced observations on glaciers and rock-fall events.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
31	Ground Truth 2.0	https://gt20.eu/	The observatories focused on environmental indicators in urban and rural areas (e.g. water quality and quantity, air quality, phenology, biodiversity, heat, human-wildlife incidents) related to spatial planning issues as well as land and natural resources management.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Restore our Ocean and Waters

32	GrowApp	https://www.growapp.today/#/	With the GrowApp you can make time Lapse animations of your changing environment through seasons and even years.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
33	OpenTEK	https://openteck.eu/licci	Aims to bring insights from Indigenous and local knowledge to climate research. To do that, LICCI has created the OpenTEK citizen science platform.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
34	Melanogaster: Catch the Fly!	http://melanogaster.eu/	First European citizen science network on adaptation genomics.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
35	Digivol	https://volunteer.ala.org.au/	DigiVol is used by institutions around the world to digitise their data. This data may be in the form of museum object labels, field notebooks and diaries, recording sheets, registers or photographs.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
36	eBird	https://ebird.org/home	Organisations and communities support eBird to detect birds around the world and assist in scientific research to understand the needs of this species.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
37	Dawn Chorus	https://dawn-chorus.org/en/	Record bird sounds with mobile phones. Upload the recordings on the web and share experience with people around the world by uploading it to a soundmap.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
38	AlpTrees iNaturalist	https://www.alpine-space.eu/	ALPTREES uses iNaturalist platform to collect non-native trees abundance in the Alpine space in both forest and urban environment.	Adaptation to Climate Change	A Soil Deal for Europe
39	Frogs on the Road	http://konnadelfond.ee/index	With help of volunteers, rescuing frogs from the traffic and at the same time collecting data on amphibian spring migration to the breeding areas.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Other

40	DragonFly Ireland 2019-2024	https://biodiversityireland.ie/surveys/dragonfly-ireland/	Citizen Science survey of dragonflies and damselflies in Ireland. Volunteers take part through submitting casual records and conducting site surveys of water bodies and water courses.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Restore our Ocean and Waters
41	Micromascotas	http://micromascotas.ibericavis.es/galeria-de-acaros/	Citizen science experiment, the participants sent dust samples from their homes and through the application of microscopy and microbiology techniques, the detection of microorganisms such as bacteria, mites or fungi is analysed in the laboratory. The collected data provides information to create a map of microorganisms, or micro wildlife in the home education.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
42	Urban Birds Conservation Program of Vitoria-Gasteiz	https://www.vitoria-gasteiz.org/wb021/was/contenidoAction.do?idoma=es&uid=39e55291_14ac2d076b7f84	Knowing the distribution, abundance, conservation and population dynamics of the urban birds to know the natural heritage of Vitoria-Gasteiz municipality. -Improving the knowledge of biology and the responsible factors of the variation of populations of urban birds.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Climate Neutral Smart Cities
43	Sicily's Indigenous CyberTrackers	https://collettivorewildsicily.tilda.ws/page37071166.html	Exploring how 'indigenous' knowledge about wildlife and fire regimes can be aggregated using CyberTracker co-creating data driven landscape management supporting Rewilding.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Other
44	Observation	https://observation.org/	A platform for biodiversity citizen science project development and monitoring.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
45	Biodiversidad Virtual	https://www.biodiversidadvirtual.org/	A platform for biodiversity citizen science project development and monitoring divided into galleries.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No

46	Mysnowmap	NA	The snow maps are generated through a physically-based model that estimates snow evolution in proportion to the energy and mass balance of the snow pack. The input data are numerical weather predictions and in-situ snow measurements.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
47	PhenoTandem	https://web.ritmenatura.cat/projects/phenotandem/index-esp.htm	Catalonia has a long tradition of phenological observations with a group of persistent enthusiasts that has been extended by the EU H2020 Ground Truth 2.0 Citizen Observatory RitmeNatura.cat. Produces new phenology products derived from high resolution optical remote sensing (Sentinel-2) with the traditional phenological in-situ observations done by volunteers.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
48	BioRegistro	https://ambiente.cm-viana-castelo.pt/bioregisto	Citizens are invited to contribute to biodiversity knowledge, by doing species observation.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
49	PILZFINDER	https://www.spotteron.net/apps/global-community-science-projects/pilzfinder	Contribute mushroom observations map from all across Europe and get feedback from the expert of the Austrian Mycology Society. Preserve and expand the very knowledge about wild-growing mushrooms and toadstools and, introduce the topic to and engage the younger generation.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
50	Ant Picnic	https://scistarter.org/form/ant-picnic	Citizen science experiment to inform scientists about global food preferences of ants.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Other
51	Snapshot Safari	https://snapshot-safari.wordpress.com/blog/	Citizen scientists identify wildlife to help scientists understand the diversity and dynamics of wildlife populations across Africa. They classify animals from camera traps. It includes 26 projects	Adaptation to Climate Change	No

52	CoCoRaHS	https://www.cocorahs.org/	The Community Collaborative Rain, Hail, and Snow Network is a unique, non-profit, community-based network of volunteers of all ages who measure and report precipitation.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Other
53	Great Sunflower Project	https://www.greatsunflower.org/	3 pathways: (1) plant sunflowers and identify the effects of pesticides on pollinators; (2) pollinator count; (3) pollinator challenges to improve their habitats.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
54	Instantwild	https://instantwild.zsl.org/intro	Image classification from camera traps to improve knowledge on conservation. Infrastructuring of individual specific projects.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
55	Flora incognita	https://floraincognita.com/	An app to support the development of citizen science projects with the purpose of documenting plants in a specific area, and identifying selected species to address conservation-related queries.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
56	Obtectus Finders	https://www.obtectusfinders.rs/en/	A project to analyse the genetic variability of natural populations of seed beetles.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
57	Audubon Christmas Bird Count	https://www.audubon.org/community-science/christmas-bird-count	From December 14 through January 5 each year tens of thousands of volunteers throughout the Americas brave snow, wind, or rain, and take part in the effort. Audubon and other organisations use data collected in this long-running wildlife census to assess the health of bird populations, and to help guide conservation action.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
58	Celebrate Urban Birds	https://celebrateurbanbirds.org/	A platform that promotes inclusive, equity-based community science projects that serve communities that have been historically underrepresented or excluded from birding, conservation, and citizen science.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No

59	NestWatch	https://nestwatch.org/	A monitor program designed to track status and trends in the reproductive biology of birds: including when nesting occurs, number of eggs laid, how many eggs hatch, and how many hatchlings survive. The goal is to use the database to study the current condition of breeding bird populations and how they may be changing over time as a result of climate change, habitat degradation and loss, expansion of urban areas, and the introduction of non-native plants and animals.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
60	All About Birds	https://www.allaboutbirds.org/news/	A platform where to find information about North America birds, and resources to be part of the citizen science community led by Cornell Lab of Ornithology.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
61	The Horseshoe Count	https://horseshoecrab.org/about/count.html	A community driven effort to count crabs on 18 key beaches throughout Delaware and New Jersey.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
62	Budburst	https://budburst.org/	Contribution to understanding changes in the environment through the observation of the life cycle of plants.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
63	Community Snowobs	https://communitysnowobs.org/	A community science campaign to measure snow depths in mountain places too vast for researchers to monitor.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Restore our Ocean and Waters
64	Feld Food Forest	https://www.feldfoodforest.org/	A community that gathers to share and spread knowledge around permaculture, food and soil regeneration on the former airfield of Tempelhofer Feld in the heart of Berlin.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
65	Walk Up Aniene	https://asud.net/progetto/walk-up-aniene/	A participatory environmental monitoring action (monitoring the quality of biodiversity and the river functionality of the Aniene along the lower stretch of the river), to bring attention to the impacts produced by urbanisation and air and water contamination.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Climate Neutral Smart Cities

66	Terrifica	https://terrifica.eu/	Territorial Responsible Research and Innovation Fostering Innovative Climate Action: contributed to reducing the effects of climate change through engaging a diverse number of stakeholders, from scientific experts to citizens and decision makers, into climate mitigation and adaptation processes.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
67	InNat	https://eu-citizen.science/project/281	Local monitoring in Italy of 34 insect species (8 dragonflies, 2 orthopterans, 7 beetles and 17 butterflies), one endemic crayfish, 3 plant species and 2 habitats.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
68	OpenTEK	https://openteck.eu/domain?f=licci // https://www.licci.eu/	Documenting climate change impacts reported by communities and researchers and bringing these different data sources together to understand better how people and ecosystems are being impacted by climate change.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
69	Plant Letters	https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/cate draunesco/plant-letters	A collective action to transcribe handwritten letters received by the Botanic Garden of the University of Coimbra from ca. 1870 and 1928, from more than 1100 correspondents from around the world.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
70	LandSense	https://landsense.eu/	Connecting citizens with satellite imagery to transform current approaches to environmental decision making with Land Use & Land Cover (LULC) monitoring.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
71	Flooron	https://www.flooron.nl/	Citizens register the locations of plant species by crossing them off on a list in a predetermined area.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
72	Mapping Change	https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/zooniverse/mapping-change	Transcribe data from hand-written museum specimen labels to map biodiversity in the Midwestern US.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No

73	Fossil Atmospheres	https://fossilatmospheres.wixsite.com/fossilatmospheres	Researching how the cells of leaves on ginkgos have changed over time, and whether it is possible to use them to learn about the ancient atmosphere of the Earth.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
74	Alerta Forestal	https://www.alertaforestal.com/es/	A citizen science platform that analyses the state of health of Catalonia's forests through observations made by citizens. These observations are based on five forest disturbances that affect forests: processionary, box butterfly, drought, gale and snowfall.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
75	Citizen Arenas	https://citizenarenas.eu/en/	Raise citizens' awareness about environmental challenges and alternative resource management options related to water, biodiversity, waste, air, climate and energy.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Restore our Ocean and Waters
76	Ritme Natura	https://www.ritmenatura.cat/participa/	A project to collect data and phenological observations in Catalonia. Collected by citizens, this data is offered for consultation in real time with the aim of making it useful for decision-making.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
77	Schools and Satellites	https://tahmo.org/schoolandsatellites/	SaS aims to better quantify and understand precipitation patterns in Ghana in West Africa.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
78	Chronolog	https://www.chronolog.io/	Environmental photo monitoring project, it creates time lapses of ecosystems to better understand how these landscapes are changing.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
79	Andalusia Better With Science	https://andaluciamejorconciencia.fundaciondescubre.es/en/	A project that seeks the implementation of citizen science projects in Andalucía (Spain), in order to achieve improvements in the environment of a community through technology and innovation.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
80	Instant Wild	https://instantwild.zsl.org/intro	Contribute to animal conservation around the world, by identifying the species in	Adaptation to Climate Change	No

			the pictures.		
81	iSpot	https://www.ispotnature.org/	Monitoring biodiversity around the world through picture taking.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
82	ECF4CLIM	https://www.ecf4clim.net/	ECF4CLIM uses a multidisciplinary, transdisciplinary, and participatory approach to develop and validate a European Competence Framework (ECF) for transformative change, enabling the educational community to tackle climate change and support sustainable development.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
83	Safeguard	https://www.safeguard.biozentrum.uni-wuerzburg.de/	The project aims to contribute to reversing the loss of wild pollinators across Europe through increasing the general understanding of the direct and indirect drivers of pollinator declines, environmental, economic and societal impacts and delivering an integrated assessment framework as basis for a portfolio of effective policy and practice solutions.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
84	CoAdapta	https://www.coadaptalitoral.net/	A project to explore adaptation to climate change through qualitative and quantitative approaches, focusing on communities at risk.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
85	Vlinderstichting	https://www.vlinderstichting.nl/butterfly-conservation-europe/	The Butterfly Foundation is an organisation that brings together knowledge from the Netherlands and Europe about butterflies and dragonflies.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
86	EuropaBon	https://europa-bon.org/	The goal of this project is to work with stakeholders to identify user and policy needs for biodiversity monitoring and investigate the feasibility of setting up a center to coordinate monitoring activities across Europe.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No

87	PoshBee	https://www.poshbee.eu/	The project supports healthy bee populations, sustainable beekeeping and pollination across Europe. Integrating the knowledge and experience of academics, beekeepers and farmers.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
88	Biodiversity Genomics Europe	https://biodiversitygenomics.eu/	Accelerate the use of genomic science to enhance understanding of biodiversity, monitor biodiversity change, and guide interventions to address its decline.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
89	The Natural History Consortium	https://www.bnhc.org.uk/	A partnership of 14 members who work collaboratively on promoting citizen commitment to nature through collaborative action. By allowing workshops, events, involving a diverse audience in the integration of their techniques.	Adaptation to Climate Change	A Soil Deal for Europe
90	Izeltlabuak	https://www.izeltlabuak.hu/	Promoting citizen science through monitoring of arthropods in Hungary. Protecting natural values, creating a relationship between wildlife and humans, exploring and celebrating the beauty of biodiversity.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
91	SPIN-CITY	https://www.spiderspotter.com/en/	Monitoring spiders' colour and webs, to get information about how animals can adapt to climate change, using the spider color as a natural thermometer to better determine how quickly the city's environment heats up.	Adaptation to Climate Change	Climate Neutral Smart Cities

92	Report the Species	https://kc-prod-01.luz.si/realm/nukleus-zrsvn/protocol/openid-connect/auth?client_id=sporocivrsto-ui&redirect_uri=https%3A%2F%2Fsporocivrsto.si%2F&state=cea3c053-1f4b-4e30-92f3-14f124479b6b&response_mode=fragment&response_type=code&scope=openid&nonce=88d80eda-bfa7-466d-91b1-1e9c9dd262d3	The aim of the application is to collect data on the presence of 2000 species of particular conservation concern, for the Institute of the Republic of Slovenia for Nature Conservation.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
93	MammalNet	https://mammalnet.com/	A partnership between different scientific and academic institutions in Europe and local science fans, working together on wildlife research, management, and conservation.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
94	Naturens Kalender	https://www.naturenskalender.se/	The project has the mission to collect phenological observations of plants and birds in Sweden. Observations are made by citizen scientists throughout Sweden of: Plants budburst, flowering, ripening of fruits and berries, seed dispersal, autumn coloring and shedding of leaves, Bird appearance (continuous, not only spring and autumn migration), Autumn coloring of trees (school project).	Adaptation to Climate Change	No

95	Orchid Observers	https://orchidobservers.wordpress.com/	<p>The Orchid Observers project combined identification of orchid photos taken in 2015 with classifications and transcriptions of historical museum specimens to study how orchid flowering times are affected by climate change. The project had over 2000 volunteers taking part, made new observations of wild orchids in around 200 locations where particular species of orchid hadn't been recorded before, and submitted 50,948 classifications on the Orchid Observers online platform.</p>	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
96	Svinnkollen (The Food Waste Experiment)	https://forskarsfredag.se/massexperiment/svinnkollen/	<p>In the Food Waste Experiment, researchers will be developing and testing a new way to reduce food waste in Swedish schools: by providing more information and individual feedback. Food waste is responsible for over one-third of human-caused climate emissions.</p>	Adaptation to Climate Change	Other
97	Cricket Tales	https://crickettales.ex.ac.uk/	<p>Cricket Tales is a citizen science project, developed in collaboration between FoAM and the Wild Crickets researchers. By tagging events in the cricket CCTV videos, players contribute directly to research which will determine whether crickets have individual personalities. The results will tell us whether some crickets are more active in the morning, while others are more active at night. This tells us how flexible their lifestyles are, and how insects might cope as our climate changes. At the end of each game play, the latest results are displayed, including the data just contributed.</p>	Adaptation to Climate Change	No

98	Big Seaweed Search	https://www.bigseaweedsearch.org/	The distribution of seaweeds around the UK is changing. The project focused on scaling up a survey that was launched for the first time in 2009, to collect thousands of new observations and to focus on key environmental issues that need research. These issues are: (1) Rising sea temperature; (2) The arrival and spread of non-native species of seaweed; and (3) Ocean acidification (the sea becoming more acidic as a result of absorbing carbon dioxide from the air).	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
99	The Cyprus Herp Atlas	https://en.herpatlas.cy/	Atlas where is collected and organised existing data of the Cypriot herpetofauna: more than 6,600 localities for the 23 terrestrial reptiles and amphibians of Cyprus.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
100	Explorator	https://coicatalogue.uc.pt/explorator/	A crowdsourcing platform to digitise the largest Portuguese biological collection, and facilitate the investigation of botanists worldwide.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
101	BIODIVERSITY GO!	https://labpaisagem.pt/en/projetos/biodiversity-go-en/	The Biodiversity GO! application aims to encourage citizen participation in Citizen Science projects related to biodiversity that are respectful of both the physical integrity and natural behavior of the species.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
102	Vigie Nature Ecole	https://www.vigienature-ecole.fr/	Vigie-Nature École offers French teachers the opportunity to monitor what is known as “common” biodiversity by implementing scientific protocols with their students.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
103	Harnesstom	http://harnesstom.eu/en/citizen-science-home.html	Improve the accessibility and use of tomato genetic resources, and the knowledge about them generated in previous EU-research projects, in order to tackle the new challenges imposed by consumers and global change	Adaptation to Climate Change	A Soil Deal for Europe

			threats.		
104	Looking for Cowslips	https://www.cowslips.eu/	The aim of the project is to examine the patterns of heterostyly in cowslip populations all across Europe using a citizen science approach.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
105	Penguin Watch	https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/penguin79/penguin-watch	Count penguin adults, chicks and eggs in far away lands to increase understanding of penguins and their response to changes in the Southern Ocean.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
106	Scent	https://scent-project.eu/about-scent	Support the monitoring of land-cover/use changes using smartphones and tablets.	Adaptation to Climate Change	A Soil Deal for Europe
107	Alternet Europe	https://alternet-europe.eu/	ALTERNET is a network promoting sustainable land management and citizen science to enhance soil health and biodiversity. It supports ecological farming practices, engages communities, and fosters knowledge exchange.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No
108	COwLearning	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/cowlearning-875	The CowLearning project engages citizens in sustainable farming practices by observing and improving cow management for better animal welfare and environmental impact.	Adaptation to Climate Change	No

Appendix 3. “Climate Neutral Smart Cities” Mission’s projects

N°	Name of the project	URL	Project focus	EU Mission	Other EU Missions tackled
1	Telraam	https://telraam.net/en/what-is-telraam	Monitoring traffic data of vehicles, cyclists, pedestrians, and more from a citizen’s window.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
2	MOSAIC	https://mosaic-mission.eu/	CS for enabling co-creation for problems and solutions related to climate adaptation in cities.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change

3	Basecamp Research	https://www.basecamp-research.com/	DNA monitoring to create better food, better medicines and better products for the planet.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Restore our Ocean and Waters
4	Socio-BEE	https://socio-bee.eu/?page_id=584&lang=es	Monitoring air quality in cities to influence policies.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	A Soil Deal for Europe
5	Urban Relief	https://urbanrelief.eu/	Promotes collaboration between local communities and public authorities to address urgent climate issues related to urban greenspace planning, heat stress, and air pollution.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
6	Opush	https://opush.net/	Librarians, scientists, community managers, city administration and members of the general public are working together toward building a community of practice for sustainable urban development.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
7	Every Walk You Take	https://ciencia-ciudadana.weebly.com/	uHealth platform with personalised healthy routes according to the user geo-localisation, preferences and with real-time information on air quality and climate + CS data on barriers and facilitators for active living.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
8	URwatair	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/356188125_Citizens_in_the_Loop_for_Air_Quality_Monitoring_in_Thessaloniki_Greece	Map rainwater monitoring and air quality problems and to arrive at a set of best practices applicable to everyday life, on the basis of collaborative data analytics and knowledge extraction.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
9	The Acoustic Experiment – Akustikförsöket	https://v-a.se/2011/01/forsk-afredags-akustikforsok/	59 primary school classes in Sweden and 689 classes in Denmark took part in measuring the acoustic properties of their classrooms.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	

10	Citizen Science Garrotxa	https://twitter.com/olotsmart	Community in Olot using sensors from EU projects and others (Telraam, SCK, Flow sensor) to produce data on noise, air and traffic.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
11	Hush City	https://opensource.soundsources.org/	Free, citizen science app, which empowers people to identify and assess quiet areas in cities to create an open-access, web-based map of quiet areas, with the potential of orientating plans and policies for healthier living.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
12	Dnoses	https://dnoses.eu/	Monitor odour pollution control at local, national and global levels.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
13	NO2 NO Grazie	https://www.cittadiniperlaria.org/no2-no-grazie-2020/	Measure air quality in Italian main cities. Call to volunteers to place diffusion tubes.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
14	ISeeChange	https://www.iseechange.com/	Residents contribute real-time observations of climate events like flooding and heat waves, which ISeeChange transforms into actionable insights using AI and sensor data. These insights enable cities, engineers, and utilities to prioritise infrastructure investments and design resilient solutions. Infrastructuring of individual specific projects.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
15	Globe at Night	https://globeatnight.org/	An international campaign to raise awareness about the impact of light pollution, by measuring night sky brightness and uploading the data via laptop or phone.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
16	BiciZen	https://www.bicizen.org/	Collaborative platform that allows users to share data and information about cycling: bicycle parking, theft, safety, conflicts with other road users, or obstructions in cycle paths, and more.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
17	FulFill	https://fulfill-sufficiency.eu/	Studying lifestyle change towards sufficiency with a systemic approach across micro-, meso- and	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No

			macro-level.		
18	PS Lifestyle	https://pslifestyle.eu/	The project is closing the gap between climate awareness and individual action. Its aim is to inspire citizens to adopt a positive, sustainable, and healthier lifestyle by helping reduce their environmental impact.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
19	Compair	https://www.wecompair.eu/	Monitoring air quality in cities and regions, equipping citizens with easy to use sensors and data dashboards to supplement gaps in official data and to help drive the personal and policy changes needed for a sustainable future..	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
20	GreenSCENT	https://www.green-scent.eu/	The project is developing a competency framework embracing all Green Deal focus areas, which include sustainable transport, a zero pollution Europe and the transition to a circular economy.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
21	JUSTNature	https://justnatureproject.eu/	The objective of JUSTNature is the activation of nature-based solutions (NbS) by collaborating with citizens on ensuring a just transition to low-carbon cities, based on the principle of the right to ecological space.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
22	UPSURGE	https://www.upsurge-project.eu/	Assisting the urban transition by introducing the European Regenerative Urban Lighthouse: used as a best-practice reference framework to enable the implementation of targeted nature-based solutions.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
23	DivAirCity H2020	https://divaircity.eu/	The project's scope is to support the Sustainable Development Goals, valuing diversity and social inclusion to achieve innovative, creative, culture driven, green and carbon neutral urban society.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No

24	Connecting Nature	https://connectingnature.eu/	Position Europe as a global leader in the innovation and implementation of nature based solutions.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
25	FloodCitiSense	http://www.floodcitisense.eu/	To improve cities' resilience to floods, FloodCitiSense aims at developing a pluvial flood early warning service for, but also by citizens and city authorities.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
26	Liquency (1-2)	https://www.liquency2.org/	The goal of Liquency is to use bioindicator lichen species to produce air quality maps, involving educational communities (teacher training centers, teachers, students) in a citizen science project.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
27	CleanAir@School	https://www.eea.europa.eu/themes/air/urban-air-quality/cleanair-at-school/cleanair-at-school	citizen science campaigns to better understand children's exposure to a key air pollutant, nitrogen dioxide (NO ₂), in the school environment across Europe.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
28	Sensor.Community	https://sensor.community/en/	Originally named Luftdhaten. Mapping air quality through low cost sensors. Recently added noise pollution.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
29	AirNow	https://www.airnow.gov/aqaw-2021/citizen-science-sensors/	User air quality low cost sensors, also making learning about air quality measurement more accessible to communities.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
30	Balaguer Citizen Science Kiosks	https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/14/6/2544	Kiosk/totem with questionnaires and surveys for citizen inputs on sensors data.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
31	Air Quality Egg	https://airqualityegg.com/home	A network of citizen-led air quality monitoring stations using sensors to measure pollutants in urban areas.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
32	HackAir	https://www.hackair.eu/	HackAIR aims to raise collective awareness about the daily conditions of air quality and thermal comfort, as well as provide information about the probability of forest fires in Europe.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No

33	Mobility Urban Values - MUV	https://www.muuv2020.eu/	Uses gamification and citizen participation to encourage sustainable mobility in cities.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
34	PowerPoor	https://powerpoor.eu/	Citizens helping to address energy poverty by promoting renewable energy.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
35	CitiCAP	Can't find the original website	Smart city data collection to promote sustainable urban mobility.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
36	Twenergy	https://www.twenergy.eu/	Explore with citizen communities new twin-based solutions to improve renewable energy integration and explore the concept of energy communities	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
37	Amber	https://www.amber-forschung.de/en/Participate/	The AMBER project invites citizens in Berlin and Frankfurt (Oder) to track and analyse their mobility patterns using an app, focusing on factors like air quality, noise, and transportation preferences.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
38	Fulfill	https://fulfill-sufficiency.eu/	Sustainable lifestyles and behavioural change	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
39	Inclusive Mobility	https://impetus4cs.eu/toward-inclusive-urban-mobility-a-study-of-accessibility-for-people-with-disabilities-in-torun-poland/	The project studies accessibility barriers in public transport for people with disabilities in Toruń, Poland, gathering community data to inform improvements.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
40	Beepath	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-023-02328-3	The Bee Path in Ljubljana promotes urban beekeeping, connecting local beekeepers, schools, and cultural institutions to foster sustainability, biodiversity, and public awareness. It offers educational programs, enhances self-sufficiency, and serves as a tourist attraction.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No

41	PING	https://www.mobil21.be/en/initiatives/ping	<p>PING is a citizen science project that helps improve urban cycling by collecting real-time data on bottlenecks and unsafe conditions. Cyclists use an app to report issues, which are analysed to inform local policy changes, enhancing cycling infrastructure.</p>	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
42	Tra:well	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/tra-well-en	<p>The TRA:WELL project explores how active mobility (walking, cycling) impacts children's well-being, physical activity, and independence, focusing on urban environments. It involves collecting data from children to assess mobility behaviors and their correlation with health.</p>	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
43	On the Trail of Springs	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/on-the-trail-of-springs	<p>The "On the Trail of Springs" project in Austria focuses on mapping and protecting natural springs, essential water sources and habitats, in the Großes Walsertal Biosphere Reserve. Citizen scientists document spring locations, conditions, and surrounding flora and fauna, contributing to the long-term conservation of water resources and biodiversity in response to climate change impacts.</p>	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
44	City Layers	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/city-layers-1047	<p>The City Layers project invites citizens to map their urban experiences, sharing subjective data on city aspects like accessibility and safety. Using an app, participants contribute insights to improve urban design, fostering better communication between citizens and planners.</p>	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No

45	Making Sense	https://making-sense.eu/	Making Sense empowers citizens to use sensors for environmental monitoring, co-creating solutions to track pollution and improve urban sustainability. It fosters community-driven data collection in various European cities, addressing issues like noise, air quality, and radiation.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
46	DeVOTE	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/devote-740	The DeVOTE project explores the meaning of voting for citizens, analysing how it varies across individuals and countries, with a focus on its political, symbolic, and psychological aspects. It examines the impact of elections on citizens' political behaviors and attitudes.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Other
47	Fire Database	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/fire-database-536	The Fire Database project collects and analyses forest fire data in Austria, allowing public participation through online reporting and data visualisation. It tracks fire incidents, causes, and patterns, contributing to forest fire research and management.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Other
48	Urban Heat Stories	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/urban-heat-stories	The Fire Database project collects and analyses forest fire data in Austria, allowing public participation through online reporting and data visualisation. It tracks fire incidents, causes, and patterns, contributing to forest fire research and management.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
49	Trusted Spotter Network Austria	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/wettermelde-n-at-trusted-spotter-network-austria-649	The "Wettermelden.at / Trusted Spotter Network Austria" project enables citizens to report weather impacts in real-time using a web app, supporting weather warnings, research, and climate studies.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Other

50	Everyday morality	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/everyday-morality	The "Everyday Morality" project explores how people justify immoral behavior in everyday life, analysing excuses and rationalisations across situations. Participants observe and report these behaviors in media, personal encounters, and social contexts, helping researchers compare theoretical moral frameworks with real-life actions.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
51	Salon of Open Secrets	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/salon-of-open-secrets-980	The "Salon of Open Secrets" project uses citizen science and artistic methods to explore ethical hardware, addressing the impact of technology and conflict materials. Participants engage through interactive storytelling and workshops, creating green, fair hardware prototypes while connecting with global collaborators.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Other
52	Update Social	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/update-social-964	The Update Social project fosters collaboration across sectors to address social challenges, encouraging citizens to co-create solutions through ideation labs and accelerator programs. It strengthens social innovation ecosystems in Upper Austria by combining expertise from public services, civil society, and businesses.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
53	Recycling Heroes	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/recycling-heroes-916	The Recycling Heroes project raises awareness about e-waste and promotes recycling, involving students in surveys, eco-design, and prototype development. Participants analyse data, create sustainable products from e-waste, and contribute to improving recycling practices.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No

54	FLAMENCO	https://researchportal.vub.be/en/projects/flamenco-flanders-mobile-enacted-citizen-observatories	FLAMENCO project (FLAnders Mobile ENacted Citizen Observatories) is focused on creating a digital platform that allows citizens to engage in data collection and participate in citizen observatory campaigns. These campaigns are designed to address local concerns and facilitate collaboration in areas like mobility, environmental monitoring, and more, through mobile tools and community participation.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
55	Athena Citizen Science	https://athenauni.eu/citizen-science-how-ordinary-residents-help-solve-unexplored-problems/	The project "Citizen Science: How Ordinary Residents Help Solve Unexplored Problems" showcases the transformative role of citizens in research. It emphasises how everyday people contribute to scientific discovery and help solve complex issues by participating in data collection, formulating problems, and collaborating with scientists.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Other
56	Citizen Science as a Service (CSaaS)	https://northsearegion.eu/score/solutions/citizen-science-as-a-service-csaas/	Citizen Science as a Service (CSaaS) enables citizens to report flood events using a mobile app, collecting data on rainfall, river flow, and water levels. The app supports decision-making for local authorities by leveraging advanced techniques like deep learning, natural language processing, and image classification.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
57	RISE Program	https://www.rise-program.org/	The RISE program revitalises informal settlements in Makassar, Indonesia, and Suva, Fiji, integrating water-sensitive infrastructure to improve health and sanitation. The initiative co-designs solutions with local communities, emphasising ecological diversity and residents' well-being, especially children.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Restore our Ocean and Waters

58	Urban Flood Resilience	http://www.urbanfloodresilience.ac.uk/	The Urban Flood Resilience project develops solutions to mitigate urban flooding, using innovative approaches to improve flood risk management and resilience.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
59	Creating communities through citizen science	https://www.stantec.com/en/ideas/creating-communities-through-citizen-science	The "Creating Communities through Citizen Science" project involves engaging communities in flood risk management by collecting and analysing data to improve flood resilience. It empowers citizens to contribute to scientific research using modern technology and data-sharing platforms.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
60	Flood Watch	https://waterfrontalliance.org/2019/12/05/citizen-scientists-on-the-flood-watch/	The "Citizen Scientists on the Flood Watch" project engages volunteers in New Jersey and New York to track flooding and sea level rise. By contributing photos and data, participants help improve flood forecasts and contribute to climate change mitigation plans, enhancing community resilience.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
61	iSCAPE	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/689954/reporting	The iSCAPE project focused on improving air quality in European cities through passive control systems, behavioral interventions, and citizen engagement. It aimed to reduce air pollution, enhance climate resilience, and empower citizens in co-creating sustainable urban solutions.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
62	AIR Casting	https://scistarter.org/aircasting	AirCasting uses the AirBeam, a portable device that measures air quality, to help communities track pollution and health risks. Citizens can monitor particulate matter, temperature, and humidity, mapping hyperlocal pollution levels and advocating for clean air.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No

63	CanAIRIO	https://canair.io/index.html	CanAirIO is a citizen science initiative that uses mobile and static sensors to monitor air quality. Participants can build devices, track pollution levels, and share data, helping improve public health and policy through collaborative efforts.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
64	IQ Air	https://www.iqair.com/newsroom/citizen-science-air-quality-monitoring?srsltid=AfmBOOpEJDQTbUrt8wm0XEBM1FkbaoRu0HLQGRuGOuBbRBRH8FeErjT1	The IQAir citizen science project promotes public participation in air quality monitoring through the use of portable sensors. Volunteers contribute data to a global network, helping track pollution levels and enhance community health initiatives.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
65	SimRa	https://www.digital-future.be/rlin/en/research/projects/simra/	A platform for collecting data on bicycle routes and near miss incidents using smartphone-based crowdsourcing.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
66	Missing Maps	https://www.missingmaps.org/	Missing Maps is a global initiative where volunteers map areas vulnerable to disasters using OpenStreetMap, aiding humanitarian organisations with critical data for disaster preparedness and response.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
67	CSIRO Energise	https://www.csiro.au/en/Showcase/CSIRO-energise	CSIRO Energise was an app that allowed Australians to contribute to national energy research, providing insights into household energy use and generation. It aimed to enhance understanding of energy patterns, supporting efforts to build a sustainable and reliable energy future.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
68	Cities-4-People	https://civitas.eu/projects/cities-4-people	Collaborative citizen platforms for sustainable urban mobility.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No

69	Hollandse Luchten	https://hollandse-luchten.org/	Hollandse Luchten is a citizen science project in North Holland that uses sensor technology to monitor air quality, empowering residents to engage in discussions and actions to improve their environment. The project encourages collaboration among citizens, experts, and authorities to enhance the local quality of life.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
70	De Luchtclub	https://www.rotterdam.nl/de-luchtclub	The "Luchtclub" project in Rotterdam empowers citizens to monitor local air quality using sensors, contributing to environmental data and public awareness. Participants can track fine particulate matter levels, engage in workshops, and collaborate on solutions for better air quality in their communities.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
71	Delft Meet	https://www.tu-delft.nl/scd/waterlab/doe-mee-aan-onderzoek/project-7-delft-meet#:~:text=Wie%20%26%20waar%3Fvoor%20tenminste%20%20machten%20lang.	The Delft Meet project by TU Delft involves local residents in monitoring urban climate factors such as rainfall and temperature using sensors. Participants collect data to understand microclimates within the city, contributing to research on climate adaptation. The project encourages citizen science engagement for at least three months, fostering community-driven data collection.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	Adaptation to Climate Change
72	Tiny Forest	https://edu.earthwatch.org.uk/tinyforest	The Tiny Forest project by Earthwatch invites schools and communities to create dense, small forests in urban areas. These forests help mitigate climate change, improve biodiversity, and address environmental challenges like flooding and heat stress. Participants engage in citizen science activities, contributing to environmental research while connecting with nature and learning about sustainability.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	A Soil Deal for Europe

73	Check My Barangay // Making all voices count	https://ansa-eap.net/welcome-to-ansa-eap/projects/other-projects/check-my-barangay/ // https://www.makingallvoicescount.org/	The Making All Voices Count program supported innovative approaches to fostering accountable governance through citizen engagement and digital tools. It focused on using mobile and digital technologies to promote transparency, inclusivity, and responsive governance.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
74	Gender Digital Inclusion Map	https://www.itu.int/en/action/gender-equality/SiteAssets/Pages/equalSGDImap/map.html	The Gender Digital Inclusion Map by the ITU tracks global efforts to close the digital gender gap. It visualises progress and identifies areas needing improvement, helping policymakers address barriers to digital equality for women and girls. The tool emphasises data-driven decision-making to enhance gender-inclusive digital policies.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
75	Participatory Budgeting Map	https://www.participatorybudgeting.org/?attachment_id=10925	The Participatory Budgeting Project (PBP) empowers communities to directly engage in decision-making by allocating public funds to local projects. It promotes democratic participation and transparency, enabling citizens to shape their neighborhoods and influence policy decisions through inclusive, collaborative processes.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
76	Smart Dublin	https://smartdublin.ie/	Smart Dublin is a collaboration that uses technology and data to enhance public services and quality of life in Dublin. It connects citizens, businesses, and academics to address urban challenges and improve services such as mobility, environment, and smart governance.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No

77	Savvy Citizen Alerts	https://savvycitizenapp.com/	The Savvy Citizen app connects residents with their local government by providing real-time updates on events, alerts, and notices. It enables efficient communication, enhancing community engagement and ensuring that important information reaches citizens quickly through multiple channels like text, email, or the app.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
78	Blinds Square	https://www.blindsquare.com/	BlindSquare is an accessible GPS app designed for blind, deafblind, and partially sighted users, providing navigation and real-time location updates. It integrates with other navigation tools, offering voice-guided directions and detailed information about points of interest to support independent travel in urban and indoor environments.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
79	Smart Cities 4 All	https://smartcities4all.org/	Smart Cities for All aims to bridge the digital divide for people with disabilities and older citizens by promoting ICT accessibility in smart cities globally. The initiative provides tools and strategies to help urban planners and policymakers create inclusive, accessible environments.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No
80	Bike Ridership Data	https://www.bikedataproject.org/	The Bike Data Project collects and analyses cycling data to improve urban bike infrastructure. By crowdsourcing bike movement information, it helps cities enhance safety, planning, and policy for cyclists, fostering healthier and more sustainable communities.	Climate Neutral Smart Cities	No

Appendix 4. “Restore our Ocean and Waters” Mission’s projects

N°	Name of the project	URL	Project focus	EU Mission	Other EU Missions tackled
1	Marine Litter Watch	https://marine.litterwatch.discomap.eea.europa.eu/AboutMLW.html	Monitoring information with an APP about the litter (mainly plastic, also other materials) present in coasts. To influence the EU policy agenda related to preventing plastic waste.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
2	Fresh Water watch	https://www.freshwaterwatch.org/pages/about	Measure and monitor the health of rivers, lakes, streams, ponds and wetlands. To restore freshwater resources.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
3	The Sea Cleaners	https://www.theseacleaners.org/news/citizen-science-against-plastic-pollution/	Waste collection actions on land, in cities, on beaches or in the countryside.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
4	Smart Lagoon	https://www.smartlagoon.eu/	Monitoring Biodiversity. Find new modeling approaches to predict socio-environmental evolution in highly anthropised coastal lagoons, to understand how to prevent and minimally impact the natural balance of ecosystems	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
5	Plastic Pirates	https://www.plastic-pirates.eu/en	Prevent and eliminate pollution in European seas and waters.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
6	Plastic Origins	https://www.plasticorigins.eu/	A platform to collect, analyse and disseminate data on plastic pollution in rivers and encourage local authorities to take action.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
7	CS4rivers	https://www.cs4rivers.unisi.it/	Monitoring, preserving and restoring Italian and Mediterranean biodiversity.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
8	Gelavista	https://gelavista.ipma.pt/	Monitoring gelatinous organisms along the entire Portuguese coast, Azores and	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No

			Madeira.		
9	FLOW	https://www.flow-projekt.de/	Ecological monitoring of small rivers and streams.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
10	DRYVER	https://www.dryver.eu/	DRYRivERS app enables citizens to map and report drying cases in rivers and streams.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
11	Litter Intelligence	https://litterintelligence.org/	Collection of litter data, to provide insights about the problem, and actionate solutions in coasts of New Zealand.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
12	WeSenseIT	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/308429/reporting	Support citizens, communities and authorities in developing real-time situation awareness.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
13	Ice Watch	https://icewatch.met.no/	Program coordinating routine visual observations of sea-ice, including icebergs and meteorological parameters.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
14	Fuen Aragon	https://fuenaragon.com/	Identify and characterise the sources and springs of Aragon through citizen science. In addition, it will distribute the necessary material to assess the water quality of springs and fountains using nitrate concentration as an indicator.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
15	Algforskarsommar	https://www.su.se/forskning/forskningsprojekt/algforskarsommar	Citizens have been engaged in finding new knowledge about algae along the Swedish coast in the Baltic Sea.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
16	Observatorio Ciudadano de la Sequía	https://observasequia.es/	Citizen scientists will participate with the Observatory by sharing information of interest on the state of water and drought in their territories through web forms and social networks.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change

17	Schools and Satellite	https://tahmo.org/schoolandsatellites/	Measure the rainfall with self-made rain gauges that can be made using empty Fanta bottles, some concrete, a ruler and some glue. Teachers will be trained to take measurements with their students.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
18	Seaturtle	http://seaturtle.org/	Support the research and conservation efforts in the sea turtle community.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
19	Secchi Disk	http://www.sechidisk.org/	Open source hardware and an application to collect, measure and collect data on phytoplankton levels in the sea.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
20	Plankton Portal	https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/kelseyswieca/plankton-portal/	The plankton portal allows volunteers to classify different typologies of plankton recovered from Situ Ichthyoplankton Imaging System (SIIS) pictures, to better understand their life and function in the marine environment.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
21	Seasearch	https://www.seasearch.org.uk/	A network that collects information about the habitats, plants and animals that can be seen underwater, to track the health of the marine environments.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
22	Coral Watch	https://coralwatch.org/	Create public understanding of the value of reefs and provide opportunities to help save the reef through participation in scientific research and education.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
23	Jelly Watch	https://www.jellywatch.org/	A global public database documenting ocean conditions about jellyfish washing up, red tides, squid and mammal strandings, and other indicators of ocean health.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
24	Happy Whale	https://happywhale.com/	A project established to record whale sightings and build a better understanding of these creatures.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No

25	Earthdive	https://earthdive.com/	A global research project for millions of recreational scuba divers, snorkelers and others who can help preserve the health and diversity of the oceans.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
26	Shark Trust	https://www.sharktrust.org/	A project that works globally to improve the conservation status of sharks, skates and rays. Advocating for policy changes and generating collective action .	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
27	Eye on Water	https://www.eyeonwater.org/	The EyeOnWater colour app helps us to classify rivers, lakes, coastal waters, seas and oceans based on its colour (it can be used for both fresh and saline natural waters).	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
28	CrowdWater	https://crowdwater.ch/en/welcome-to-crowdwater/	Citizen scientists collect hydrological data in the categories water level, temporary streams, soil moisture and plastic pollution, using the CrowdWater SPOTTERON app. data quality is controlled by citizen scientists playing the CrowdWater game online.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
29	Marine Mammals in Belgium	https://www.marinemammals.be/	Repository of all Belgian marine mammal observations and strandings. It includes data about dolphins, whales and seals from Belgian waters.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
30	Slovenian dolphin project	https://www.morigenos.org/	A long-term program of research, monitoring, and conservation of the bottlenose dolphin species.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
31	From Sea to Street	https://equals.ea.eu/ongoing-projects/from-sea-to-street/	A citizen science initiative that collects ocean-themed murals across Europe and investigates which emotions they evoke in the viewer.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
32	OSPARITO	https://osparito.surfrider.eu/	A program to understand about the problem of water pollution, through a scientific protocol developed around the world of police investigation.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No

33	Observadores del mar	https://www.observadoresdelmar.es/	Multi-function platform, through which any citizen can collaborate with research by contributing their knowledge and experience and submit observations from the sea.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
34	Debris Tracker	https://debristracker.org/	Map plastic pollution. While the focus is specifically on oceans, data from land is also collected as it is an antecedent.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
35	Monitor Water	https://www.monitorwater.org/campaigns/ https://www.monitorwater.org/	Build a global youth movement to protect and restore our ocean planet.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
36	Smart Pebbles - SCORE	https://score-eu-project.eu/2023/10/06/raising-students-awareness-with-the-smart-pebbles-workshop/	Activities to engage students and experts in an experiment involving smart pebbles and advanced 3D scanning technology.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
37	Water Sentinels	https://www.ocean-alive.org/en/water-sentinels	A project for engaging citizens on collecting water samples and information about areas where pollution events happen at Sado estuary - Portugal.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
38	National PlasticWatch	https://www.tudelft.nl/scd/waterlab/doe-mee-aan-onderzoek/project-6-nationale-plasticwatch	Citizens report litter to help Rijkswaterstaat gain insights on the origin, transport and distribution of litter.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
39	Crowd Water	https://crowdwater.ch/en/welcome-to-crowdwater/	CrowdWater stands for an independent data collection by citizens for modelling of floods and droughts and as a supplement to existing measurements. The method is developed scientifically by the University of Zurich such that it can be applied in remote regions and in developing countries.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No

40	B.C. Cetacean Sightings Network	www.wildwhales.org	The B.C. Cetacean Sightings Network (BCCSN) collects sightings of cetaceans and sea turtles in the waters surrounding British Columbia, Canada using a network of citizen scientist observers.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
41	Beach Environmental Assessment, Communication & Health	www.ecology.wa.gov/Water-Shorelines/Water-quality/Saltwater/BEACH-program	The BEACH Program monitors the safety of saltwater swimming beaches from Memorial Day to Labor Day.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
42	Beach Watch	https://beachwatch.farallones.org/	Volunteers collect data on live and dead species of birds and marine mammals and human activities. They also report violations, detect oil pollution, and collect oil samples.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
43	Big Seaweed search	https://www.bigseaweedsearch.org/	Monitor the effects of environmental change on Britain's sea life by exploring the seashore and recording the living seaweeds	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
44	Biscayne Bay Drift Card Study	www.carthe.org/baydrift	Understanding our local ocean currents and how trash and other pollutants are transported.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
45	Bleach Patrol	https://www.ldeo.columbia.edu/~blinsley/Dr._B._K_Linsley/Coral_Bleach_Patrol.html	The "Bleach Patrol" are citizen scientists, surfers, divers, and general enthusiasts working together to map out the extent of global coral bleaching.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
46	Blue Water Task Force	https://www.surfrider.org/programs/blue-water-task-force	Since the inception of the Blue Water Task Force program more than 25 years ago, Surfrider volunteers have been out in their communities testing water quality at the beach.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
47	Cape Radd Citizen Science Day	www.caperadd.com/courses/citizen-science-day	Snorkel for science: people that buy the experience contribute with data about fishes and sharks	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No

48	Capturing our Coast	https://www.sams.ac.uk/science/projects/cocoast/	Learn more about a range of coastal species, from phenology to behaviour, and distribution to abundance.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
49	Caribbean Lionfish Response Program	www.corevi.org	Inspires communities to be better stewards of the environment through marine awareness education and hands on coastal programs.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
50	Chesapeake Bay Parasite Project	www.serc.si.edu/citizen-science/projects/chesapeake-bay-parasite-project	Studying (1) Size of the crab, (2) Sex of the crabs, (3) Presence or absence of outward signs of the Loxo parasite.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
51	Clean Sea LIFE	cleansealife.it	Awareness raising program on marine litter uniting all marine enthusiasts in Italy – divers, yachtsmen, fishermen, beach goers, students and citizens – in the protection of the Mediterranean sea.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
52	Coastal Observation & Seabird Survey Team (COASST)	www.depts.washington.edu/coasst	Monitoring local marine resources and ecosystem health.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
53	Coastal Ocean Mammal & Bird Education & Research Surveys (Beach COMBERS)	www.mlml.calstate.edu/beachcombers	Trained volunteers to survey beached marine birds and mammals monthly at selected sections of beaches throughout the Monterey Bay area.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
54	Community Seagrass Initiative	https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/mark-dot-parry/the-community-seagrass-initiative-seagrass-explorer	Raising awareness of declining seagrass habitats in South West England.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
55	Coral Reef Monitoring Data Portal	https://www.coris.noaa.gov/	Support, enhance, and widen the scope of existing monitoring efforts in Hawaii.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No

56	Crab Watch	www.seachangeproject.eu/seachange-about-4/crab-watch	<p>The goals of Crab Watch are:</p> <p>1) To raise awareness of the changing distribution of native and non-native crabs across Europe.</p> <p>2) To encourage people to explore and engage with their sea's ocean.</p> <p>3) To use citizen science to generate valuable scientific data and to make these results freely available.</p>	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
57	Digital Fishers	https://www.oceannetworks.ca/learning/post-secondary-education/citizen-science-resources/digital-fishers/	<p>Crowdsourced, ocean science observation game in which volunteers help answering:</p> <p>What environmental factors influence the distribution of species in the deep?</p> <p>What is the biodiversity associated with deep-sea environments?</p> <p>How do species interact with each other and with their environment?</p>	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
58	divers4oceanography	https://scistarter.org/divers4oceanography_website_not_active	To channel temperature & location data from divers to scientists.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
59	eOceans	https://www.eoceans.org/citizen-science	eOceans enables dynamic, collaborative, transparent, science-based, and informed decisions and actions by connecting data and results with all ocean stakeholders and rights holders.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
60	Fish Watchers	https://fishbase.mnhn.fr/fishwatcher/menu.php	Supports the uploading of fish observations and photos through the Internet, e.g. from divers or anglers. The information will be used to create current distribution maps to assist in monitoring trends in biodiversity.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No

61	FjordPhyto	https://fjordphyto.ucsd.edu/	Understanding changes in fjord ecosystems over the season. in the Antarctic.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
62	Floating Forests	https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/zooiniverse/floating-forests	Uncover the history of Giant Kelp forests around the globe - undersea.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
63	Follow & Learn About the Ocean & Wetland (FLOW)	https://www.amigosdebolsachica.org/	Preserve and monitor wetlands in California.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
64	Global Microplastics Initiative	www.adventurescientists.org/microplastic	Volunteers collected microplastic samples between 2013 and 2017 across the world's oceans and rivers to develop a global database.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
65	Gotham Whale	https://gothamwhale.org/citizen-science/	Web form to submit pictures about whales in the NYC area.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
66	Grunion Greeters	https://www.grunion.org/	Dedicated to a better understanding of the habits and habitats of beach-spawning grunion.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
67	Horseshoe crabs as homes	No Website https://scistarter.org/horseshoe-crabs-as-homes	Discover what species live on horseshoe crabs.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
68	IHO Crowdsourced Bathymetry	https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/iho-data-center-digital-bathymetry#csb	Steward the global collection of bathymetric data.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
69	Invader ID	https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/serc/invader-id	Track changes in coastal environments by identifying marine invertebrates.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
70	iSeahorse	https://projectseahorse.org/iseahorse/	iSeahorse harnesses the power of community scientists — anyone, anywhere in the world who sees a seahorse in the wild — to improve our understanding of these animals and protect them from overfishing and other threats.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change

71	Kelp Watch	https://serc.si.edu/participatory-science/projects/kelp-watch	Invasive plant in southern California. Action-based citizen science project provides guidance on what to do if encountered, including submitting pictures.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
72	Long-term Monitoring Program & Experimental Training for Students (LIMPETS)	https://limpets.org/	LIMPETS is a community science program that monitors the coastal ecosystems of California and helps youth develop a scientific understanding of the ocean.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
73	MangroveWatch	http://mangrovewatch.org.au/	Environmental health monitoring program for shorelines. Learning about mangroves and tidal wetlands in your region Discovering the many benefits tidal wetlands provide to our ecology Monitoring changes to shorelines and river estuary health. Helping with surveys of estuary and coastline condition	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
74	Manta Matcher	https://mantomatcher.org/overview.jsp	Machine learning based analysis of citizen observation of Manta globally. The algorithm provides researchers with a ranked selection of possible matches. Researchers will then visually confirm a match to an existing manta in the database, or create a new manta profile.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
75	Marine Metre Squared (Mm2)	https://mm2.net.nz/	Easy way to survey the intertidal community. Monitor a 1m x 1m square patch of your local shore once every season by recording the animals and plants that live there	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
76	MCS Wild Bottle Sightings	https://naee.org.uk/wildbottlesighting/	Campaign to clean Scottish shorelines from plastic bottles and report findings to the parliament to trigger policy. Engagement of schools.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
77	Mitten Crab Watch	https://www.dassh.ac.uk/citizen-science/mitten-crabs	Collectively build a data archive for biodiversity in the UK. On iNaturalist.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change

78	Monitor Tupinambás	https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/laris-sakawabe/monitore-tupinambas	To test a simple, quick and low-cost tool for the long-term monitoring of the organisms of MPAs, integrating employees, researchers and citizen scientists, in order to assist in the management of these areas.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
79	North Atlantic Right Whale Sightings Advisory System	https://www Fisheries.noaa.gov/resource/map/north-atlantic-right-whale-sightings	The Right Whale Sighting Advisory System (WhaleMap) aims to reduce collisions between ships and endangered North Atlantic right whales by alerting mariners to their presence. CS data integrated with several other sources.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
80	Ocean Sampling Day	https://www.microb3.eu/osd.html	Simultaneous sampling campaign of the world's oceans.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
81	Orcasound	www.orcasound.net	Orcasound connects your headphones to live hydrophones (underwater microphones), your ears to an ocean of sound. Help us explore and conserve marine life around the globe, starting with studying and saving the Southern Resident killer whales of the Pacific Northwest.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
82	OSPAR Beach Litter	https://www.ospar.org/work-areas/eiha/marine-litter/assessment-of-marine-litter/beach-litter	OSPAR monitors litter on 100m stretches at over 70 beaches in the North-East Atlantic.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
83	Our Radioactive Ocean	https://ourradioactiveocean.org/	Help scientists at the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution understand the ongoing spread of radiation across the Pacific and its evolving impacts on the ocean of Fukushima.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
84	Redmap	https://www.redmap.org.au/	Range Extension Database and Mapping project. This project invites Australians to share sightings of marine species that are 'uncommon'	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change

			to their local seas.		
85	Reef Check Mediterranean Sea	https://www.reefcheckmed.org/	Underwater monitoring with associated protocol.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
86	Reef Check Tropical	https://www.reefcheck.org/	Empowers people to save our reefs and oceans. Divers receive training and collect data.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
87	Reef Environmental Education Foundation (REEF)	https://www.reef.org/	Surveys for divers, interested people, snorkelers etc. to gather data about Florida's keys.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
88	Satellites Over Seals (SOS)	Website not active https://scistarter.org/satellites-over-seals-sos	Citizens scan satellite images of Antarctica searching for weddell seals.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
89	Scuba Tourism For The Environment	https://www.steproject.org/	Involve tourists for monitoring corals in the red sea.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
90	Seabird Ecological Assessment Network (SEANET)	https://seanetters.wordpress.com/	long-term collaborative effort to identify and mitigate threats to marine birds. SEANET volunteers conduct beached bird surveys in order to identify and record information about bird mortality along the east coast of the United States.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
91	Seabirdwatch	https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/penquintom79/seabirdwatch	Determine chick survival and breeding success, and how this varies across species ranges. Identify the causes of chick mortality (e.g. predation in the colony versus parents abandoning chicks) Record changes in the timing of breeding (e.g. arrival date, fledging date) and how this is	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change

			affected by environmental conditions.		
92	Seagrass Spotter	https://seagrassspotter.org/	Mapping seagrass globally.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
93	Seagrass Watch	https://www.seagrasswatch.org/seagrasswatch/	Mapping seagrass globally.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
94	Seawatch Submit a Sighting	https://www.seawatchfoundation.org.uk/	Monitor and improve conservation of cetaceans in the UK.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
95	SharkBase	https://scistarter.org/sharkbase	Map distribution of Sharks population.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
96	Smartfin	https://www.surfriider.org/programs/smartfin	Provide datasets for research from observations made through a smart fin sensor placed on surfboards on water temperature.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
97	South Africa Elasmobranch Monitoring (ELMO)	https://elmoafrica.org/	Sharks conservation. Mapping shark sightings and eggs spotting. larger focus on elasmobranchs (sharks, rays and skates).	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
98	Tangaroa Blue	https://tangaroablue.org/	Beach cleanup actions in WestAustralia and gathering data to prevent debris.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
99	The Great Nurdle Hunt	https://www.nurdlehunt.org.uk/	Collect Plastic Nurdles Worldwide.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
100	The Wetland Bird Survey (WeBS)	https://www.bto.org/our-science/projects/wetland-bird-survey	Monitors non-breeding waterbirds in the UK.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
101	TLC Juvenile Lobster Monitoring Program	http://www.lobsters.org/volunt/volunteer.html	To measure the health and productivity of lobster nursery habitats over space and time. We do this by measuring the abundance and distribution of juvenile lobsters and using mark/recapture techniques to investigate growth rates and survival.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change

102	Whale Track	https://whaletrack.hwtdt.org/	Advanced the understanding of species that visit seasonally or are resident in the Hebrides.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
103	Whales as Individuals	www.zooniverse.org/projects/tedcheese/whales-as-individuals	Identify individual Humpback Whales by clueing our computer algorithms into patterns on their tails.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
104	Wildbook for Whale Sharks	www.whaleshark.org	Track and monitor shark populations. The Wild Book for Sharks photo-identification library is a visual database of various shark encounters and of individually catalogued sharks.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
105	eDNA Citizen Scientist	https://www.smith-root.com/edna/edna-citizen-scientist-sampler	Network of collaborators to collect samples. That's why we built a sampling system that is compact, easy to ship, and has everything you need to quickly collect high-quality samples.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
106	SenseOcean	https://www.astrolabe-experiments.org/sciences-programs/sensocean-physical-oceanography/	Program of participatory science which aims at equipping the sailboats of the voluntary boaters with physical measurement sensors. By this way, anyone navigating on the open sea will be able to perform temperature and salinity measurements on the surface.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
107	Meteo Meduse	https://www.meteomeduse.it/meteomeduse	Citizen science project to report jellyfish in Italy.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Other
108	Sargassum Monitoring	https://sargassummonitoring.com/en/#google_vignette	Mapping Sargassum Seaweed as it is invading our coasts due to pollution and negatively affecting biodiversity.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
109	Ocean Initiative	https://www.initiativesoceans.org/it/	Waste and litter collection and classification from beaches.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No

110	Curl	https://www.surfrider.eu/our-missions/water-quality-and-health/curl-analyzing-surfers-exposure-to-chemical-pollution-in-the-ocean/	CURL aims to assess the level at which swimmers and surfers are exposed to chemicals found in coastal recreational waters.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
111	Care4Seals	https://focamonaca.it/care4seals/	Mix of different monitoring methods to preserve Monk seals in the central Mediterranean sea. A significant innovative part is based on environmental DNA analysis	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
112	Plankton Planet	https://planktonplanet.org/	To harness the curiosity and creativity of sailors and scientists to sample ocean plankton at unprecedented scales, for in depth evaluation of ocean health, biodiversity, & evolution.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	Adaptation to Climate Change
113	Oceano Vox	https://www.oceano-vox.com/en/	A community of Ocean citizens on a mission to accelerate marine research and protect our playground. For people with boats, sailors etc. that install a sensor.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
114	Coastal Flooding Community Science	https://gmri.org/projects/coastal-flooding-community-science/	Floods in coastal areas.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
115	Citcrops	http://www.citcrops.eu/	Monitoring water quality in urban coastal areas using citizen science.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
116	Ocean conservancy's International Coastal Cleanup	https://oceanconservancy.org/trash-free-seas/international-coastal-cleanup/ // https://www.coastalcleanupdata.org/	The Coastal Cleanup Data platform collects and analyses global data on ocean trash collected by volunteers. It helps guide solutions to reduce marine litter and improve coastal ecosystems. By entering cleanup data, participants contribute to addressing ocean pollution and supporting sustainable ocean health.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No

117	SOPHIE	https://sophie2020.eu/activities/citizen-science/	Citizens monitor the health of marine environments with a focus on cities near coasts.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
118	The Ocean CleanUP	https://theoceancleanup.com/	The Ocean Cleanup is dedicated to developing innovative technologies to remove plastic from the ocean, focusing on the Great Pacific Garbage Patch. Their efforts include large-scale systems to collect waste and prevent more plastic from entering waterways.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
119	Tamaragua	https://www.preciousplasticgrancanaria.com/tamaragua/	Tamaragua is a citizen science project focused on monitoring microplastics along beaches in Gran Canaria. Volunteers participate in activities like sampling beaches, raising awareness through videos, and contributing data to scientific research on plastic pollution. It aims to involve the community in protecting coastal environments through education and collective action.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No
120	OpenLitterMap	https://openlittermap.com/	OpenLitterMap is a global citizen science platform that enables individuals to map and track litter locations, raising awareness about plastic pollution. It allows users to log data about waste, helping inform cleanup initiatives and environmental policies through crowdsourced information.	Restore our Ocean and Waters	No

Appendix 5. “Cancer” Mission’s projects

N°	Name of the project	URL	Project focus	EU Mission	Other EU Missions tackled
----	---------------------	-----	---------------	------------	---------------------------

1	Transbiome	https://www.transbiome.org/accueil	Transwomen: to gain a better understanding of the microbial diversity and composition of the microbiomes that are found in neo-vaginas.	Health more generally	Cancer
2	Obstretic Coevolution	https://www.obstreticcoevolution.eu/en/	Characterise and reduce postpartum depression through coevolving obstetric practices, including women and medical experts.	Health more generally	Cancer
3	FEMale	https://findingendometriosis.eu/	Connect different fields and sectors to turn genetic and epidemiological insights into practical clinical tools for better diagnosis and care decisions.	Health more generally	Cancer
4	Cell Slider	https://www.cellslider.net/ // https://scistarter.org/cell-slider	Cell Slider was a project that asked volunteers to analyse tissue samples that had been donated to future research by cancer patients who had been treated on clinical trials.	Cancer	No
5	Trailblazer	https://scistarter.org/cancer-research-uks-trailblazer-project/ // https://www.cancerresearchuk.org/get-involved/citizen-science/the-projects#citizenscience3	A small-scale web-app designed to continuously improve citizen scientists' ability to spot cancer cells in different types of tissue samples.	Cancer	No
6	Genigma	https://genigma.app/es/	Co-created game for smartphones to assemble with citizens the 3D genomes of most used cell lines for cancer research.	Cancer	No
7	NIH Citizen Science Working Group	https://www.cancer.gov/research/resources/citizen-science/working-group	Integrate CS in cancer research: collection of projects.	Cancer	No
8	Citizen Science at UF Health Cancer Centre	https://cancer.ufl.edu/community-2/citizen-scientists/	Active contribution of cancer survivors in cancer research definition: scope, consent, engagement.	Cancer	No

9	Citizen science lures gamers into Sweden's Human Protein Atlas	https://www.proteinatlas.org/about/history/2018+Deep+learning+and+citizen+science	The citizen science initiative entices gamers to help analyse around 250,000 images of stained tissue samples by embedding the scientific data within EVE Online, a futuristic role-playing game with around half a million subscribers that has been running for more than a decade.	Cancer	No
10	Re-Mend	https://v-a.se/eng/projects/public-engagement-projects/re-mend/	Improving early detection and prevention measures for mental health issues.	Cancer	No
11	CitieS-Health	https://www.citieshealth.eu/	Five pilots on environmental epidemiology and CS.	Cancer	Health more generally
12	SEAWave	https://seawave-project.eu/	Assess risk assessment of 5G RF EMF - serious game for people to gain literacy about the topic - education.	Cancer	Health more generally
13	Quality of life of patients living with vascular LIVER diseaseS Developing research on the social impact of rare diseases	https://www.livesproject.eu/	The aim of the project is to develop the research on the social impact of rare diseases and to develop patient and public involvement in the making of qualitative research with and by patients.	Cancer	Other
14	InfluenzaNet	https://influenzanet.info/home	Create a map of incidence and additional information about spread and details of seasonal flu. European volunteers in 12 countries to help us track these diseases by self-reporting their health status every week.	Cancer	Other
15	Sleep: One Third of Life	https://ayeletlab.net/technion.ac.il/sleep-one-third-of-life/	Designed for middle and high school. We invite teachers to take part in the project and investigate students' sleeping habits in modern multi-screen and artificial light society.	Cancer	Other
16	The Neureka Project	https://www.neureka.ie/	Neureka gathers data from users and also provides users with the latest in scientific findings relevant to brain health (dementia and mental	Cancer	Other

			health).		
17	STEP CHANGE: Infectious Disease Outbreak Preparedness	https://stepchangeproject.eu/citizen-science-initiatives/infectious-disease-outbreak-preparedness/	Citizen Science Initiative will co-design a citizen science strategy for infectious disease preparedness in Italy, in order to raise awareness on the role of citizen science as a relevant tool to be incorporated into institutional and scientific practices for a better management of infectious disease outbreaks.	Cancer	Other
18	STEP CHANGE: Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease	https://stepchangeproject.eu/citizen-science-initiatives/non-alcoholic-fatty-liver-disease/	To develop a better understanding of the experiences of patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease taking part in a clinical intervention as well as in a lifestyle and weight loss programme.	Cancer	Other
19	Machine learning as a citizen science tool to improve the quality of life of older people and their caregivers.	https://gerontec.uji.es/wordpress/	Bring the research done by scientists in the fields of psychology and computer science to society in a participatory and accessible way, through an issue of social interest such as the early detection of loneliness, social isolation and stress in older adults.	Cancer	Other
20	Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker	https://www.bsq.ox.ac.uk/research/covid-19-government-response-tracker	Collects data on what measures governments have put in place, and which ones are working in the fight against COVID-19.	Cancer	Health more generally
21	Proyecto COVID-PHYM	https://iberivis.es/proyecto-covid-phym-entrevista-con-javier-martinez-de-salazar/	Research on genetics and protein for effective drugs against covid through the support of the thousands of personal computers that are part of Iberivis' distributed computing platform ('Iberivis BOINC'), to which anyone who wants to collaborate can join.	Cancer	Other

22	BELpREG pregnancy registry in Belgium	https://belpreg.be/en/	Address the issue that little is known about medication during pregnancies. The BELpREG pregnancy registry, a unique citizen science research project in Belgium, wants to address the knowledge gap on medication safety in pregnancy by using real-world data registered by (pregnant) women.	Cancer	Other
23	Colony B	https://csb.cs.mcgill.ca/colonyb/#game	Citizen science game where players grow colonies of bacterias, and through cluster identification, to generate new bacterias.	Cancer	Other
24	Brain Explorer	https://brainexplorer.net/	Game to solve puzzles and help research to understand better brain patterns.	Cancer	Other
25	STRATUM	https://www.stratum-project.eu/	STRATUM will develop a clinically demonstrated 3D Decision Support Tool for brain surgery guidance and diagnostics based on multimodal data processing through Artificial Intelligence algorithms that will be integrated as an energy-efficient Point-of-Care computing tool.	Cancer	No
26	Citizen health	https://www.citizen.health/	Use the power of shared experiences to provide relief to patients and families navigating rare and complex conditions.	Cancer	Health more generally
27	MyPeBS (My personal Breast cancer Screening)	https://www.mypebs.eu/the-project/	The project involves citizens in the design and implementation of personalised screening strategies, incorporating data from genetic, lifestyle, and environmental factors.	Cancer	No
28	iPoP	https://med.stanford.edu/ipop.html	Involves citizens in health data collection, focusing on cancer and other diseases.	Cancer	Health more generally
29	Rare Cancers Europe	https://www.esmo.org/policy/rare-cancers-working-group	Integrates patient involvement in cancer research, particularly for rare cancers. The initiative uses citizen-driven data to develop better care strategies	Cancer	No

			and research directions.		
30	All of US	https://www.joinallofus.org/	Collects health data from a diverse group of citizens, including cancer patients, to accelerate research into prevention, treatment, and cures.	Cancer	Health more generally
31	Citizen Endo	https://citizenendo.org/	This project focuses on endometriosis but also contributes to cancer research by collecting citizen-generated data on hormonal disorders, which are sometimes linked to certain types of cancers.	Cancer	Health more generally
32	EUCAIM	https://cancerimage.eu/	Cancer Image Europe provides a platform for researchers, clinicians, and innovators to access diverse cancer images, enabling the benchmarking, testing, and piloting of AI-driven technologies.	Cancer	Health more generally
33	Node Code Breakers: looking for patterns in lymph nodes	https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/effeli/node-code-breakers-looking-for-patterns-in-lymph-nodes	Analyse images of lymph nodes from breast cancer patients to generate data that will be used to help improve our AI model performance.	Cancer	No
34	Genes in Space	https://scistarter.org/play-to-cure-genes-in-space-7/ https://www.cancerresearchuk.org/get-involved/citizen-science/the-projects#citizenscience3	Genes in Space was the world's first mobile game dedicated to analysing cancer data.	Cancer	No
35	Reverse The Odds	https://scistarter.org/reverse-the-odds/ https://www.cancerresearchuk.org/get-involved/citizen-science/the-projects#citizenscience3	A game to help complete a muscle-invasive bladder cancer study.	Cancer	No

		enscience3			
36	The Impossible Line	can't find the website. general info from the UK cancer's research institute: https://www.cancerresearchuk.org/get-involved/citizen-science/the-projects#citizenscience3	A game to help better understand how mutations cause different subtypes of breast cancer.	Cancer	No
37	EyeWire	https://eyewire.org/explore	EyeWire is a game where citizens map the neural networks of the brain.	Cancer	Health more generally
38	Gut Instinct	https://www.gutinstinct.org/	This citizen science project focuses on the relationship between gut health and diseases like cancer.	Cancer	Health more generally
39	Mark2Cure	https://mark2cure.org/	Mark2Cure is a citizen science platform where volunteers read scientific literature and help categorise information related to diseases, including cancer.	Cancer	Health more generally
40	Foldit	https://fold.it/	A game-like platform where citizens can help researchers by solving puzzles related to protein folding.	Cancer	No
41	DreamLab	https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=au.com.vodafone.dreamlabapp&hl=es	An app by Vodafone for citizens to donate their computational power to analyse data for cancer research.	Cancer	Health more generally
42	World community Grid - mapping cancer markers	https://www.worldcommunitygrid.org/research/mcm1/overview.s	Part of a larger platform where people donate their computers' processing power	Cancer	Health more generally
43	European cancer Patient Coalition	https://ecpc.org/	Coalition of cancer patients for advocacy. Organises campaigns where people can take active part.	Cancer	Health more generally

44	EUCanImage	https://eucanimage.eu/	An EU-funded project developing a cancer imaging platform to enhance AI-based cancer research, involving patients and citizens in data sharing.	Cancer	Health more generally
45	Patient Innovation	https://patient-innovation.com/	Platform to connect patients, caregivers, and collaborators from all over the world, enabling the sharing of solutions, treatments, devices, and other relevant knowledge.	Cancer	Health more generally
46	DataSavesLives	https://datasaveslives.eu/case-colorectal-cancer	Within the mission of fostering health data sharing, a project on cancer research for early detection of colon cancer.	Cancer	Health more generally
47	European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition (EPIC)	https://epic.iaarc.fr/	Large-scale collaborative project that studies different populations from countries across Europe to investigate the relationships between diet, nutrition, lifestyle, and environmental factors, and the incidence of cancer and other chronic diseases.	Cancer	Health more generally
48	Let's Cure Cancer	https://letscurcancer.org/	Encourages public participation in fundraising and awareness campaigns to support cancer research.	Cancer	No
49	Dental Disease Detection	https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/huhui/dental-disease-detection	Part of a research of the University of Surrey, a tool for diagnostics of dental diseases. The research consists of developing an AI-assisted workflow to automatically identify multiple common dental diseases from an x-ray radiograph and generate a diagnosis report.	Health more generally	No
50	Cancer Crusade	https://cancercrusadegame.com/	A game to help improve cutting-edge cancer research.	Cancer	No
51	Malaria Spot	https://malariaspot.org/en/about-us/	A videogame to advance Malaria research. 20 people playing = 1 scientist.	Health more generally	No
52	Phylo	https://phylo.cs.mcgill.ca/	A game to solve a puzzle and genetic disease research.	Health more generally	No

53	The Cure	http://genegames.org/cure/	Crowdsourcing Game for Gene Selection for Breast Cancer Survival Prediction.	Cancer	No
54	The Omega Cluster	https://scistarter.org/the-omega-cluster	A game to support research with AI on cancer treatment.	Cancer	No
55	GeSort	https://gesort.cs.umanitoba.ca/	A game to solve genomics sorting problem.	Health more generally	No
56	Stall Catchers	https://stallcatchers.com/main	A game to help speed up Alzheimer's disease research at Cornell University.	Health more generally	No
57	The Psychological is Participatory	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/the-psychological-is-participatory-954	The project "The Psychological is Participatory" explores feminist, critical participatory action research with women's counseling centers. It empowers women, particularly marginalised groups, to document their life stories and experiences through storytelling and visual methods, reflecting on the role of counseling in shaping their lives. It emphasises the importance of incorporating clients' perspectives in psychology and aims to create social change through collaborative research.	Health more generally	Cancer
58	Hero	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/hero-937	The HERO project develops a digital information tool for cardiac rehabilitation, co-designed with patients and healthcare professionals to improve care.	Health more generally	Cancer
59	KoKo-Health	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/koko-health-en	The KoKo-Health project co-designs a health literacy model with children and adolescents, enhancing their ability to make informed health decisions.	Health more generally	Cancer
60	Pollen Diary	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/pollen-diary	The Pollen Diary allows users to track allergic symptoms and medication, correlating them with pollen levels, aiding diagnosis and treatment.	Health more generally	Adaptation to Climate Change

61	Patio Patient Involvement in Oncology	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/patio-746	The PATIO project empowers prostate cancer patients and caregivers by co-designing a digital tool to enhance daily life and treatment.	Cancer	No
62	Ideenbox (Box of Ideas)	https://www.citizen-science.at/en/projects/ideenbox-711	The Ideenbox project collects health-related issues from citizens to co-develop solutions with researchers, fostering collaborative innovation in healthcare.	Health more generally	Cancer
63	Saca la Lengua	https://www.sacalalengua.org/sobre-el-proyecto/	The "Saca la Lengua" project involves citizens in the study of oral microbiomes, aiming to understand bacteria diversity and its health impact.	Health more generally	Cancer
64	ISALA project	https://isala.be/en/	Started in Belgium, the largest vaginal microbiome study in the world, with already sister projects in as many as 20 countries.	Health more generally	No
65	Watch What Matters	https://itpcglobal.org/our-work/watch-what-matters/	Watch What Matters is a community monitoring and research initiative that gathers data on access to and quality of HIV treatment globally	Health more generally	No
66	My Village My Home	https://www.jsi.com/resources/my-village-my-home-a-tool-to-optimize-immunization-coverage/	The "My Village My Home" tool helps communities track infant immunisation status, improving vaccine coverage and encouraging local ownership.	Health more generally	No
67	Zoe Health	https://health-study.zoe.com/	The ZOE Health Study collects data on nutrition, health, and lifestyle to understand how these factors affect individual health outcomes.	Health more generally	No
68	GLOBE Mosquito Habitats Mapper	https://observer.globe.gov/do-globe-observer/mosquito-habitats	App-based tool that will help you document mosquito habitats and identify mosquito types.	Health more generally	No

69	Community Treatment Observatory	https://www.aidsdatahub.org/sites/default/files/resource/itpc-community-treatment-observatory-model-explained-2019-summary.pdf	Using metrics and indicators informed by, and meaningful to communities of people living with HIV, this data is used to identify gaps in essential services, and to inform advocacy for improving them	Health more generally	No
70	Ritshidze	https://ritshidze.org.za/	Community led clinic monitoring in South Africa.	Health more generally	No
71	POWEMOM	https://www.scripps.edu/support-us/powemom/	Mothers-to-be share their data for research on maternal mortality causes.	Health more generally	No
72	BigO	https://bigoprogram.eu/mybigo-app/	Monitor behaviours of people to improve research on obesity prevention.	Health more generally	No
73	Snakebite Information and Data Platform	https://www.who.int/teams/control-of-neglected-tropical-diseases/snakebite-envenoming/snakebite-information-and-data-platform	The WHO Snakebite Information and Data Platform provides tools for managing, analysing, and visualising data on venomous snakes and antivenoms.	Health more generally	No
74	Careables	https://www.careables.org/	Careables.org connects makers, healthcare professionals, and patients to co-design customisable, open-source solutions for health challenges using digital fabrication tools.	Health more generally	No
75	Shubra El Khema Smart clinic	https://globalinnovationgathering.org/shubra-el-khema-smart-clinic/	The Shubra El Khema Smart Clinic offers affordable healthcare services through a participatory model, combining local volunteers and technology to enhance access.	Health more generally	No
76	CoAct	https://coactproject.eu/	The CoAct project engages citizens as co-researchers to address social issues like mental health, youth employment, and gender equality through participatory	Health more generally	No

			research.		
77	ISALA project	https://isala.be/en/	Isala is a citizen science project studying the female microbiome, collecting data through swabs to improve women's health globally.	Health more generally	No

